

TWO PATHWAYS

WHAT WE'LL SEE DOWN
TWO PATHWAYS TO ZERO
EMISSIONS FROM BUILDINGS

June 2025

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This report is the main report on the Boltzmann Institute’s Two Pathways project. The project’s full title is, “What We’ll See Down Two Pathways to Zero Emissions from Buildings.”

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Foreword

Early in 2022, we learned that Brookfield Infrastructure had sold the Toronto part of Enwave Energy for an amount likely in excess of two billion Canadian dollars. Enwave was the private-sector successor to a crown corporation, the Toronto District Heating Corporation (TDHC), formed in the early 1980s at the initiative of the then City of Toronto at a cost of under \$100 million. This news stimulated discussions among several Ontario-based retirees who had been involved at one time with TDHC, a group later described by a fan as “a gang of grandpas.”

The discussions were productive retirement therapy in that they led to the establishment of the Boltzmann Institute, a federally incorporated, not-for-profit corporation named after Ludwig Boltzmann, a 19th century Austrian physicist and philosopher, a founder of the science of thermodynamics.

The Institute’s mission is broad: “to help eliminate harmful emissions from human energy use through research and education.” The shared interest of the Institute’s founders and the evident importance of emissions from space heating – likely the main source of greenhouse gases in most Canadian cities – led to an initial focus on the challenges of building decarbonization. The new Institute entered a federal government’s competition among universities and think tanks for research funding. It was successful in being awarded a contribution of \$750,000 towards conduct of the project reported here, as noted on Page 2 of this report.

The Institute’s directors and members believe that much has been achieved during its three years of existence, largely on account of the opportunity to carry out the present project. In the course of its conduct, we believe we’ve sown enough doubt among policy-makers about the feasibility of widespread electrification of space heating to allow for serious discussion of alternatives. With this report, a collaborative exercise involving the many people listed on Page 10, we hope to make much more impact.

Richard Gilbert
Chair, Board of directors
The Boltzmann Institute
June 5, 2025

Abstract

This report rigorously compares two primary pathways for decarbonizing building heating in Ontario: widespread electrification using heat pumps and extensive deployment of thermal networks (district energy). Through comprehensive data analysis, literature review, and expert consultation, the study quantifies the technical, economic, and social implications of each pathway. Findings reveal that electrification, especially with air-source heat pumps, would require a massive and costly expansion of the electricity system, with significant challenges during winter peaks. In contrast, thermal networks could reliably serve up to 70% of Ontario's buildings at a much lower societal cost. This will rely on use of waste heat, combined heat and power, and large-scale thermal storage. Where thermal network service is viable but not yet available, installation, on an interim basis, of air-source heat pumps sized to replace end-of-life air conditioners would avoid the need for expensive power system upgrades while achieving modest GHG reductions; gas furnaces would be kept for use below about +4 °C. All buildings should be promptly converted to thermal network service when it becomes locally available. For the 30% or more of buildings where thermal networks will not be viable, ground-source heat pumps are a better option than air-source heat pumps, due to their much lower peak power demand. Long-term high efficiency can be assured by installing solar thermal collectors to restore heat taken from the ground. Strategic planning for provision of heating and the coupling of electricity and heat infrastructures will be key to efficient and affordable achievement of net-zero emissions by 2050.

Summary

This is the main report on a two-year project that challenges a salient feature of federal and provincial approaches to decarbonization of space heating, presently a major source of greenhouse gas emissions. Proposals for wholesale electrification of space heating, chiefly through deployment of heat pumps, are shown to be unaffordable and essentially unworkable. The alternative of substantial deployment of thermal networks to up to 70% of Ontario's buildings is found to be much more feasible and affordable. Here are the main conclusions drawn from the project:

- Both the Electrification and Thermal Network pathways can theoretically achieve net-zero emissions from buildings but the cost and primary energy requirements of these two pathways are very different.
- Electrification of heating, in high population dense cities in a cold country like Canada, will dramatically lower the operating capacity factor of the electricity system. That will have a significant adverse impact on future electricity rates - well above normal inflation rates.
- Electrification of heating using an optimal mix of various zero-emission generation technologies will result in the waste of primary energy production (waste heat) that is actually larger than the heat energy needed to provide space and water heating.
- Careful thermal energy planning and selection of pathways best suited to local conditions (population density, sources of waste heat, etc.) is essential to minimize primary energy production and consumer total energy costs, while actually achieving zero emissions from buildings with any reasonable degree of certainty by 2050.

The long-form title of the project is in the page header above. Its short form is the Two Pathways project. It was conducted by the Boltzmann Institute between April 2023 and March 2025, and managed by John Stephenson (jstephenson@bi-ib.ca). It was supported by a contribution from Environment and Climate Change Canada noted on Page 2.

As well as the present report, products of the project included six annexes to the report, also described below. One of these six annexes includes 55 short reports on the implication of building decarbonization for almost all of Ontario's local (electricity) distribution companies (LDCs). Other outputs have included a conference on municipal thermal energy planning (see Section 10 below), a [video](#) on the project, and six issues of the Boltzmann Institute's [District Energy Digest](#). (Click on the live links in the last sentence to access the indicated material. For access to the annexes, click on the respective links in the descriptions below.)

What follows is a section-by-section description of this report and then a description of each of the six annexes. Conclusions from each section and overall conclusions are in Section 13 and are mostly not repeated in this Summary.

Section 1 begins by noting that to heat all buildings in Canada without using natural gas is a bigger problem than has been recognized. It sets out the objectives of the Two Pathways project. They were chiefly to compare and contrast widespread electrification of space heating and widespread deployment of thermal networks, chiefly from a broad Ontario perspective – with

evident national implications – and with particular reference to LDCs and First Nation communities. This section notes the project's accomplishments and challenges, sets out its ten key findings, and describes the organization of the present report. Here are the topics of the key findings:

- Building retrofits
- Air-source heat pumps
- Thermal networks
- Ground-source heat pumps
- Sector coupling
- Transition strategy
- Energy efficiency
- Application to Indigenous communities
- Distributional consequences
- Legal and financial ability

Section 2 provides a synopsis of the two main pathways to building decarbonization, the electrification and the thermal networks (TN) pathway. In the electrification pathway, space heating is provided mostly by building-based heat pumps powered by non-carbon sources, notably nuclear, hydroelectric, wind, solar, and biomass, with limited RNG also available for peaking use. The TN pathway involves delivery of heat to buildings from central, non-carbon sources, usually as hot water, by an underground network of pipes, i.e., by a thermal network. Discussed is what may be the optimal pathway, a combination of the two with the TN pathway predominant in urban and suburban areas and the electrification pathway predominant in rural and other low-density areas.

Section 3 describes the methods employed in the project. These have included an extensive literature review and compilation of an extensive bibliography. Data sources are described as are the subject-matter experts who have been consulted and sometimes engaged to work on the Two Pathways project. Also mentioned is a study tour of district energy facilities in northern Europe, conducted quite separately from the project but nevertheless having a considerable influence on the project.

Section 4 discusses heat demand in buildings. It presents substantial amounts of data and analysis that illustrate in dramatic form the extent of the problem facing those who seek to replace Ontario's space heating by natural gas. The main issue is the enormous energy requirements needed to provide space heating on the coldest days.

Section 5 sets out the electrification pathway noting its elements of building retrofits and challenges posed by the huge cost of battery storage to provide the additional electricity required during protracted cold spells. It includes explanations of the functioning of air-source and ground-source heat pumps, and their advantages and disadvantages. Examined are the special challenges for the electrification pathway of the peak energy demands noted in Section 4. Mention is made of Ontario's current predicament whereby using an electric heat pump can result in a higher level of GHG emissions than using natural gas furnace. This can happen because of the relative inefficiency of gas-fired generation – which would be generating most of the incremental power required – compared with the high efficiency of heat production by a new natural gas furnace.

Section 6 describes the TN pathway. It first describes district energy systems: how they deliver thermal energy via networks of underground pipes – usually as hot water, and increasingly as chilled water too, with legacy systems continuing to distribute steam. The systems can use a large variety of thermal energy sources including solar thermal (likely stored seasonally), biomass,

cold water from Lake Ontario's depths, and energy that would otherwise be unused such as heat rejected during nuclear and other electricity generation. Up to 70% of Ontario's buildings could be served by TN, at a cost that may be less than half of the cost of full electrification of space heating. Among the strongest advantages of the TN pathway is the ability to use relatively low-cost storage of thermal energy – which per unit of energy can be less than one percent of the cost of storing electricity. The section notes that deployment of TN can exploit a vast amount of positive international experience.

Section 7 discusses the hybrid approach of having both space-heating pathways, with most buildings being served by thermal networks, and a large minority, chiefly in rural and other areas of low settlement density areas having ground-source heat pumps. This section also discusses transition processes towards attainment of building decarbonization through such a hybrid approach.

Section 8 reviews the distributional consequences of the pathways, i.e., their economic and other impacts on society, businesses, and households. Among the non-economic impacts discussed are reliability, equity, employment, health, and safety.

Section 9 sets out the legal, regulatory, and financial frameworks for the development and maintenance of district energy systems (DES). The focus is on provincial legislation and its impacts on Ontario's municipalities, which would likely lead or otherwise be heavily involved in DES. The section also points to how the chronic financial inability of Ontario's municipalities with respect to patient investment in DES could be overcome.

Section 10 continues the focus on municipalities while pointing to the need for systematic thermal energy planning, likely conducted by municipalities. It reports on a one-day conference on municipal thermal energy planning held at the University of Toronto on March 20, 2025, as part of the work of the Two Pathways project.

Section 11 concerns the application of the TN pathway to Indigenous communities. It reports on plans and development in Bingwi Neyaashi Anishinaabek (Ontario) and in Oujé-Bougoumou (Quebec). It notes the importance of reliable, affordable heating in remote areas, the value of local biomass resources, and the need for tailored solutions that respect community priorities and sovereignty.

Section 12 summarizes assessments of impacts and opportunities presented by the two pathways for 55 of Ontario's approximately 60 local (electricity) distribution companies (LDCs). It provides limited information on the feasibility of local heat sources and on the impacts on grid infrastructure. It emphasizes the need for LDC engagement in planning and implementation.

Section 13 sets out conclusions from the project, first section by section, then the one overarching conclusion, and finally some other general conclusions and a call for action.

An **Appendix** to this report provides a brief account of energy basics, noting the dominant role of the Sun as an actual and potential source of energy. It distinguishes between energy and fuel, and between energy and exergy.

The **Bibliography** is the final item in this report. It lists 277 items from government, academic, and other literature pertaining to the project's topics. Many of the items are cited in the present report.

This report's six annexes are published as separate documents. They are described below. (Click on the brief title in each case – e.g., Annex A – for access to the respective document.)

Annex A: “Space Heating Electrification – Impact on the Ontario Electricity Grid and Retail Rates.” This report presents the results of an analysis of Ontario’s electricity system to determine the impact if air-source heat pumps are used for building heating, at scale.

Annex B: “District Energy Pathway Pre-Feasibility Study for an Illustrative Community in Ontario.” This study evaluates two pathways to decarbonize building heating in Anywhere, Ontario, an illustrative community to determine the affordability and practical feasibility of approaching zero emissions using low carbon district heating.

Annex C: “Peak Power, Heat Sources, Thermal Energy Storage.” Includes three reports prepared mostly by students at McMaster University’s Institute for Energy Studies.

Annex D: “Indigenous Community District Energy Costing Analysis.” This describes how the experience of one Indigenous community served to guide district energy development in another. Lessons learned were included to assist other communities in their exploration and development of similar systems.

Annex E: “Distributional Consequences.” This report examines the distributional consequences of decarbonizing building heating in Ontario, Canada by transitioning from natural gas to two alternative pathways: electrification via air-source heat pumps and centralized district energy systems. The analysis spans technical performance, economic costs, funding models, macro-economic and employment impacts, public health and environmental outcomes, technological innovations, and social equity and cultural considerations. It elaborates what is in Section 8.

Annex for LDCs. Ontario has about 60 electricity local distribution companies (LDCs). No matter what heating decarbonization pathway is followed in any given LDC, the electric power demand will change. Significant electrification of heating in an LDC could result in peak demand growing so much that almost the entire distribution network would need to be replaced/upgraded to have several times the existing peak capacity. This annex contains a separate report for each of 55 LDCs for which adequate data was available. Included in each LDC report are tables and figures showing key data and analysis results relevant to electric power demand that the LDC may need to serve.

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Abbreviations and Definitions

a	annum (year), as in MWh _{th} /a
A/C	air-conditioning
AHU	air-handling unit
APO	Annual Planning Outlook (of the IESO)
ASHP	Air-Source Heat Pump
BES	Battery Electric Storage
BI	Boltzmann Institute
C	° Celsius
CANDU	type of nuclear reactor built in Canada, now marketed by AtkinsRéalis (formerly SNC-Lavalin)
ccASHP	cold climate ASHP
CEEDC	Canadian Energy and Emissions Data Centre
CEUD	Comprehensive Energy Use Database, published by Natural Resources Canada
CHP	Combined Heat and Power, also known as cogeneration
COP	Coefficient of Performance, the efficiency of heat pumps, the ratio of useful heating output to the energy input required. Higher COP values indicate greater efficiency and lower operating costs.
DC	District Cooling
DE	District Energy
DES	District Energy System(s)
DH	District Heating
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DB	Dissemination Block, the smallest geographic area for which Statistics Canada disseminates population and dwelling counts
ΔT	Delta-T, a difference or change in temperature
EEA	European Economic Area, the EU plus the European Free Trade Association (EFTA): Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway
ER	electric resistance (heater)
ETS	Energy Transfer Station
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
FSA	Forward Sortation Area, the first three characters of a postal code
FVB	FVB Energy Inc., a global, integrated engineering firm specializing in district energy solutions, particularly in the development and design of low-carbon energy systems
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GSHP	Ground-source Heat Pump
GTHA	Greater Toronto and Hamilton Area

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GW	gigawatt, a billion watts
ha	hectare, 10,000 square metres
HDH	Heating Degree Hour
HRHP	Heat Recovery Heat Pump
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
IEA EBC	International Energy Agency's Energy in Buildings and Communities Programme.
IESO	Independent Electricity System Operator
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
LDC	Local (electric) Distribution Company
kW	kilowatt
kWh	kilowatt-hour
kWh _{th}	kilowatt-hour thermal
km	kilometre
m	metre
MPAC	Municipal Property Assessment Corporation, not-for-profit, responsible for assessing and classifying properties, funded by Ontario municipalities and accountable to the province, municipalities, and property taxpayers.
MDEI	Markham District Energy Inc.
MMR	Micro-modular reactor
MWh _{th}	megawatt-hour thermal
MURB	multi-unit residential building
MW	megawatt
NEA	Nuclear Energy Agency
NG	natural gas
NRCan	Natural Resources Canada
OEB	Ontario Energy Board
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPG	Ontario Power Generation
OSPE	Ontario Society of Professional Engineers
PV	Photo-Voltaic
PVT	Photo-Voltaic Thermal (generates electricity and heat)
ppl/ha	people/hectare
RNG	Renewable Natural Gas (formerly known as green gas, pipeline gas or high-btu gas, biogas cleaned and upgraded to allow injection into the natural gas distribution system)
RDH	a consulting and engineering firm specializing in building science
SAGSHP	solar assisted ground-source heat pump
SHC	solar heating and cooling
SMR	small modular reactor
StatCan	Statistics Canada
STES	Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage

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t CO ₂ eq/a	tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent per year
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
TN	Thermal Energy Network (also known as District Energy System)
TWh	terawatt-hour (a trillion watt-hours)
TWh _{th}	terawatt-hour thermal
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture.
4G DE	4th Generation District Energy (generally below 70°C supply temperature)
4GDH	Same as 4G DE
5G	5th Generation (applied to District Energy generally means low-temperature operation, possibly bi-directional energy flows, and decentralized energy management)

1. Introduction

“In a cold climate, heat is not a luxury—it is a matter of life and death.”

James Marston Fitch, American Building: The Environmental Forces that Shape It (1972)

But it’s not a problem that demanded much thought in most of Canada, until it was accepted that the emissions from burning natural gas would have to be phased out within a couple of decades. The thrust of this report is that heating all the buildings in Canada without using natural gas is a bigger problem than has been recognized. It might be the elephant in the room when planning to reach Net Zero by 2050. Seemingly modest in its technical requirements, it has yet to be moved. Emissions reduction is not happening. Quite the reverse.

What to do? That’s what this report is all about, at a strategic level. Is there some basic physics that dictates the best strategy? We believe there is. That is why we have undertaken this weighty research project with slight monetary compensation at considerable cost to our personal lives when most of us should have been enjoying a well-earned retirement.

There is something we all felt deep down that must be said.

1.1. Context

Buildings are the proximate cause of about 18% of Canada’s total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (NRCan, 2024). This is due, primarily, to at-building burning of natural gas (NG) and other fossil fuels for space and water heating. GHG emissions also result from electrically powered space and water heating (and air conditioning) in jurisdictions where fossil fuels are used to generate electricity. Toronto has estimated that buildings cause about 56% of its total GHG emissions (Toronto, 2024). For international comparison, see (Xiang et al., 2023).

The energy used in Canada each year for space and water heating is about equal to (and perhaps greater than) the electrical energy delivered for all uses. The peak thermal power demand for heating buildings, during winter cold spells, is about five times the annual mean heating demand and more than three times the peak electric power demand for all purposes (including existing electric heating).

To decarbonize all building heating is an enormous challenge. No single approach to solving the problem will be feasible or optimal everywhere. Different situations will warrant different solutions. Suitably matching solutions to situations will improve the chances of success and reduce societal costs.

The Boltzmann Institute (BI) undertook the project reported on here to consider and compare two quite different pathways to greatly reduce Canada’s GHG emissions due to buildings:

1. **Electrification Pathway:** There is a dominant narrative that improving buildings to reduce their heat demand and changing heating systems to electrically powered heat pumps will

be the best path forward to reduce (even eliminate) buildings-related GHG emissions.¹ Whether that narrative is factually correct is of crucial importance. Strategic decisions to reliably achieve required GHG reductions should be based on rigorous investigation and analysis rather than on a simple narrative that has become dominant as a result of optimism and frequent repetition.

2. **Thermal Networks Pathway:** Thermal Networks (TNs), also known as district heating (DH) or district energy (DE), deliver thermal energy (hot and/or cold) as a service to many or all buildings in a community. Hot (or cold) water carries the energy to buildings through a network of buried pipes, much like natural gas is delivered through pipes but with return pipes as well. At-building energy transfer stations (ETS) extract heat as needed for space and water heating, making the return flow in the TN colder (or warmer). With TNs, building owners no longer have primary responsibility for making changes to their building equipment and energy supply to provide heating and cooling. Moreover, if there is ample, affordable, low- or zero-emissions supply of thermal energy then costly building improvements may not be warranted.

The present study involved wide-reaching research and analysis to assess the relative merits of the above two pathways and to support optimal pathway selection in different communities across Canada. Ontario was the main focus, but many of the findings are either directly applicable to or can serve as guides for similar analysis in the other provinces and territories. The purpose of this project has been to consider, compare, and draw conclusions regarding two different approaches, or pathways, to (almost) eliminate GHG emissions from the buildings sector, at-scale, in communities across Canada – large and small, urban, suburban, rural and Indigenous. For practical reasons, including data availability, most of the detailed analysis was focused on Ontario. Nonetheless, a clear objective was to obtain findings and draw conclusions that may be applicable across Canada.

This is a multi-faceted, complex problem with no easy or universal solution. In addition to technical aspects, it is necessary to consider environmental, social, economic, industrial, organizational, regulatory and political aspects and international commitments, time constraints and competition for all kinds of resources.

1.2. Relevant published work

Published material relevant to this study is extensive. To provide context, we cite in this subsection references of broad strategic relevance. Other citations are provided in later sections where they are particularly relevant. All referenced materials are listed in the Bibliography, which also includes relevant materials that are not specifically cited in the text. (A different citation format is used in Sections 9 and 10, as explained there.)

Decarbonization of buildings is an objective being pursued by many countries, especially those with cold climates (EU, 2023; EU, 2024; Joint Research Centre et al., 2019; Directorate-

¹ See, e.g., <https://natural-resources.canada.ca/energy-efficiency/building-energy-efficiency/canada-green-buildings-strategy-transforming-canada-s-buildings-sector-net-zero-resilient-future>.

General et al., 2023; Economidou et al., 2020; Paardekooper et al., 2018; Yuan et al., 2022; UNEP, 2024; World Bank, 2023). This has included major efforts and research studies on:

- reducing the energy demand of buildings (Zhang et al., 2021; EEA, 2024; IEA EBC, 2022; Hummel et al., 2021; Moran et al., 2020; Prabatha et al., 2020; Brocklehurst et al., 2021; Scott, 2023; Giandomenico, Papineau and Rivers, 2022; Fořt and Černý, 2022; Ahlrichs et al., 2022; Walker et al., 2021; Walker, Hischer and Schlueter, 2022)
- electrification of building heating with at-building heat pumps (Carroll, Chesser and Lyons, 2020; Chesser et al., 2021; Sadeghi, Habibollah and Singh, 2022; Winkler and Ramaraj, 2023; RDH, 2020; RDH, 2021; E4TheFuture, 2024)
- large-scale implementation of low- or zero-emissions thermal networks (IEA, 2022; IEA, 2023; IEA, 2023a; UNEP, 2015; Lettenbichler et al., 2023; Mathiesen et al., 2019; Johansen and Werner, 2022; Moser and Puschnigg, 2021; Bertelsen, 2021; Manz et al., 2021).

1.3. Objectives

The goal of the Two Pathways project was to quantify the potential costs, to customers of each Ontario electricity local distribution company (LDC), that would result from following either of the above building decarbonization pathways. The specific objectives were:

- Accurately estimate the increased peak power demand likely to arise from electrification of heating and the consequences
- Quantify zero-emission heat sources, such as renewable heat, in each of the LDC service areas
- Juxtapose results from above for each LDC
- Estimate the typical cost and benefit in Ontario of large-scale thermal energy storage
- Illustrate the typical cost of 4GDH² infrastructure supplying existing buildings with zero emissions heat
- Apply to remote, Indigenous communities
- Describe the distributional aspects of each pathway
- Ensure the information derived in this project reaches potential knowledge users, at a minimum a good portion of the 63 LDC's in Ontario.

1.4. Accomplishments and challenges

Technical aspects

The hourly, weather-dependent thermal energy required for space heating, to replace all existing, at-building natural gas space heating in Ontario, was estimated with good confidence (Section 4). The hourly electric power required, in the electrification pathway, to deliver that heat was estimated on the basis of published studies of real-world performance of air-source heat pumps (ASHPs) and ground-source heat pumps (GSHPs). Estimates were also obtained for the cost and

² 4GDH - 4th Generation District Heating. See Section 6.

feasibility of increasing power system capacity (generation, transmission and distribution) to deliver the reliable power needed for heating electrification. (Section 5, Annex A)

Thermal and electric power demand for heating electrification were determined for almost all LDCs, but with somewhat less confidence than for the whole province due to unavailability of detailed data – electricity, natural gas, buildings – at the LDC level. (Section 12, LDC Annexes)

The viability of thermal networks in any given area depends on having sufficiently high local heat demand density. Census data was used to determine population density at high resolution across Ontario. By assuming that local annual space heating demand is proportional to population density, an estimate was obtained for the fraction of buildings (and total heat demand) in Ontario and in each LDC that could be reasonably served by TNs. The accuracy and uncertainty of these estimates could be improved by detailed data on buildings and existing natural gas use. (Section 6)

A multitude of zero-emissions sources of heat for TNs were considered and quantified. Those sources have a strong potential to reliably and economically meet the demand for heat across Ontario. Options were investigated for large-scale, long- and short-term thermal energy storage (TES) to allow low- or zero-emissions heat to be collected when it is available and delivered to buildings when it is needed. (Section 6, Annex C)

While every LDC has the potential to collect adequate heat from within its boundaries, thermal power stations, including nuclear, configured for combined heat and power (CHP) were identified as having the potential to economically provide a significant fraction of all heat needed by TNs for Ontario's major urban areas. The potential for and costs of major heat transmission lines from CHP power stations to LDCs as far as 100 km away were thus also investigated. (Section 6) (Friedrich et al., 2024)

Thermal Network for an Illustrative Community

An analysis was completed of a representative, but fictional, Illustrative Community to determine the affordability and practical feasibility of pursuing the TN pathway. This included developing a heating plan, then a development plan to gradually connect and serve all the buildings with district heating, all from non-emitting, local heat sources supported by thermal energy storage. The capital and operating costs were estimated based on unit costs from recent projects in Ontario. (Annex B, Section 8, Annex E)

Application to Indigenous Communities

Oujé Bougoumou in northern Quebec is an example of an Indigenous community where all the buildings in the community have been heated for several decades using a thermal energy network with a primarily non-emitting heat source (biomass), backed by fuel oil. Leveraging existing good relationships with community leaders, the prospects for developing new thermal energy networks in Indigenous communities were assessed by considering what the present day cost would be to replicate the function of the existing system based on current technologies, best practices, and lessons learned over the last 30 years. (Section 11, Annex D)

Bingwi Neyaashi Anishinaabek (BNA), a First Nations community on the south eastern coast of Lake Nipigon, was also consulted. Although full economic details have not yet been made available, the community has considered options and has made a decision to adopt a biomass based district heating system. The principal considerations were that the electricity supply to the community experiences frequent interruptions and a Band-owned sawmill provides waste wood at low or no cost for the energy system. Some details of the system and their rationale for choosing district heating are provided.

Distributional consequences

The impacts of pursuing zero emissions from buildings down each pathway (electrification or thermal networks) were examined at three scales: the whole province, individual communities, and “typical” households. (Section 8, Annex E)

The required infrastructure investment was estimated for the province as a whole for each pathway. The provincial estimates considered only capital costs for infrastructure; investments by building owners for energy conversion or transfer equipment inside their buildings were not included.

Separate analysis estimated costs to communities, including in-building costs and operation and maintenance costs, without and with the allocation of electrical infrastructure costs, recognizing that energy users will pay for electrical infrastructure either through rates or taxes.

Finally, the monthly energy costs faced by households were projected for each scenario, based on “typical” consumption. Energy costs included the amortization and maintenance of in-building equipment and electricity (not just for heating), natural gas and/or thermal energy corresponding to the scenario.

Projected non-monetary distributional consequences were assessed, including: reliability, financing and ownership implications, macroeconomic effects, employment effects, health, safety and environmental impacts, impetus to innovation, social equity and culture.

Communications and Outreach

Continual engagement with stakeholders and groups with related interests was a priority throughout the project. It is expected to continue, and likely increase, following publication of this report.

Frequent communication and outreach with municipal officials was concomitant to the research. Extensive consultation took place with both the provincial and federal governments, with reporting on findings and exchanges of opinions and ideas on related activities or policies. Electricity utilities were contacted through their organizations like IESO and OPG and there was some communication with LDCs on possible impacts of electrification and how thermal energy systems could reduce or minimize grid congestion and the need for upgrades.

Recognizing the many stakeholders and perspectives in the transformation of energy systems, efforts were made to reach out to other groups/organizations with similar interests and foster a shared vision of pathways for decarbonizing our energy system. Still, many persist with pre-existing points of view; consolidation of views appears, in the short term, unlikely among

some but promising with many. Having multiple advocates and pathways is probably confusing to the public and to policy or program managers.

A close working relationship was established with the Ontario Society of Professional Engineers (OSPE), with the Boltzmann Institute representatives on the OSPE Energy Task Force. Strong respect has developed for the potential and importance of thermal energy systems as a complement to electric power systems; this report may serve as a basis for further actions.

The nuclear community was engaged in multiple ways to develop an appreciation by all stakeholders for the value and feasibility of nuclear CHP to supply heat to thermal networks, and to help bring about changes that will help Canada realize that value. The Boltzmann Institute teamed with senior advisors to the Canadian Nuclear Association and both nuclear and thermal networks specialists at McMaster University to produce a position paper on the integration of Nuclear CHP and thermal networks (Friedrich et al., 2024). The position paper was the focus of an executive workshop, in February 2024, attended by key decision makers from the electric power, nuclear, and district energy industries; federal, provincial, and municipal governments and agencies; academia; think tanks; and others. A special session on nuclear CHP, thermal energy networks and seasonal thermal energy storage has been organized for the Canadian Nuclear Society (CNS) Annual Conference, in June, 2025, that will include sharing of some information developed during this project. Until now, the dominant rationale for nuclear power in Canada has been the production of baseload electricity. With nuclear CHP coupled to thermal networks and seasonal thermal energy storage, the nuclear industry could extend its duty to also encompass load following, displacing fossil fuel generation. It would then become, not only, a leading instrument in decarbonization of building heating in Canada but also of the broader economy. However, lack of an integrated regulatory framework for electricity and heat appears to act as a deterrent to implementation of nuclear CHP, resulting in inability to realize the societal (and environmental) benefits.

Communications with the international community has also been strong. Boltzmann Institute has been sharing approaches with the IEA DHC Technology Collaboration Party (TCP), has a letter of endorsement for its work on nuclear CHP and thermal networks and an invitation to provide a summary report on developing an integrated approach to thermal and electricity systems.

Boltzmann Institute has also been working on an OECD NEA report on nuclear CHP and has been invited to participate in a workshop on this subject in late June, 2025. The Institute also serves as an advisor to EuroHeat and Power, assists in the evaluation of their Climate Awards program and was invited to a EuroHeat and Power panel to speak on nuclear CHP, heat only reactors and their potential to serve heat loads including district heating systems.

These opportunities have reinforced our understanding that thermal networks pathways are proven and possible, with little risk, and that Canada can derive opportunities in Canada, North America and Internationally. The consultation has revealed that we are filling a clear void in integrated energy systems opportunity that is not well addressed by governments or utilities but that, if better understood, could become a major decarbonization initiative in Canada.

1.5. Key findings

- 1. Building Retrofits:** Building retrofits (e.g., insulation and other envelope improvements) could potentially reduce the thermal energy demand and, correspondingly, the electric power demand. But substantial evidence indicates that gains through retrofitting of existing buildings are unlikely to materially exceed the additional demand from new buildings. Lack of adequate industrial capacity, unaffordably high costs, and reliance on individual initiatives of millions of building owners are major factors contributing to lack of significant thermal energy demand reductions from building retrofits.

For any given building, carefully chosen retrofit measures may reduce the combined cost of retrofits and electric power (including power system expansion). But the savings will be a small fraction of the no-retrofit heating electrification costs. Building thermal energy demand reductions exceeding 50% are rare, and will almost certainly have no economic payback.

- 2. Air-Source Heat Pumps:** It is neither feasible nor affordable to decarbonize the heating of Ontario's buildings by relying primarily on heating electrification with ASHPs. To do so would require adding over 60 GW of zero-emissions, reliable peak capacity to the electric power system at an estimated capital cost of \$600 billion (+60%/–30%).³ (The reliable generation capacity of the existing Ontario power system is about 21 GW (IESO 2024).) For such power system expansion, the average annual amortization costs per electrified dwelling, at 3% interest for 50 years, would be about \$3000; commercial and industrial customers would face proportionately greater costs; and operating costs would be in addition. But the bigger concern is that such a massive power system expansion would be an unnecessary folly and a practical impossibility.

That the peak power demand would be so high has not been widely recognized, and may be questioned by others. But it is carefully explained in Section 5, with support from multiple published field studies. In brief: on very cold days, when the demand for heat is greatest, most ASHPs operate at low efficiency and are unable to supply adequate heat; supplementary heating systems take over. Most current ASHP installations in areas of Ontario with natural gas service rely on gas furnaces or boilers for supplementary heat. But for large-scale decarbonization of existing natural gas heating, electric resistance (ER) supplementary heat would be the only option; that results in the extreme peak demand. The combination of ASHPs and ER supplementary heat may yield an effective, seasonal average coefficient of performance (COP), or efficiency factor, of about 2.4 (± 0.3); but at the coldest periods the instantaneous ASHP COP adjusted to allow for ER supplementary heat is $COP_{adj} \approx 1$.

- 3. Thermal Networks:** It would be feasible and economical to meet the space and water heating needs of up to 70% of Ontario's buildings with net-zero thermal networks by 2050. The societal cost of TNs, operated and regulated as utilities, would be dramatically lower

³ All costs are in 2024 overnight dollars, with uncertainties as indicated. See also Annex A.

than the cost of the electrification pathway – perhaps one third to one half the cost. Existing thermal energy, normally lost to the environment, would be harvested year-round and stored until needed in large-scale thermal energy storage (TES). The overall efficiency of retrofitted and new thermal power stations (using renewable or nuclear fuel) could be increased by 100 to 200 percent by configuring and operating them for combined heat and power (CHP). CHP plants could potentially supply most of the needed heat. Other countries consider CHP by default for thermal power stations; they economically transmit heat up to 100 km through insulated pipes from nuclear CHP power stations to urban load centres.

- 4. Ground-Source Heat Pumps:** For the ~30 percent of Ontario buildings where the density is too low for TNs to be viable, electrification with ground-source heat pumps (GSHPs) will usually be the best option for decarbonization of heating. While GSHPs cost more than ASHPs for building owners to install, they have the advantage of maintaining high efficiency (COP = 3 to 4, sometimes higher) even in very cold weather. From a societal perspective, the extra investment in GSHPs is more than offset by the reduced need for investment in peak power system capacity compared to capacity needed for ASHPs. Societal benefit and equity could be optimized by providing targeted subsidies, where TNs are not viable, to make GSHPs more attractive than ASHPs for building owners to install. Incentives should also motivate building owners to install solar thermal collectors to use the sun's heat for domestic hot water, to reduce GSHP electricity use, and to maintain an annual balance between heat extracted from and injected into GSHP boreholes.
- 5. Sector Coupling:** The energy-intensive infrastructures used to provide different services (e.g., fuels, electricity, water, heat, transportation, communications, information, waste management) to consumers have, until now, been kept largely independent. All these infrastructures are less than 100 percent efficient, and produce "waste" products including heat. It is increasingly recognized that improved overall efficiency and lower costs can be achieved through creative coupling of two or more infrastructures (Münster et al., 2020).

A particularly relevant example involves thermal power plants, fueled by nuclear, fossil or non-fossil fuels. Due to thermodynamic limitations, most of the heat generated by the fuels consumed cannot be converted to electricity. Instead of discarding the residual heat to the environment, the plants can be configured to operate as combined heat and power (CHP) plants that supply valuable thermal energy in addition to electricity. For a nuclear CHP plant, the overall efficiency can be increased from 30% to as much as 90%. The salvaged heat can be collected year-round, stored in large-scale TES, and used by TNs to heat nearby cities. In addition to using reactor heat much more efficiently, nuclear CHP power stations would become dispatchable for the electric power system, enabling greater utilization of wind and solar PV power and reducing or eliminating the need for gas-fired generation to meet power system reliability requirements (IESO, 2025c).

- 6. Transition Strategy:** Elimination of GHG emissions in the buildings sector is a long-term challenge. Meeting the target of net-zero by 2050 will require both individual actions and

major infrastructure changes. Reliance on electrification would require unprecedented, and likely infeasible, expansion of electric power systems. An emphasis on thermal networks would require deployment of TNs at an unprecedented scale in Canada, although many other cold-climate countries have already shown that large-scale TNs are both feasible and economical. Use of Canada's existing natural gas infrastructure will have to be greatly reduced or even eliminated.

In low density areas, where TNs are not viable, electrification of heating with GSHPs will have the lowest societal cost. Installing GSHPs would create the least need for expansion of electricity infrastructure and make the best use of existing electrical capacity. Where local conditions allow, shallow-buried horizontal ground loop heat exchangers will have lower initial and lifetime cost than boreholes; heat removed during the winter will be naturally restored during the summer, avoiding the need to maintain annual thermal balance in boreholes. Where boreholes are the only option, the annual balance can be achieved by installing solar thermal collectors (which can also heat domestic hot water (DHW) year-round). For buildings close to large water bodies, water-source heat pumps may be an even better option than horizontal loop GSHPs.

In higher density areas, where TNs will generally be viable for both existing and new buildings, building decarbonization will be most effectively and efficiently achieved with a staged approach that avoids unrealistic power system expansion while allowing time for implementation and organized transition to community-scale TNs. For example:

- In the short term, systematically replace end-of-life air conditioners with standard ASHPs of similar capacity (not more expensive, higher capacity cold-climate ASHPs). The ASHPs would not require increased peak power and would provide efficient heating above about +4 C. Use of natural gas heating would continue, but only at lower ambient temperatures. Use of ASHPs above +4 C would reduce combined GHG emissions from at-building gas heating and electricity generation by about 7 percent. At-building natural gas consumption for heating would drop about 17 percent.
 - Plan and develop community-scale TNs starting immediately and continuing until TN services are provided to all existing and new buildings where that is economically viable. This includes construction of suitable heat distribution networks; identification and integration of diverse heat sources capable of meeting demand (which might initially include natural gas); and implementation of large-scale (and seasonal) thermal energy storage to manage temporal mismatches between heat supply and demand.
 - Connect all buildings to TNs as their services become available within each community and disconnect those buildings from the natural gas network.
- 7. Energy Efficiency:** Much attention has been given to the efficiency of buildings with the objective of reducing the amount and cost of energy used for space and water heating and the corresponding GHG emissions. However, it tends to be overlooked that vast amounts of thermal energy are routinely discharged into the environment through exhaust fans, chimneys and cooling towers, into lakes, etc.

It will often be more feasible and more cost-effective to improve efficiency by harvesting and using thermal energy that would otherwise be deliberately discharged to the environment at major facilities, such as power stations, instead of persuading millions of owners to undertake expensive projects to reduce thermal energy losses from their buildings. In many situations, the ability to economically harvest most or all the heat needed may mean that efforts to improve the efficiency of individual buildings would actually increase GHG emissions (e.g., embodied emissions). This also applies to energy efficiency standards for new buildings that will be **served** by TNs; making new buildings highly efficient may be counterproductive.

- 8. Application to Indigenous Communities:** Replicating the function of the 30 year old Oujé Bougoumou thermal energy network in a similar community was found to be feasible using current unit costs and modern practice. The investment for this particular community, with ~175 single-family residences, and ~30 public buildings, would be approximately \$37.6 million. That appears to have a long-pay-back on paper (about 22 years) versus the electrification pathway (that might be viable in similar grid connected communities). But it must be remembered that such a comparison relies on electricity rates kept affordable by subsidization from the large grid rate base. There would be strategic benefit in achieving decarbonization while avoiding increasing winter peak electric demand, in this case by 3 MVA. Although, at first blush, Quebec seems to be well endowed with hydroelectric resources, nevertheless it is still winter peaking, so the system would benefit from avoiding winter peaks from new demand with low capacity factor.
- 9. Distributional Consequences:** If it were even possible to reach zero emissions from building heating down the electrification pathway for those buildings currently heated by natural gas (about 70% of floor-space in Ontario), which is highly doubtful for reasons outlined in this report as a whole, the capital investment required from society as a whole in Ontario (and it is believed similar in other provinces) would be about double that which would be required to achieve the same emissions goal down the thermal network pathway and it would be in the hundreds of billions of dollars. This result is driven by the very high new peak demand that the electricity system would be required to accommodate.

Naturally, spending that much extra money to achieve a similar result would be relatively more inflationary, with corresponding avoidable negative effects on the economy. This finding and other non-monetary impacts are described in Section 8 and Annex E.

- 10. Legal and financial ability.** District energy systems (DES) are likely to be established only by municipalities or with strong municipal support. In Ontario, municipalities are legally empowered to establish DES, alone or in partnership with private-sector entities. Although not essential, municipal involvement in providing DES services to customers may be more expeditiously achieved through establishment of municipally owned corporations. Municipal ability to provide the patient investment required for DES

deployment is limited. Funding by other governments is possible but the most available investment may come from the private sector.

A truly important municipal role is the provision of thermal energy planning (TEP), known too as heating planning and heat planning – a necessary prelude to substantial investment towards decarbonization of space heating and cooling. TEP assesses the current and future thermal energy demand of all current **and** anticipated buildings in a defined area, identifies available no-carbon and low-carbon sources of thermal energy, and matches the two in a long-term plan with regular updates.

1.6. Organization of this report

This main report for the Two Pathways project has 13 substantive sections, one appendix, and an extensive bibliography. There are also separate annexes published in conjunction with this report. Annexes A through D were prepared by other organizations that the Boltzmann Institute engaged for specific parts of the research. Annex E was produced by the Boltzmann Institute. Another annex contains reports for each of 55 local (electricity) distribution companies (LDCs).

Section 2 provides a synopsis to define the electrification and thermal networks pathways, considered as sole solutions for heating decarbonization; it also introduces the potential for hybrid/transitional solutions and the issues of energy supply, storage, and sector coupling. The methodology applied in carrying out the work is described in Section 3.

Section 4 is focused on heat demand. The annual, seasonal and hour-by-hour variation of heat demand are currently not well understood because nobody measures them except district heating systems. Understanding hourly heat demand of buildings, and collectively communities, is sine non qua for appreciating the prospects of the Two Pathways.

Detailed discussion and analysis of the electrification pathway is in Sections 5 and of the thermal networks pathway in Section 6. Hybrid/transitional solutions are discussed in Section 7. Section 8 (a digest of Annex E) examines the quantitative and qualitative distributional consequences of each pathway to citizens and energy consumers in Ontario.

The regulatory, legal and financial landscape is surveyed in Section 9. Section 10 introduces the concept of thermal energy planning – a methodical process to help decide what decarbonization pathways or solutions to adopt, over time, in each part of a study area: neighbourhood, municipality, or larger. Such planning is warranted by the potentially enormous societal impacts of sub-optimal decisions.

Brief accounts of work done in relation to Indigenous Communities and Electricity Local Distribution Companies are given in Sections 11 and 12, respectively, with references to corresponding Annexes.

The closing Section 13 provides an overall summary and conclusions for the Two Pathways project. It is followed by a brief Appendix on Energy Basics and the extensive Bibliography.

2. Synopsis of Pathways

The goal driving this work is to **decarbonize the heating of almost all Ontario buildings by 2050**. Each viable pathway must address the progressive transition from the present, when most heating uses natural gas, to a future state, just 25 years from now, when fossil fuels are not used. Both space heating and water heating are in scope, but space heating is the much more difficult challenge and is the main focus of attention.

This section provides overviews of what is entailed in the electrification (Section 2.1) and thermal networks (Section 2.2) pathways, each considered on its own (except where TNs would not be viable). While neither the electrification nor the thermal networks pathway will be entirely realistic or universally applicable, they provide "bookends" that might lay out the extremes and allow policy makers and utilities to consider the options, the relative costs and benefits and then do more work to support a better way forward.

Taking a more realistic view, Section 2.3 describes options and considerations for deployment of hybrid solutions that strategically employ electrification and thermal networks for different parts of the building stock. Section 2.4 addresses the sources, magnitude and efficiency of energy supply, storage and delivery and the mechanisms and benefits of coupling or integration of the involved energy sectors.

2.1. Electrification Pathway

The electrification pathway would reduce GHG emissions attributable to buildings through a combination of:

- high efficiency standards for new buildings and energy efficiency retrofits of existing buildings (of all sizes), to reduce each building's heating (and cooling) demand
- at-building, electrically-powered heat pumps instead of fossil-fueled furnaces / boilers for space heating
- high-efficiency, electrically-powered water heaters, stoves, dryers and other devices instead of fossil-fueled equipment
- more sophisticated thermostats and other control systems to optimize the use of electricity
- upgrading of the electric power system – generation, transmission and distribution – to provide the electric power needed by electrified buildings, using zero-emissions generation.

The last bullet, above, is often neglected by advocates of the electrification pathway, perhaps because the need is not evident when the number of electrified buildings is very small, and because building owners have no direct responsibility for implementing the power system upgrades.

For existing buildings, individual building owners would have primary responsibility for implementing building-specific measures, although they may have guidance / pressure and financial and other support from government programs. New buildings would be constructed in

compliance with stringent energy efficiency standards. Some fraction of building owners are expected by electrification proponents to install solar PV panels to reduce the demand for grid electricity; and some to install batteries (e.g., Tesla PowerWall) and/or to use EV batteries to enable use of stored electricity to help reduce the peak load on the grid. At-building thermal energy storage devices, which typically heat ceramic bricks to high temperature, are also proposed as a means to flatten the load.

Heat pumps for space heating would be predominantly air-source heat pumps. Ground-source heat pumps, which may also heat DHW, would be installed for a smaller fraction of buildings. A very small fraction of buildings, that are situated close to suitably deep water bodies, might have water source heat pumps.

Heat pumps, particularly ASHPs, intended and sized for both heating and air conditioning, are typically not capable of meeting the high demand for heat in very cold weather. To reliably provide sufficient heat in even the coldest weather, it is common to install (or retain) supplementary (or auxiliary or backup) heating systems. Today, natural gas furnaces / boilers are most often used for supplementary heat; but to achieve net-zero GHG emissions for almost all buildings electric resistance (ER) heating would have to become standard.

In principle, net-zero fuels could be used for supplementary heat, but there is no reasonable evidence or indication that renewable natural gas (RNG), green hydrogen (whose production, typically by electrolysis of water, does not use fossil fuels), or geologic hydrogen (whose commercial production at-scale is still unproven) could be available and distributed to more than a small fraction of Ontario buildings by 2050. Those fuels are thus not considered as significant factors in the present work. (Should cost-competitive geologic hydrogen become available at a scale comparable to existing natural gas usage in Ontario, the Two Pathways study could become obsolete. The same applies to any other revolutionary new source of zero-emissions energy. All such present proposals are so undeveloped as to not deserve further consideration here.)

While GHG emissions due to at-building combustion of fossil fuels would be significantly reduced or eliminated, the electrification pathway would involve greatly increased consumption of electricity. The full impact on total GHG emissions would depend on the emissions that result from increased electricity production.

Buildings, whether new or retrofitted, that are more energy efficient tend to have more embodied emissions than less efficient buildings (where comparable effort has been put into design for low-embodied emissions). This is due to more GHG emissions incurred in the materials and equipment supply chain and the construction process. Similarly, substantial embodied emissions are incurred in the expansion of power systems and the production and installation of heat pumps, solar PV panels and batteries. In spite of their potential significance, detailed estimates of embodied emissions and comparison to operational emissions are beyond the scope of the present work.

2.2. Thermal Networks Pathway

The thermal networks pathway transfers responsibility for decarbonization of heating from building owners to thermal network (TN) providers. Also known as district heating (DH) or district

energy (DE), TNs deliver thermal energy as a service to many or all buildings in a community. Hot water carries the energy to buildings through a supply and return network of buried, insulated pipes. At-building energy transfer stations (ETS) extract heat as needed for space and water heating, making the return flow colder.

Although the main focus here is on heating, many TNs also provide service for cooling buildings by circulating cold water that is returned warmer. Whether a given TN will serve cooling needs in addition to heating is a decision that will depend on detailed analysis of the local context and circumstances. Such analysis is beyond the scope of the present work. Provision of a TN cooling service in Ontario will have little impact on total GHG emissions since the annual energy needed for heating is about ten times (or more) the annual energy for cooling, and most cooling is already electrified.

TNs are capital intensive, with relatively low operating costs (Annex B). They must be planned, financed and established as strategic initiatives with the expectation of steady monthly revenue from sufficiently many reliable long-term customers.

With TNs, building owners no longer have complete responsibility for making changes to their building equipment and energy supply to decarbonize heating. Costly building improvements to reduce the need for heat may not be warranted since the TN provider should be able to eliminate GHG emissions and improve energy efficiency in a less costly and more effective way.

A limitation is that TNs are only viable in areas of sufficient density. There must be sufficient demand for heat per metre of pipe to justify the cost of installing and operating the network. A similar limitation applies to natural gas distribution networks; the minimum viable density will be comparable for both TNs and NG networks. (Gas networks must also transmit the gas from its usually-distant sources, whereas TNs may be able to obtain their heat locally, e.g., with solar thermal collectors.)

No matter what business model a TN provider chooses, the buildings served must be assured of affordable and reliable TN services for the long term. Just as with water, electricity and gas utilities, it is usual to have one TN provider offering service to buildings in a given area. Withdrawal or disruption of service, or unexpected price increases, could have unacceptable impacts on customers. With these considerations, TNs are energy utilities, and may be regulated in a manner similar to, or even integrated with, other energy utilities.

A TN can be small, serving tens to hundreds of buildings. But, like electric power systems, TNs can be large, complex, hierarchical and interconnected to serve whole cities or metropolitan areas. They can be intimately coupled in a mutually beneficial manner to electric power and other sectors.

TN providers have responsibility for planning, financing, building and operating the infrastructure, obtaining the needed supply of heat, making the heat reliably available to customers' buildings when it is needed, and achieving decarbonization objectives.

For large-scale deployment of TNs, such as contemplated here, multiple public and/or private companies could contribute to different elements of a hierarchical thermal network system; or one large provider could do it all. The elements would include: collection / production

of heat; high capacity heat transmission (up to about 100 km); seasonal and shorter-term thermal energy storage (TES); distribution piping networks that connect customer buildings; energy transfer stations (ETS) within buildings (including for DHW); sometimes in-building heat transfer equipment (e.g., water-to-air heat exchangers and air handling units (AHU) that replace furnaces); and monitoring and control systems (distributed and central). This could be comparable to a regional electric power system in terms of its scale (energy and power), multiple players, diverse elements and hierarchical structure.

The collection / production of heat can employ a wide variety of heat sources whose number, characteristics (scale, time variation, temperature, GHG emissions, etc.) and mix can change over time. A TN could initially use fossil fuels to ensure a reliable heat supply, but progressively shift to zero emissions heat sources whose use is made feasible by large-scale TES and heat transmission lines. The greater the thermal power available from a source the longer distance it can be economically transmitted.

In Europe, Russia, China and elsewhere, thermal networks are deployed for heating urban buildings at large scale (IEA, 2023). Denmark has a leadership position, with district energy serving 98% of buildings in Copenhagen and 65% across the country; upgrades and expansion are systematically decarbonizing the systems. Other Nordic countries also employ district energy at large scale and are making strong progress towards very low GHG emissions (Maliszewska-Nienartowicz et al., 2024).

Canada has over 200 TNs, including some that have gained international profile (CEEDC, 2023; Sibbitt et al., 2012; C40, 2025; C2E2, 2025). However, the percentage of buildings served is still very small, compared with other countries. The main impediment to greatly increased use of TNs in Canada may be the wide availability and low cost of natural gas, but with the need to decarbonize that may change.

2.3. Hybrid/Transitional Solutions

As noted above, TNs will only be viable in areas with sufficient density. Such areas will include most urban and suburban buildings, but generally not rural buildings (except in compact towns or villages). Complete building decarbonization in rural areas will thus substantially depend on electrification. TNs could be the dominant solution in non-rural areas.

To proceed at a scale consistent with the goal of net-zero GHG emissions by 2050, both pathways – electrification and thermal networks – must include massive investments to produce and deliver the zero-emissions electric power and heat needed to replace natural gas. However, building the needed infrastructure will take years to decades and hundreds of billions of dollars. In Ontario, increasing the capacity of electric power systems is already a priority to meet the anticipated demand from electrification of transportation and industry (Ontario, 2025). But, as is shown in later sections of this report, present projections and plans fall far short of what would be needed for heating electrification. Plans for TNs are very limited and certainly far less ambitious than what will be needed.

Sophisticated modeling and strategic planning – as discussed in Section 10 – will be needed to decide what pathway will be chosen for each community, on what timelines, and, based on

those choices, what specific infrastructure must be available when. The modeling and planning process will be iterative and ongoing, adapting to situational and technology changes and always with attention to the lead times required for implementation of different infrastructure elements.

During the next decade (or more), instead of waiting for new or upgraded infrastructure, it will be important to implement measures that are possible with existing infrastructure and still help to reduce emissions. These short-term measures, although they might be orchestrated by government programmes, would likely be implemented by owners of individual buildings. They could include no-regrets measures to reduce energy demand as well as installation of heat pumps (ASHP or GSHP) whose collective power demand does not materially exceed existing air conditioning peaks.

The peak power constraint would mean that ASHPs (installed only in non-rural buildings) are not operated below about +4 C, since operation at much lower temperatures would almost certainly require more power than used on a hot summer day. They should thus be sized to match the air conditioners they replace. Heating at lower temperatures would continue to use natural gas heating systems; existing natural gas furnaces that reach their end of life could be replaced with very high efficiency gas furnaces, reducing emissions by 10% or more. Conversion to a more significant and sustainable building decarbonization solution would happen in a second stage once the necessary infrastructure is available (which could be at different times in different communities).

For rural buildings, GSHPs would be a better choice than ASHPs; GSHPs require much less power (one third or less) in very cold weather. Rural buildings with existing electric resistance heat could be directly converted to GSHPs capable of meeting the full heat demand in the coldest weather; that would actually reduce the peak demand on the power system. The peak demand for GSHPs could be further reduced by use of horizontal ground loops (where that is possible) or using solar thermal panels to increase borehole temperatures (Adebayo et al. 2024), possibly allowing electrification of all rural buildings without requiring major power system upgrades.

2.4. Energy Supply, Storage, and Sector Coupling

That heating buildings requires energy is obvious. Not so obvious is whether affordable, reliable supplies of zero-emissions electricity and/or thermal energy can be made available, when needed, for large-scale decarbonization of building heating with ASHPs and/or TNs. The primary sources of energy are discussed in the appendix. The decarbonization pathways must also address how that energy will be supplied to buildings as electricity and / or heat.

History has shown that natural gas can reliably meet the highly variable demand for heat. Two main advantages of NG are storage and line pack. Ontario facilities can store almost a winter's worth (over 110 TWh) of NG supply (CER, 2023). Line pack exploits compressed gas held (in essence, stored) in transmission and distribution pipes to meet rapid demand fluctuations by letting the pressure change (KnowledgeBase, 2025). The peak power supplied by natural gas in Ontario is about 70 GW (see Section 4). A small fraction of that natural gas is used for up to about 7 GW (peak) of gas-fired electricity generation, dispatched particularly when non-emitting generation types cannot economically meet peak demands.

Ontario's existing electric power demand peaks on hot summer days at about 9 GW above the 15.5 GW annual average demand. As is shown in Section 5, large-scale electrification with ASHPs would create an unprecedented new demand for peak power – at least 50 GW above summer peaks – with only a 30% increase of the energy delivered. The extreme peak is because up to 35 C degrees of winter heating⁴ can be required, compared to about 10 C degrees of summer cooling, and because the high efficiency of ASHPs at moderate temperatures (which keeps the annual energy use low) does not persist at very low temperatures. Contemplated electrical energy storage in Ontario could serve up to 2 GW of demand for about 10 hours (Dunsky, 2024). On a very cold day, fully charged electrical storage could power only about 4% of Ontario-wide electrified heating for 10 hours before being discharged.

Ontario's use of NG generation has been increasing in recent years due to growing demand and nuclear station outages (mostly for refurbishment). The IESO has determined that NG generation will be needed until 2035 and beyond to reliably meet expected demand (IESO, 2025). That expected demand does not include electrified heating of existing buildings; until 2035, and likely beyond, increased demand to power heat pumps will be mostly served by NG generation.

The energy needed by thermal networks is mostly low-grade heat. Modern TNs typically supply heat at about 70 C, although the temperature may be increased in cold weather to ensure adequate heating of the buildings served. (This is the TN alternative to gas networks' line pack.) The supply temperature may also be higher where conversion of older buildings to low temperature supply would be excessively costly. The needed heat can be obtained from a wide range of sources, which can change over time. In particular, initial heat sources that involve GHG emissions can be replaced by non-emitting sources with no impact on customers. Importantly, TNs can make use of existing residual heat from power generation, industry, commercial, wastewater and many other sources; and TNs can use heat collected from the sun. Furthermore, various types of thermal energy storage (TES) can economically store as much heat as needed for the best part of a year. That allows heat to be collected whenever it is available, e.g., during the summer, stored, and then recovered when needed.

To be sure, TNs also need electricity, notably for pumps and control systems, but also for temperature boosting heat pumps. But TNs' electric power needs are quite modest, or can be shifted in time to make use of electricity from non-emitting generation when the (potential) electricity supply exceeds demand (e.g., windy or sunny days).

Thermal power plants (nuclear, NG, other fuels) that use fuels to first produce heat and then use the heat to produce electricity always have residual heat. Instead of rejecting that residual heat to the environment, which is common today in Ontario, the plants can be configured to supply heat (at a profit) to TNs and reject far less heat to the environment. The overall efficiency with which heat from nuclear fuel is used can be increased from roughly 30% to as much as 90%. Such combined heat and power (CHP) plants can adjust the ratio of their electrical and heat

⁴ Degrees of heating needed (or heating degrees) are the difference between the threshold temperature, above which heating is not needed, minus the (effective) outdoor temperature at any given time. See Section 4 for details.

outputs at the convenience of the power company, making them effectively dispatchable and enabling improved utilization of intermittent renewable generation facilities (wind, solar). Differences between heat output and demand can be buffered by TES.

Such mutually beneficial linkage of electric power and thermal networks is referred to as sector coupling. It is made particularly attractive by the low cost of large-scale TES that can buffer between differences of heat supply and demand over periods from hours to years.

2.5. Summary

While neither the electrification or thermal networks pathway will be realistic as a universal solution, they provide "bookends" that might lay out the extremes and allow policy makers and utilities to consider the options, the relative costs and benefits and then do more work to support a better way forward.

Hybrid solutions for building decarbonization will employ a mix of electrification and thermal networks, with thermal networks generally preferred in urban and suburban areas and GSHPs in rural areas where there is sufficient land to make GSHPs viable. Strategic integration of the electricity and thermal network infrastructures can yield significant benefits to both.

Shortly before completing this report, we became aware of a recent publication from the United States' National Renewable Energy Laboratory (Simpson, Long and Zhu, 2024) that addresses similar issues.

3. Methodology

This work has been undertaken with the objective of obtaining results that are reliable and sufficiently complete for purpose. It makes extensive use of existing published materials and large data sets from reliable sources. Where specialist expertise was required, subject matter experts were engaged to undertake specific parts of the study. Over 10,000 lines of Python code was developed to collect, combine and analyze the data and produce numeric results and plots included in this report. The work involved a great deal of outreach and collaboration, within Canada and internationally.

3.1. Existing literature and other resources

All topics of interest in the present work have been studied elsewhere and reported on in academic journals, theses, reports and other forms at websites of governments, universities, research institutions, corporations, think tanks, etc. Extensive and repeated searches were undertaken to identify relevant references and save them in a database that has grown to over 800 entries. The Bibliography of this report (Section 14) includes references deemed to be particularly useful or relevant.

These references were used to inform and support each part of the present work. They have provided evidence, from Canada and elsewhere, that reduces the need to rely on assumptions when drawing conclusions. They have also helped validate or refute assumptions, both explicit and implicit, that often play significant roles in other published work and which have serious implications for the viability of Canadian efforts to reduce GHG emissions in the buildings sector.

3.2. Data

The work reported here has made extensive use of large volumes of openly-available data from reliable sources. The most important ones are listed below:

- Census** Data from the 2021 Canadian census (from <https://www.statcan.gc.ca/>) was used to determine the population and number of dwellings within any chosen geographic area (large or small), and the land areas and geographic boundaries of those areas.
- Weather** Weather station geographic coordinates and hourly temperature and dew point data were obtained from <https://climate.weather.gc.ca/> for 55 weather stations across Ontario, for time periods as needed.
- Electricity** The Independent Electricity Operator (IESO) makes a great deal of historical power system operating data available at <https://reports-public.ieso.ca/public/>. Most importantly, this includes hourly data on province-wide electricity demand and power generation by source type (nuclear, hydroelectric, natural gas, etc.), but other records were also used. Summary data for local distribution companies (LDC) was obtained from the Ontario Energy Board (OEB) (<https://www.oeb.ca/sites/default/files/yearbook-General-Statistics-2021.xlsx>).

Natural Gas Data on monthly natural gas consumption was obtained from the OEB (<https://www.oeb.ca/open-data/natural-gas-reporting-record-keeping-requirements-rrr-section-2114-natural-gas-quantities>) and from Statistics Canada (<https://www150.statcan.gc.ca/t1/tbl1/en/tv.action?pid=2510005901>).

Energy Use Tabular data from the NRCan Comprehensive Energy Use Database (CEUD) (https://oee.nrcan.gc.ca/corporate/statistics/neud/dpa/menus/trends/comprehensive_tables/list.cfm) and various StatCan tables were used to obtain estimates regarding consumption and buildings. Mandatory reporting, surveys and modeling are typically used by NRCan and StatCan to derive values for the tables, which sometimes leads to significant uncertainty about the accuracy of the stated values. These values may thus often differ significantly from the truth.

Important data that could not be obtained, either because suitable records do not exist or due to the information owners not facilitating or allowing access includes:

- data regarding electricity produced, stored and/or consumed at the distribution level (such as by solar PV panels and/or batteries) and thus not visible to the IESO
- data that characterizes the customer bases of LDCs, the power delivered by customer category (ideally at hourly resolution), and distribution-connected generation (e.g., solar PV)
- hourly electricity consumption and fuzzy location (e.g., FSA) for a statistically representative sample of pseudonymous electricity customers across Ontario – residential, commercial / institutional, industrial; all sizes
- natural gas consumption data that Enbridge Inc. discloses to municipalities with tight restrictions on further disclosure, and that Enbridge would not directly disclose for this project
- monthly natural gas consumption and fuzzy location data for a statistically representative sample of pseudonymous NG customers across Ontario – residential, commercial / institutional, industrial; all sizes
- buildings data held by the Municipal Property Assessment Corp. (MPAC) that would have cost much more to acquire than the entire project budget
- annual data on numbers of completed building retrofits, nationally or in different jurisdictions, including the specific envelope improvements made, the cost of each measure, and before and after energy consumption (electricity and fuels)
- annual data on heat pumps installed, nationally or in different jurisdictions, including products installed (models, supplementary heating, control systems), total installed costs (including electrical work), and before and after energy consumption (electricity and fuels).

Lack of suitable data could sometimes be coped with by making reasonable approximations or assumptions, informed by available data and the literature. However, lack of data did limit the scope and detail of analysis that could be undertaken.

3.3. Subject Matter Experts

Contributing members of the Boltzmann Institute have expertise and decades of experience covering all aspects of the project. This includes: amalgamation of district energy systems, electricity and heat generation, marketing of heat, consulting for municipalities, local electricity distribution companies and developers on energy development projects, community energy plan development, helping to establish multiple new district energy systems including feasibility studies, community information, negotiation of customer and supply contracts and electricity off-take, construction management, staff recruitment and training and operational technical and business support. Nonetheless, external expertise and capacity was engaged for specific elements of the work.

A leading district energy engineering firm, FVB Energy, Inc., was engaged to develop a plan and business case for implementation of district energy for an entire generic, hypothetical community, including all required components of a complete system and associated costs. FVB reports are available as Annexes B and D.

An electric power management consultant, MIDAC Corp., with deep knowledge of the Ontario power system and its management was engaged to investigate the implications of adding electrified heating loads on the generation mix, GHG emissions and household cost of electricity and total energy. The MIDAC report is available as Annex A.

The McMaster Institute for Energy Studies (MIES) at McMaster University was engaged to undertake detailed studies on: the thermal energy demand of buildings; the real-world performance characteristics of heat pumps; characteristics and costs of various kinds of thermal energy storage; and the zero-emissions sources of recoverable heat within communities. Three MIES reports are available, on reasonable request, as Annex C. (Material in the MIES reports is being submitted by students and their co-authors for publication in peer-reviewed journals. Once published, requests for Annex C will be responded to by providing references to the published papers.)

3.4. Analysis

The reference materials and data discussed above provided the foundation for analysis of the heating decarbonization pathways. Much code was developed to characterize, in considerable detail, the hourly heating demand in communities across Ontario during the period 2018 to 2023 for which all necessary data was available. Manufacturers' product specifications and published results of real-world field studies were used to develop realistic, but optimistic models of heat pump performance. Those models then allowed calculation of the estimated hourly electric power demand that would result if various scenarios of heating electrification had been in place instead of the actual natural gas heating.

By focusing on past years, the weather-dependent electric power demand for electrified heating scenarios could be added to the actual electrical demand for those years to determine the full power system impact. The complication and uncertainty that would have been incurred by attempting to model future years were deemed so great as to not be worthwhile.

Notwithstanding the mismatch of actual 2022 weather and the IESO's projection for 2050, Annex A obtained a rough estimation of the dramatic impact of electrified heating in 2050 by adding the 2022 electrified heating demand to hourly power demand projected by the IESO for 2050.

Reliance on assumptions has been kept to a minimum; where they have been necessary they and their potential implications have been made explicit. Uncertainties involved in the modeling have been estimated and stated along with the results. Where feasible, multiple data sources, different modeling approaches (such as top down and bottom up), modeling by independent researchers, and statistical analysis have been used to judge validity, identify discrepancies, and guide the estimation of uncertainties.

3.5. Study Tour

Undertaken separately and funded by the participants, the Boltzmann Institute organized a study tour of district energy facilities in Northern Europe. A detailed report on the study tour was prepared, including conclusions that summarize the learnings that can help guide large-scale development of district energy in Canada (Gilbert, Halim and Taylor, 2024).

3.6. Outreach and Collaboration

Outreach efforts resulted in useful collaboration with numerous relevant organizations. These included:

- Indigenous communities, particularly Oujé Bougoumou, with whom Michael Wiggin has had a professional relationship for 30 years, and Bingwi Neyaashi Anishinaabek in northern Ontario were consulted.
- Natural Resources Canada: experts in various departments including the nuclear division, office of energy R&D, and CANMET – the research sector including community energy systems, buildings, solar energy and seasonal energy storage
- The Ontario Society of Professional Engineers Energy Task Force
- Universities: McMaster, Toronto, Carleton, University of Ontario Institute of Technology, Concordia's McNeil Centre, University of Ottawa
- Municipalities: Durham Region, Peel Region, the Cities of Markham and Toronto, Ottawa, Kitchener-Waterloo and others.
- Industry: Independent Electricity System Operator (IESO), Ontario Power Generation (OPG), Markham District Energy, Enbridge Gas, Enbridge Gaz Québec, AtkinsRéalis, Thermistor, Urecon, PCL Construction, Theta Concepts (Germany), General Motors
- Associations: Canadian Nuclear Association, RealPAC (the national association representing top tier executives and decision makers of the Canadian commercial real estate industry), Canadian Nuclear Society
- (IEA DHC TCP) International Energy Agency District Heating and Cooling Technology Collaboration Party, OECD Nuclear Energy Agency, EuroHeat and Power, IDEA, Cogen Europe.

- Other Non-Profits, including Transition Accelerator, Ontario Clean Air Alliance, Canadian Climate Institute.

The following project-related outreach activities were also undertaken:

Heating Planning Conference

This 1-day conference in Toronto attracted over 100 participants, including many from local municipalities. Post-event surveys indicated many attendees agreed that effective heating planning will be a prerequisite to progress down either Pathway to zero emissions from buildings. See Section 10 for an account of this event, and <https://bi-ib.ca/events> for material presented there.

Position Paper and Executive Workshop

The position paper "Thermal Networks and Nuclear Energy – Advancing the Dialogue towards Clean Heat Infrastructure for Canada" (Friedrich et al., 2024) was a collaborative effort of the Boltzmann Institute, senior advisors to the Canadian Nuclear Association, and McMaster University. It was presented and discussed during a 1-day Executive Workshop in February, 2024. Follow-up efforts continue: to increase awareness and understanding by key stakeholders and decision makers, and to elicit action on the Position Paper's recommendations.

Canadian Nuclear Society Session on Nuclear CHP and Thermal Energy Systems

While this Conference Session will take place after the finalization of this report, the consultation and preparation was well underway as part of this report consultation and as a follow-up to the development of the above position paper. The Session promises to expose the Canadian Nuclear industry and electric utilities to the substantial opportunity to increase the contribution of nuclear power to decarbonize the building heating sector. Consultation and related research revealed that the possibility of enabling nuclear generators to produce variable output of heat and electricity at constant reactor output could make them more "dispatchable" while also substantially increasing nuclear revenues.

3.7. Publication of results

This main report for the Two Pathways project, all Annexes and related products noted below are published at <https://zenodo.org/communities/twopathways> to ensure their long-term availability. Suitable links can also be found on the Boltzmann Institute website, <https://bi-ib.ca>. Annexes A through D have been noted in Section 3.3. Annex E addresses Distributional Consequences of the two pathways, expanding on Section 8.

A mini-report was produced for each of the 55 electricity local distribution companies (LDCs) in Ontario for which adequate data could be obtained. They are contained within a separate annex. Their content is briefly described in Section 12.

The Boltzmann Institute produces District Energy Digest, with reviews and comments on recent happenings relevant to district energy, every four months. It is distributed by email to about 350 persons concerned with district energy, mostly in Ontario with some in other provinces and abroad, and published at <https://bi-ib.ca/publications>. Beginning with Issue No. 5 (June

WHAT WE'LL SEE DOWN TWO PATHWAYS TO ZERO EMISSIONS FROM BUILDINGS

2023), a two- to three-page annex on progress of the Two Pathways project was added to the Digest's regular six to eight pages.

A documentary video was made to tell the story of Two Pathways, including on-site interviews with participants. To access the video, go to <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15580866>.

4. Buildings Heat Demand

Energy consumption for space heating and cooling and for heating of domestic hot water (DHW) is the dominant cause of operational GHG emissions in the buildings sector (Xiang et al., 2023). Today, those emissions are due, almost entirely, to fossil fuels – primarily natural gas, but also fuel oil, propane, etc. – consumed at buildings, or consumed to generate electricity that is supplied to buildings, or in the life-cycle activities of producing and delivering the fuels and repairing environmental damage afterwards.

Building retrofits – primarily envelope improvements such as air sealing, insulation, and better doors and windows – can reduce the energy needed for heating (and cooling). New buildings are already being built to high standards, which are progressively being made even more stringent in many jurisdictions (if not in the Ontario Building Code – see Section 9). For existing buildings, retrofits are seen as an important way to reduce thermal energy needs. Changes to heating systems, such as installation of heat pumps or conversion to district heating, are considered here to be distinct from retrofits; they are considered in later sections.

Better buildings have lower operational GHG emissions, but that comes at a cost of greater embodied emissions.⁵ While they might be very significant, estimation of the increased embodied emissions due to high standards and various retrofit measures is beyond the present work.

Also beyond are GHG emissions caused by energy use in or at buildings for purposes other than heating, such as for lighting, appliances, electronics, swimming pools, and motors.

As can be seen in the left chart of Figure 4.1, heating Ontario's buildings uses more energy than all the electrical energy used for all purposes. Energy from natural gas is twice that from electricity; NG, burned at buildings, powers about 70% of space heating.⁶ The right chart shows that peak power for heating, whether from NG or from electricity for hypothetical ASHPs in place of NG, is far greater than the current electricity peak.

⁵ On top of operational emissions, the emissions embedded in construction material supply chains for retrofits and new buildings are significant. Clean Energy Canada estimates that the production, transport and demolition of construction materials used in public infrastructure accounts for approximately [8 million tonnes of greenhouse gas emissions annually](#). If private construction is considered, this figure increases to [approximately 28 million tonnes](#), which is equivalent to around half of Canada's electricity generation emissions or four percent of Canada's total emissions in 2021." Quotation from: <https://natural-resources.canada.ca/energy-efficiency/building-energy-efficiency/canada-green-buildings-strategy-transforming-canada-s-buildings-sector-net-zero-resilient-future>, accessed February 26, 2025.

⁶ NRCan CEUD (NRCan, 2023) data indicates that NG provides about 80% of energy for space heating – 72% in the residential sector and 89% in the commercial / institutional sector. The electricity portions of space heating energy are 17% residential and 22.1% commercial / institutional. CEUD has no space heating data for the industrial sector. However another CEUD table reports that about 65.5% of residential heating systems use natural gas and 12% use electricity. We use 70% as a conservative portion of the energy from NG, recognizing +10%/-5% uncertainty. Some analysis detailed below assumes 65% of residential buildings have NG heating.

Figure 4.1. Left: Annual energy consumption in Ontario – NG by sector, and delivered electricity and space heating showing contributions of NG and other energy sources. Right: Annual mean and peak power for all electricity, for existing heating by NG, and the likely electricity demand if ASHPs were to replace NG heating.⁷

This Section is focused on the hourly need for heat, and the potential to reduce both the peak power and total energy needed. (How the two pathways might supply the needed heat is addressed in Sections 5 and 6.) Subsection 4.1 describes how available data was used to obtain an estimate of hourly energy demand for buildings heated by natural gas in Ontario for six recent years. The effort and prospect for building retrofits to reduce the heat demand is discussed in Subsection 4.2. The Section closes with a summary of the above.

4.1. Estimating Space Heating Demand

To decide how best to keep buildings warm it is important to understand how much heat is needed and when. Ideally, the numbers, characteristics and energy use of existing buildings would be known at a granular level – e.g., municipality or subdivision. But such numbers are either tightly guarded or just not available.

Since detailed data are not readily available, other means must be used to determine the approximate heat demand for buildings in areas of interest. The Comprehensive Energy Use Database (CEUD) indicates that about 70% of the energy for space heating in Ontario comes from natural gas (NRCan, 2023).⁸ Data for monthly NG consumption was obtained from Statistics

⁷ Data presented in the charts are the result of Two Pathways project analysis of primary data from many sources.

⁸ The accuracy of data given in the CEUD is unknown, and is likely uneven. The CEUD methodology has not been fully disclosed, but it does make use of surveys and tracking of numbers of products shipped and their rated efficiencies. There is no evidence of the use of empirical methods, such as statistically-robust field studies, to verify data values or estimate their uncertainty. It is not evident whether real-world product performance at lower than rated efficiencies, including due to aging, has been taken into account.

Figure 4.2. Natural gas consumption obtained from OEB and StatCan, with sectoral breakdown of StatCan data.

Canada (StatCan) and the Ontario Energy Board (OEB) (StatCan, 2024; OEB, 2024). StatCan provides separate data for the residential, commercial and industrial sectors. OEB gives separate data for residential and non-residential sectors. As can be seen in Figure 4.2, there are differences of several percent between the StatCan and OEB residential and total NG consumption numbers.

More fine-grained monthly data about NG consumption is provided to municipalities by Enbridge Inc., but permission to disclose that data to others is severely limited. Toronto, for example, has disclosed the total annual NG consumed by single-family homes and the corresponding number of homes (Toronto, 2024). Data for shorter time intervals (e.g., daily or hourly) does not seem to be available.

By contrast, the Independent Electricity System Operator (IESO) makes copious data openly available (IESO, 2025a). Figure 4.3 shows many years of hourly values and their monthly averages for total electric power demand and NG generation. Figure 4.2 shows obvious winter and summer peaks of industrial and total (both StatCan and OEB) NG consumption and an upward trend in later years. Taking into account the approximately 43% average efficiency of NG generation in Ontario, these peaks and trend can be roughly accounted for by the NG usage for electric power

Figure 4.3. Ontario electricity power demand (hourly (blue) and monthly average (red)) and electricity generation by natural gas (hourly (red) and monthly average (black)).

generation shown in Figure 4.3.⁹ In recent years, NG generation is used to serve an increasing fraction of the variable load and to accommodate about half of the seasonal variability.

The hourly total power demand in Figure 4.3 shows large fluctuations and summer peaks due to air conditioning (A/C), which is highly weather dependent. Note that A/C systems remove perhaps three times as much thermal energy from buildings as the electrical energy they use; i.e., A/C has perhaps 300% efficiency. Commonly used electric resistance heating has 100% efficiency. On a hot summer day, about 10 C degrees of cooling might be needed; on a cold winter day 35 C degrees of heating could be needed. That winter fluctuations and peaks are smaller than the summer A/C fluctuations and peaks is to be expected, since electricity is currently used for almost all cooling but only a small fraction ($\lesssim 10\%$) of space heating.

A building's need for heating or cooling varies directly with the outdoor temperature. The heating for some specific large collection of buildings, such as buildings currently heated by NG in a defined geographic region, depends on the temperature at each of the buildings. Together

⁹ The average efficiency of NG generation in Ontario was determined by comparing IESO data on electric energy (MWh) from NG generation to GHG emissions reported in Canada's National Inventory Report (PSPC, 2022).

with the NG data discussed above, three large data sets were used to estimate hourly heating demand, for the years 2018 through 2023, for buildings with existing NG heating in any chosen region across Ontario. This includes the whole province. Specifically:

- hourly temperature data was obtained for 57 weather stations across Ontario ¹⁰
- data files from the 2021 Census were used to determine the population, number of dwellings, and population density for any desired geographic area, from the smallest (Dissemination Block (DB)) to all of Ontario ¹¹
- six years of hourly electricity consumption by (small) customers with smart meters, aggregated separately for residential and commercial customers in each postal Forward Sortation Area (FSA), was obtained from the IESO (IESO, 2025a).

The above data was used to determine patterns of electricity consumption for each of 55 electricity local distribution companies (LDCs) across Ontario. (Insufficient or no data was available for eight other LDCs.) To illustrate, Figure 4.4 shows analysis results for Toronto Hydro residential customers on all mid-week days (Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday). A different colour is used for each hour of the day (EST) to separate time-of-day effects from outdoor temperature effects. Hour 0 consumption is for the hour ending at midnight.

The temperatures on the horizontal axis are a decaying exponential moving average of past temperatures with an 18 hour time constant. This is the time constant that yields the simplified model curves that fit the data for each hour-of-day with the smallest standard deviation.¹² It can be understood as a consequence of the thermal mass of buildings and their contents slowing the response to outdoor temperature changes. Best fit time constants for different LDCs ranged from 14 hours to 27 hours, with most of the scatter likely due to sparse data; the population-weighted mean value for all Ontario is 17.6 hours. When different FSAs within an LDC have different closest weather stations, the temperatures used are a weighted average based on the fraction of population closest to each weather station.

Although it varies depending on the hour of day, the Toronto Hydro minimum power demand occurs at about 13 C (12.7 ± 0.7 C), which has been used for the calculation of heating degrees (see below). The steady power increase as the temperature drops below 13 C indicates electricity use for heating, which will include electricity used by NG heating systems (e.g., blowers). Starting a few degrees above 13 C, power demand for cooling rises gradually until it reaches a constant slope above about 24 C (24.1 ± 2.1 C). The gradual transition, modeled as a quadratic curve, is believed to be due to different people having widely different objectives and behaviours regarding cooling. Solar input and resident behaviour patterns may contribute to the curves' different characteristics at different times of day.

¹⁰ Climate data was from <https://climate.weather.gc.ca/>.

¹¹ Census data is available at <https://www.statcan.gc.ca/>.

¹² It has been suggested that Figure 4.4 seems excessively neat, but that is what results from analyzing each hour-of-day as described. All the data points are shown; colouring makes systematic patterns evident.

Figure 4.4. Average per-customer electricity consumption recorded by residential smart meters in FSAs across Toronto for every hour of all Tuesdays, Wednesdays, and Thursdays in the years 2018 through 2023, holidays excluded. Each hour-of-day (EST) is shown in a different colour; hour 0 ends at midnight. The abscissa is the weighted moving average of past local ambient temperatures, with the weight for h hours in the past decreasing as $\exp(-h/tc)$. The time constant $t_c = 18$ hours yields the hourly-fit curves relative to which the measured data has the smallest combined standard deviation.

The determined time constants and threshold temperatures were used to calculate the number of degrees of heating required in each LDC at each hour, referred to here as heating degree hours (HDH), over the entire six-year time period. Figure 4.5 shows the results for Toronto. Very similar plots were obtained for all 55 LDCs with adequate smart meter data.

Given the HDH records, the next task was to determine how much natural gas was used to maintain the buildings in each LDC at the occupants' chosen indoor temperatures. Elements of the calculation include:

- The CEUD indicates that about 65% of buildings are heated with NG.
- Detailed information could not be obtained on where NG service is available in Ontario or how many buildings have NG service in each LDC. An assumption was thus made that all

Figure 4.5. Six years of heating degree hours (HDH) for Toronto.

buildings located in areas with population density $\rho \geq \rho_{min}$, that collectively have 65% of the population, also have NG service.

- From census data it was determined that 65% of Ontario's population lives at density $\rho_{min} = 24$ people/ha or greater. The census data was also used to determine the population N_j at density $\rho \geq \rho_{min}$ in each LDC, where the index j identifies the LDC.
- Weighting LDC j according to N_j , the LDC-specific HDH records were combined to obtain the province-wide HDH in each hour.

Fitting the residential NG data, shown in Figure 4.2, to the province-wide HDH, and assuming 85% average efficiency of NG heating equipment, indicated that province-wide power for electric resistance heating (100% efficient) is 1823 MW per °C of heating. Figure 4.6 shows the power that would have been required to replace all the NG heating in Ontario with electric resistance (ER) heating. Since aggregated data was used to estimate the power demand, it is already fully diversified; the analysis of FSA data shows that statistical demand variations about the fitted values at each hour have standard deviations as high as 10 percent.

If the actual mean efficiency of NG heating equipment is greater (less) than 85% then the power shown in Figure 4.6 will be correspondingly too low (high).

Figure 4.6. The plot shows the hourly electric power that would be required to replace all existing natural gas heating with electric resistance (ER) heating. If ASHPs with ER backup were used instead then the peaks would be slightly lower while the total electric energy (area under the curve) would be reduced by about 60%. The overall magnitude is uncertain to $\pm 20\%$, with much better confidence in the weather-dependent fluctuations.

Plots similar to Figure 4.6 can be produced for any smaller geographic region by scaling according to local census and weather data. This has been done for each LDC for which adequate smart meter data was available.

4.2. Retrofits to Reduce Building Heat Demand

Most buildings that exist today will still be in use and will disproportionately dominate the need for heat in 2050. Retrofitting existing buildings to greatly reduce their demand for heat has thus been seen as a priority. Whether significant demand reductions can be achieved for (almost) the entire buildings sector – not just a few buildings – requires that several assumptions be valid. These assumptions, whose validity and implications warrant critical examination, include:

- It will be feasible to ensure that almost all owners actually take the initiative and make the investments needed to achieve the required / expected heat demand reductions by retrofitting their buildings.

- Building retrofit measures, which may be implemented all at once or in successive tranches, will each yield net economic and other benefits to building owners.
- Independent action and major investment by millions of building owners, often with little prospect of economic payback, can be driven by promotion, incentives, regulation and other measures and be maintained for over two decades during which there will be five or more election cycles and possibly social-political-environmental-economic upheaval.
- Sufficient capability and capacity – financial, labour, organization, materials, supply chain – will be available to complete the desired building retrofits on the required timeline (Brocklehurst et al., 2021).
- Occupants of retrofitted buildings will not change their behaviour, on average, such that potential energy savings will be sacrificed for greater comfort and convenience (Pellegrino, Wernert and Chartier, 2022). (Such behavioural change is commonly referred to as a *rebound effect*.¹³)

No doubt, greatly reducing the heat demand of some buildings through energy efficiency measures is possible – there are numerous examples where it has been done. However, the actual rate of building retrofits in Canada has been on the order of 1 percent of buildings per year, and the mean heat loss reduction achieved by those retrofits has been on the order of 10 percent (Millyard, 2023; Giandomenico, Papineau and Rivers, 2022; Papineau, Rivers and Yassin, 2025). The collective effect is that building envelope improvements have been reducing existing buildings' need for heat by only 0.1 percent per year. Studies in Europe and elsewhere have also found similarly small retrofit rates (Kelly et al., 2022; Scott, 2023; Fořt and Āerný, 2022; Schoor, 2022). Although the analyses often do not separate out contributing factors, most energy savings seem to come from conversion from fossil-fuel heating equipment to ASHPs rather than from building envelope improvements. It is generally not clear, in published studies, whether energy consumption to produce the needed electricity and the corresponding GHG emissions are fully and properly accounted for.

It remains unknown whether, to what extent, and how quickly retrofitting can be scaled up and applied to almost all buildings. Careful investigation and analysis are needed to determine realistic expectations for energy savings through retrofits of existing buildings and the corresponding costs and benefits. Toronto has an ambitious plan called TransformTO (Toronto, 2025) that includes a strategy for retrofitting existing buildings, reducing heat demand of existing buildings across Toronto by 75% by 2040. However, there is little evidence that the strategy is viable or that actual retrofits are in line with the strategy. Embodied emissions, affordability and industrial capacity are major concerns (Green, 2021).

The high cost and slow rate of retrofits is well recognized, leading to recommendations that an industrialized approach be adopted (Haley and Torrie, 2021). The leading example of such an

¹³ The Jevons Paradox, first articulated by William Stanley Jevons in 1865, suggests that technological advancements that increase the efficiency of resource use can paradoxically lead to an overall increase in resource consumption, rather than a decrease. This happens because the increased efficiency can lower the cost of using the resource, which in turn stimulates demand and can lead to more overall usage.

industrialized approach is *energiesprong* (Schoor, 2022; Stanghini, 2023), conceived in 2010 in the Netherlands for retrofits of social housing. *Energiesprong* has been adopted in many countries, including initial efforts in Canada (SBC, 2025; NRCan, 2023b; Pope, 2024; RetrofitCanada, 2025). But none of those efforts have yet managed to retrofit more than 10,000 housing units, and many are below 1,000. Whether it would be feasible to scale within 10 to 20 years to hundreds of thousands or millions of units, or to extend beyond social housing is very much in doubt. And, while industrialization does bring unit costs down, the costs are still on the order of \$1,000 per square metre with no good evidence of societal return on investment.

4.3. Summary

Province-wide natural gas monthly consumption data, hourly temperature records from weather stations across Ontario, and hourly electricity consumption data from the IESO, including from smart meters at the FSA level, have been analyzed to determine both the magnitude of energy used to heat buildings and the hourly profile for the whole province and most of the electricity LDCs. The thermal mass of buildings makes their heat demand depend on a moving average of the outdoor temperature, with a typical time constant of 18 hours. Heating is generally not needed until the moving average of outdoor temperatures is below 13 C.

Lack of more detailed natural gas data and detailed data on large buildings (MURBs, commercial, industrial) necessitated simplifying assumptions, causing a $\pm 20\%$ uncertainty in overall energy demand magnitude. Hourly fluctuations are found with much better confidence.

Numerous research studies of building retrofit efforts, mostly in Europe where programs are well-developed, indicate that reducing energy demand with retrofits is challenging, for many reasons, and very expensive. Retrofits are unlikely to make a material difference in energy demand by 2050.

5. Electrification Pathway

"... should significant electrification of heating applications (e.g., via air-source heat pumps) materialize, winter peaks could increase significantly in areas currently reliant on natural gas, oil or propane for heating." (Ontario, 2024)

The electrification pathway, as commonly advocated and considered here, includes:

- building retrofit measures, undertaken to reduce the need to expend externally acquired energy (e.g., electricity, fuels) to maintain a healthy, comfortable indoor environment
- conversion of space and water heating equipment (and possibly household appliances) to efficient, electrically power equipment – notably, but not only, heat pumps
- measures to acquire energy from the environment (wind, sunlight, etc.), for use at the building and/or supplying electricity to the grid
- measures to store energy (e.g., batteries, thermal storage) at buildings so that it can be used more advantageously at a later time
- measures implemented by electric utilities to manage customer loads by adjusting the operation of customers' equipment (e.g., thermostat, thermal storage, water heater settings).

These elements are addressed separately, below, even though they are often collectively referred to as building retrofits.

Electrification can be achieved, and often is, solely by replacing at-building equipment that uses fossil fuels with alternative at-building equipment powered by electricity – e.g., replacing a failed gas furnace with an ASHP (with electric resistance supplementary heat). All other measures are designed to reduce the demand for utility-provided electricity and/or the time-dependence of electricity demand.

Missing from the above list, but addressed in detail in later parts of this Section, is perhaps the most important element of the electrification pathway:

- provision of reliable, affordable, zero-emissions electric power to meet the increased power demands of **all** buildings whose heating and other uses of natural gas or other fossil fuels are converted to electricity.

The need for, and cost of, increased capacity to supply zero-emissions electric power are almost always left out of analyses. Even with the present Ontario power system, the additional power demands of electrified heating (with ASHPs) for just 5% of buildings will be met mostly by burning more natural gas at about 43% average efficiency. We will see that, contrary to common assumptions, it is not true that the additional power needed for a heat pump will be generated at the average emissions factor of the grid. Although natural gas would no longer be burned at the 5% of buildings with electrified heating, the increased grid emissions limit the net reduction of GHG emissions to about 14%. Moreover, most of the expense of providing more electricity will

be covered by a 2% power cost increase borne by the millions of customers who have not electrified their heating.

The true challenge posed by the last bullet, above, becomes evident when one considers the prospect of replacing almost all existing natural gas heating with electrified heating using ASHPs. On a very cold winter day, the power required for the electrified heating alone would increase the peak demand on the Ontario power system by more than twice the current peak demand. Assuming it could be done by 2050, which is doubtful, increasing the power system capacity that much might cost over \$500 billion! (See Annex A.)

5.1. Building Retrofits

There are widely held expectations that retrofits to buildings by owners will result in a significant reduction of aggregate heat demand for all buildings in any given community. For example, as noted in Section 4.2, Toronto's Net-Zero Strategy "TransformTO" expects building retrofits to reduce heat demand of existing buildings across Toronto by 75% by 2040.

Although it is often claimed that retrofits will yield a net economic benefit, such claims are not well supported by empirical evidence and detailed analysis. Indeed, it is generally understood that grants or other support are needed to induce owners to undertake the costly envelope improvements (windows, doors, attic and exterior wall insulation) needed to reduce building heat demand by much more than 10%.

The costs can be truly extraordinary. To achieve 75% thermal energy demand reduction, Toronto estimated the average cost per single-family home to be about \$277,000 (Toronto, 2021). This includes the cost of installing heat pumps and other measures beyond building envelope improvements, but those are unlikely to be more than one third of the total cost; and costs have gone up since 2021. Only a very small fraction of homeowners could afford such retrofits; annual payments on a \$277,000 loan at 3% for 30 years would be about \$14,000. That's far in excess of the annual cost of energy, so there is no possibility of ever recovering the investment. Advice from German experts on heating planning (Section 10) is that energy reductions of 10 to 20% for existing buildings might be realistic.

We are not suggesting that reducing heat demand should not be a goal. Indeed, energy efficiency should be a key criterion when deciding whether and how to upgrade or replace building components and energy-consuming devices. However, as shown in Section 6, it may often be more effective and efficient to direct investments to other ways of improving energy efficiency.

For the present work, considering both the high cost of retrofits and the limited thermal energy demand reductions actually achieved (as discussed in Section 4.2) it is assumed that the collective result of (i) envelope improvements through retrofits of existing buildings, (ii) elimination of some old buildings from the stock, and (iii) addition of new buildings built to contemporary standards will be that the total heat demand remains roughly constant until 2050. This assumption will introduce an uncertainty of perhaps $\pm 25\%$ in the total heat demand, but that will not be material to the results. Any effort to avoid this assumption would require a major

research and modeling effort that is beyond the scope of the present work, and may still not yield a more reliable estimate of the 2050 demand.

5.2. Heat Pumps

Heat pumps are seen as critical technology for making electrification of heating viable. During cold weather, buildings need heat in order to replace heat that naturally escapes from the warm indoors to the colder surrounding environment. A heat pump, used for heating, uses input electrical energy to pump even more energy (in the form of heat) from the surrounding environment into the building. The ratio of the thermal energy transferred to the building to the electrical energy consumed (by compressor, pumps, fans, blowers, etc.) is the system's efficiency factor, or coefficient of performance (COP). Figure 5.1 illustrates the functional design of an ASHP.

By reversing the flow of refrigerant through the indoor and outdoor heat exchangers, the same heat pump can be used to cool buildings when it is hot outside. In some cases, the heat pumped out of the building when cooling can be preserved for other uses instead of being discarded to the environment. In what follows, discussion of heat pumps will apply to operation in heating mode unless cooling mode is explicitly specified.

Figure 5.1. ASHP functional design, with heating mode shown. For cooling, the reversing valve effectively swaps the functions of the indoor and outdoor coils.¹⁴

¹⁴ Figure from <https://www.energy.gov/energysaver/air-source-heat-pumps>.

Figure 5.2. GSHP functional design, with heating mode shown. For cooling, the reversing valve effectively swaps the functions of the indoor and outdoor refrigerant heat exchangers.¹⁵

The type / configuration of heat pump used for a given installation depends on what part of the surrounding environment the heat is drawn from and how the heat will be transferred to the air within the building.

An air-source heat pump (ASHP) extracts heat from cold outdoor air and transfers it first to refrigerant and then to the indoor air. The heat transfer to indoor air uses either a refrigerant-to-air heat exchanger (including a blower), as shown in Figure 5.1, or a refrigerant-to-water heat exchanger that heats the circulating water in a hydronic heating system.

A ground-source heat pump (GSHP) is functionally very similar to an ASHP but, instead of from the ambient air, heat is drawn from the ground. A glycol solution is circulated through a loop of plastic pipe into either one or more deep boreholes or a horizontal loop buried below the frost line. Also interesting, but less used, are energy piles that incorporate the ground loops into building foundations (Alberdi-Pagola, 2018). The glycol is cooled in a heat exchanger by cold refrigerant, circulated through the ground loop, and returns warmer back to the heat exchanger where the heat is transferred to the refrigerant, evaporating it in the process. Figure 5.2 illustrates the functional design of a GSHP. (Just as with ASHPs, the indoor components can also be configured to support hydronic heating.) As a bonus, GSHPs can often also be configured to efficiently heat domestic hot water throughout the year.¹⁶

¹⁵ Figure from <https://www.123zeroenergy.com/how-does-a-geothermal-heat-pump-work.html>.

¹⁶ Some air-to-water heat pumps can also heat hot water, but not air-to-air heat pumps, the most common ASHPs.

A water-source heat pump works very much like a GSHP, but instead of the outdoor fluid loop being buried in the ground it extends into a river, lake or pond, where the water stays reliably above 0 C even when the needed amount of heat is extracted from it. Water-source heat pumps will rarely be viable for heating of individual buildings, so they will not be considered further in this Section. Their value for thermal networks will be considered in Section 6.

5.3. Heat Pump Performance

A heat pump's performance is characterized by its heating capacity (the amount of heat it can add to the building each hour) and its efficiency (COP). Both the capacity and COP depend on the temperature of the medium (air, ground) from which the heat is drawn and the desired indoor temperature.

The performance characteristics of ASHPs are of particular concern. For thermodynamic reasons, both the COP and the heating capacity of an ASHP decrease as the outdoor ambient temperature drops, while at the same time the building's demand for heat increases. This is shown in Figure 5.3.

Numerous field studies of ASHPs have found that typical performance falls significantly short of manufacturers' specifications (Carroll, Chesser and Lyons, 2020; RDH, 2020; RDH, 2021; Oikonomou, 2022; Marsik and Stevens, 2022; Marleau, 2023; Winkler and Ramaraj, 2023). Cold-climate ASHPs (ccASHP), designed to perform well even at very low temperatures, are included in these field studies.

Actual performance of individual ASHPs in the field studies was found to vary over significant ranges of both COP and capacity. However, if it is assumed that very large numbers of many different models and sizes of ASHPs will be installed as part of the electrification pathway, then it is most practical to work with average performance curves. Figure 5.4 shows piecewise-linear curves believed to fairly represent field study results. In the plot: COP_{heating} is the COP of the ASHP itself without consideration of supplementary heat; "ASHP fraction" is the ASHP heating capacity as a fraction of the heating load, capped at 1 when the capacity exceeds the load; and COP_{adj} indicates the adjusted / combined COP of the complete system of ASHP and, when the ASHP fraction is less than 1, supplementary electric resistance heat (which has $COP_{\text{ER}} = 1$).

This simple model, which has been used in the present work, is believed to be conservative in the sense that the true average performance of ASHPs installed by many thousands of building owners and with a range of ages spanning typical equipment lifetimes will likely be no better than indicated by the model. The supplementary heating is presumed to be electric resistance, not natural gas, because that will be necessary to achieve net-zero GHG emissions. Of particular note is that COP_{adj} approaches 1 at temperatures below -20 C.

GSHPs have the potential to provide heating at significantly lower total cost than ASHPs (Dunsky, 2020). Numerous studies have investigated real-world GSHP performance (Huelman et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2016; Bockelmann and Fisch, 2019; Abdel-Salam, Zaidi and Cable, 2021; Gao et al., 2021; Weeratunge et al., 2021; Yin, Pate and Battaglia, 2022; Eriksson, 2022; Zhi et al., 2025). GSHPs tend to maintain a more constant and consistently higher COP than ASHPs because

Figure 5.3. A representative illustration of the dependence on outdoor temperature of heating demand (Load Line), ASHP Output Capacity and ASHP COP. Annotations show typical use of backup heating at low temperatures.¹⁷

the heat transfer is more efficient and the ground temperature does not get nearly as cold as the ambient air. More advanced GSHPs with two-stage or variable speed (inverter) compressors have higher COPs, with average seasonal values approaching 4. Rather than the complicated performance model of ASHPs, GSHPs are assumed on average, in this work, to have constant COP = 4.

Since the thermal conductivity of the ground is very low, GSHP boreholes can get progressively colder if more heat is taken out in cold weather than is restored in warm weather. Over a period of many years this can lead to significant performance issues due to both decreased COP and correspondingly decreased heating capacity. Anecdotally, this has proven to be a significant problem for Ontario GSHPs where inadequate care has been taken to maintain annual heat balance. By contrast, the earth surrounding a shallow-buried horizontal ground loop will have its heat naturally restored by the sun during the summer.

¹⁷ Figure adapted, with addition of the green COP curve, from [https://natural-resources.canada.ca/sites/nrcan/files/canmetenergy/pdf/ASHP%20Sizing%20and%20Selection%20Guide%20\(EN\).pdf](https://natural-resources.canada.ca/sites/nrcan/files/canmetenergy/pdf/ASHP%20Sizing%20and%20Selection%20Guide%20(EN).pdf).

To maintain boreholes at a higher temperature, and improve performance, a common measure is to add solar thermal collectors to GSHP installations. These are referred to as solar-assisted GSHPs (SAGSHP) (Adebayo et al., 2024). Provided boreholes are not allowed to get progressively colder, properly sized GSHPs generally should not require supplementary heating for very cold weather.

(Functionally similar to the ground heat exchangers used by GSHPs are large ground heat exchangers, which may have many boreholes. These large systems are often referred to as *geoexchange*. They may be configured for use by large, industrial heat pumps to provide heating and cooling for large buildings or thermal networks, or by many smaller heat pumps as in 5G DHC (discussed in Section 6.1). It must be emphasized that geoexchange cannot use the ground as an endless source of heat. Annual balance must be maintained, as discussed above, or performance will progressively worsen.)

Figure 5.4. Simple ASHP performance model.

5.4. Electric Power System Impacts

Figure 4.6 showed the electrical power that would be required to replace natural gas heating in Ontario with electric resistance heating, such as common baseboard and portable heaters. Resistance heaters have an efficiency of 1; the thermal energy produced equals the electrical energy consumed. The peak power shown in Figure 4.6 for the electric resistance equivalent of Ontario's natural gas heating is about 59 GW. For heating only, that's 2.4 times the current peak power demand on the power system from all Ontario customers for all purposes. The average annual electrical energy for heating over the six years shown in Figure 4.6 is 99 TWh, which is 73% of the actual average electrical energy delivered during those years.

Of course, no one is advocating large-scale installation of resistance heating to replace natural gas when heat pumps offer significant efficiency advantages. As discussed above, GSHPs have consistently higher efficiency than ASHPs; but high costs and inadequate space for ground loops mean large-scale installation of GSHPs in existing urban areas is not viable.¹⁸ While GSHPs might be viable for detached homes in many suburban areas, lower costs for building owners and easier installation make ASHPs the option of choice for almost all buildings switching from natural gas. For illustration purposes, we'll consider a scenario in which only ASHPs are installed to replace natural gas heating.

¹⁸ For the purposes of this report we have assumed that GSHPs will be used primarily in areas with lower population density that have about 30% of the buildings. Improvements to drilling technology may lower costs and reduce the space requirement for a borehole or set of boreholes. This could allow GSHPs to be installed in higher density areas, including for existing buildings with underground garages.

Figure 5.5. Actual (Base) hourly Ontario power demand (blue) and what the demand might have been if all natural gas heating had been converted to ASHPs with electric resistance supplementary heating (red). The overall magnitude of the heating demand is uncertain to $\pm 25\%$; the hourly fluctuations are much less uncertain.

The ASHP performance model of Figure 5.4 was used to compute the hourly electrical demand if all existing natural gas heating were to be replaced by ASHPs, instead of by electric resistance heating. This involved use of the local hourly ambient temperatures to determine what COP_{adj} would apply in each location with population density $\rho > 24$ people/ha, which is where natural gas heating is most likely used (as discussed in Section 4.1). The resulting peak power estimate for ASHPs decreased just 800 MW to 58 GW from the 59 GW with electric resistance heating. The decrease is so small because $COP_{adj} \approx 1$ on very cold days, when electric resistance heat backs up ASHPs. By contrast, ASHPs lowered the average annual energy to 41 TWh, corresponding to average efficiency $\langle COP_{adj} \rangle = 2.39$.

Figure 5.5 shows the actual, or base, Ontario power demand over a two-year period plus the extra demand that would have resulted from conversion of all natural gas heating to ASHPs (with electric resistance backup). The quite obvious differences of demand in the two winters demonstrate how variable the weather and heating demand can be. Extreme electrical demand peaks that occur when $COP_{adj} \rightarrow 1$, in very cold weather, are about 3 times the base peak

demand (without electrified heating). In major centres like Toronto, where almost all buildings (not just 70%) have natural gas heating, electrification with ASHPs could result in peak demand increasing by a factor of 4.

The peak thermal power demand for space heating is about 5 times the annual mean thermal demand. However, due to the temperature dependence of COP_{adj}, the electric power for ASHP heating (with electric resistance backup) can have peaks as high as 12 times the annual mean power demand (for heating). New power system capacity must be added to reliably meet the peak demand for as long as extreme cold weather persists, which could be several days in Ontario. But energy sales will only be 1/12th of what that new capacity is capable of delivering. As discussed below, the low utilization will make power for ASHPs very expensive.

The above results have considered what the impact on electrical demand would have been in past years if natural gas heating had instead been provided with ASHPs. Attempting such calculations for future years would have required developing realistic models for future weather, future non-heating electrical demand (including increased electricity use for transportation and industry), and the future building stock, all of which would introduce much greater uncertainty.

Nonetheless, and recognizing the uncertainties involved, a simulation-based approach was used to project: the Ontario electricity demand in 2050; what generation mix a net-zero power system to meet that demand might have; and what the cost of electricity would likely be. While an hourly projection published by the IESO was used for the 2050 non-heating electrical demand, no corresponding hourly weather projection was available to allow projected heating demand to be properly aligned with the non-heating demand (IESO, 2025b). This will undoubtedly have resulted in underestimation of the 2050 peak demand. For the simulation details, see Annex A. The main results from the Executive Summary of Annex A are:

The analysis shows that:

- The electricity system capacity factor will drop approximately in half if we electrify space heating with ASHPs where natural gas is currently used.
- The drop in capacity factor will result in electricity rates that will more than double, not including general price inflation.
- The higher electricity rates combined with greater electricity use for ASHPs will result in a tripling of monthly energy bills for consumers, not including general price inflation.
- In a net-zero electricity system the amount of surplus clean electricity and discarded thermal energy, which could be used for building heating, will each be larger than the useful electric energy supplied to consumers for their ASHPs.
- The amount of new zero-emissions dependable generating capacity required to achieve net-zero by 2050 is much larger than Ontario's historical ability to add new electrical capacity in that period.
- Based on experience with heating buildings in cold climate countries in Europe and Asia it would be prudent to investigate alternatives to widespread ASHP electrification of building heating."

5.5. Peak Power Demand – Implications and Mitigation

From the above, it is clear that electrification of most or all natural gas heating in Ontario using ASHPs would create a need for greatly increased power system peak capacity – generation, transmission, and distribution. About 60% of that increased capacity would be needed only on very cold days – about 4% of hours. Analysis of Ontario temperature records shows that this includes continuous periods of more than 24 hours about four times, on average, per year, with the longest such period in years 2018 through 2023 being 99 hours.

On such cold days, the peak demand is driven up by reduced ASHP performance and increased use of backup resistance heating. For example, even when the ASHPs are collectively working their hardest and consuming their maximum power, which is about 21,700 MW, about 8,100 MW of electric resistance heat will be in use. The Toronto temperature at that time, Sunday January 7, 2018 at 11 AM, was -7 C, warming up from -18 C the previous evening. In still colder weather, ASHPs have less heating capacity and lower COP (see Figure 5.4); the power they use decreases while increased heat demand and greater reliance on backup resistance heating causes the total power demand to rise.

The simulations discussed in Section 5.4 showed that the future cost of net-zero electricity will be driven primarily by the capital investments required to increase the power system's reliable capacity. Operating costs, including fuel, will account for only a small fraction of customers' bills.

The issue of peak power demand, but perhaps not the magnitude or associated cost, is widely recognized. Several peak reduction strategies with optimistic assumptions were considered in McDiarmid (2023). But that study failed to recognize that, with large-scale electrification of heating, peak demand periods will be dominated by extreme cold weather that could persist for more than 24 hours. Commonly proposed ways to mitigate extreme peak electrical demand are discussed below.

Water heating

Building decarbonization will necessarily include conversion of water heating from natural gas to electricity. The CEUD (NRCan, 2023) indicates that, on an annual basis, water heating uses about 21% as much natural gas as space heating. (The percentage varies year-by-year, due mostly to weather differences.) Although relevant data could not be found, seasonal variation of the cold tap water temperature will result in greater energy demand for water heating in winter than in summer. Hot water usage also peaks in the morning and evening. A reasonable guess is that peak power demand for hot water produced with electric resistance heaters is 3 times the mean demand. Depending on coincidence of water and space heating peaks, this could add up to about 7,000 MW to the Ontario peak electricity demand.

It has been proposed that installing heat pump water heaters (HPWHs) instead of resistance water heaters would lessen the increased demand. That's because HPWHs pump heat with a COP greater than 1. However, almost all HPWHs work by drawing heat from the surrounding indoor air to heat the water. During the winter, the space heating system must make up the heat that is

taken by the HPWH, and in very cold weather that heat will be produced by electricity at a COP near 1. So the main way in which HPWHs will reduce the winter peak power demand is by heating water more slowly; the same peak demand reduction could be accomplished by using electric resistance heating with smaller elements. However, by cooling the indoor air during hot weather HPWHs will reduce the need for air conditioning and will thus help to reduce electrical demand peaks during the summer. Focused research would need to be undertaken to determine whether HPWHs offer significant value in cold climate regions.

Local electricity generation – solar PV panels

Solar PV panels installed locally, such as on houses or larger neighbourhood rooftops, can help meet electrical energy needs within a local distribution network. But they rely on sunlight; they do not provide reliable power on demand. PV panels will not reduce the peak demand on the Ontario power system, which, if heating has been extensively electrified, will most likely occur before sunrise on a winter morning. Since the cost of net-zero electric power will be dominated by capital cost, not energy, installing PV panels will only increase capital cost and total electricity cost. Moreover, PV panels installed by individual building owners will cost far more per kW (or kWh) than utility-scale installations (Hira and Krishnan, 2024).

Energy storage – electricity, heat

Optimists have suggested that energy storage (batteries, thermal storage) will be feasible and affordable to install and able to avoid large increases of grid-electricity demand during extreme cold spells. They fail to appreciate how much energy must be stored and the costs of doing so. A fully charged 13.5 kWh Tesla PowerWall 3 would be able to heat a typical Toronto detached home on a cold winter day for about 1 hour before being fully discharged. Battery capacities in fully electric cars and crossovers are typically 50 kWh to 100 kWh; pickup trucks and SUVs could have batteries as large as 200 kWh. So fully charged EV batteries might be able to heat the same home on a very cold day for 4 to 8 hours, at most. The notion that EV batteries could heat homes through an extreme cold spell is wishful – the batteries would be drained long before it warms up and homeowners would be left with no heat and a dead EV battery. Whether such use of EV batteries would be economically sensible is also very much in doubt (Wikipedia, 2025). If the batteries are limited to providing half the power needed for heating, with the rest taken from the grid, then they could last twice as long, but persistent cold weather would still leave the grid to meet the full demand after the batteries are dead. The widely-held expectation that battery storage will be able to reduce peak demand from electrified heating is not supported by thorough analysis. Batteries, for those who can afford them, will only add cost.

Whether utility-scale batteries could be used for large-scale management of power system peaks driven by heating electrification is also worth careful analysis. Existing utility-scale battery storage is only economical for 4- to 12-hour cycle times, which is good for traditional morning and evening peaks but not for multi-day heating loads. The cost of 4-hour utility-scale batteries is projected to be on the order of \$300 / kWh (or \$400 / kW) until 2050 (Cole and Karmakar, 2023). Heating, electrified with ASHPs, would have used over 1 TWh (1 billion kWh) during the 24 hours

prior to the above referenced peak ASHP demand (leaving out resistance heating) on Sunday January 7, 2018 at 11 AM. While it is recognized that longer duration batteries could have adequate power capacity and cost somewhat less, the cost of 4-hour batteries with 1 TWh energy capacity would be over \$300 billion.

Electric thermal storage (ETS) uses electricity when demand is low to produce and store heat in water, phase-change materials (PCM), or, most commonly, ceramic bricks. Then, when electrical demand is high, the stored heat is transferred as needed from the storage medium to the indoor air. The McDiarmid (2023) study assumed that ETS (ceramic bricks) is used 6 hours per day, 5 days per week during the heating season. Charging takes 11 hours at 61 A at 230 V (14 kW); this was assumed to always be at off-peak times with no consideration of whether that would be possible while ASHPs also draw power to heat the homes – likely not, for most Ontario houses. Discharge time is 13 hours; once discharged on a very cold day it would need to switch to resistance heat. Recharging would not be possible while it stays cold, without greatly increasing demand with both space heating and charging. Cold periods of much more than 12 hours would defeat the ability of ETS to reduce peak load.

ETS may be appropriate in parts of Quebec (and possibly some Ontario locations) where electric resistance heating is currently dominant and ETS could help manage morning and evening peaks. Hydro Quebec already offers ETS incentives in select communities. But ETS would not help reduce the peak electric power demand created by replacing natural gas heating with ASHPs.

Load management

Another proposal is that electric utilities could implement large-scale central control of "smart", at-building electrical equipment (thermostats, water heaters, (bi-directional) EV chargers, etc.) to actively limit the peak demand. For example: thermostat set points could be lowered a few degrees to reduce the operation of heat pumps (and backup resistance heating); and EV charging could be shifted off peak. This is already being done with thermostat setbacks, with customers who sign up offered a discount; and there is a long history of utility control of electric water heaters.

When one considers that electrified heating, as shown in Figure 5.5, could be responsible for two thirds of the peak demand, it becomes obvious that a meaningful reduction of the peak can only be accomplished by reducing the heat demand – i.e., lowering the thermostat set points in almost all buildings with electrified heating. Lowering the set point by 5 C on very cold weather days could potentially reduce the peak heating demand by up to about 15% – perhaps as much as 8,000 MW. But whether an imposed 5 C setback would be acceptable to most building owners is not obvious; many customers, even if signed up, may respond by turning on portable heaters.

The fundamental problem with such load management mechanisms is that they will all rely on not meeting the comfort expectations of building occupants. Even then, the benefits of lowering indoor temperature are fairly small. Cutting back on non-heating power use will not make a consequential difference.

5.6. Power Supply and GHG Emissions

The above discussion regarding power for electrified heating avoided considering whether the needed electricity would be available (at a cost) and have, at least by 2050, net-zero GHG emissions.

The IESO has indicated that, even without allowing for electrification of heating for existing buildings, there is not yet a known path to achieve net zero GHGs by 2050. Instead, the emissions are projected to more than double over the period 2027 to 2039, then decrease to about half the current level by 2050 (IESO, 2024a). That is for a contemplated demand growth by 2050 of about 75%, with the winter peak rising to about 37 GW (IESO, 2024b). Reduction of grid emissions would be made even more intractable by the additional flexibility requirement posed by the very variable and seasonal heating demand.

The IESO planning outlook does not include the 58 GW of peak demand, shown in Figure 5.5, that would result from electrification of existing natural gas heating using ASHPs with electric resistance backup. That means there is no plan to supply the electricity that would be needed for conversion of natural gas heating to ASHPs. Such a plan would also have to recognize the retail rate impact of ASHP power utilization as low as 8%, instead of 63% for the existing power system.¹⁹

Absent government subsidy, the investment needed to reliably meet the peak heating demand would have to be recovered by increasing rates. If spread evenly over all electricity uses then the rate would more than double. But if the costs incurred specifically to power heating were recovered from sales of power used for heating, without adjusting the non-heating rate, then the annual cost for heating power would be 8 times greater than a similar amount of energy used for non-heating purposes.

Looked at differently, the capital investment required to add power system capacity – generation, transmission, and distribution – to supply reliable electricity for ASHPs installed at-scale would be about 10 times the consumer investments to install the ASHPs. Heating electrification to date has not caused notable electricity rate increases only because the effect of a small number of ASHPs on overall rates is very small. Any actual costs have been spread over millions of customers.

If 5 million customers each pay 1 cent more per year over a 30-year amortization period of power system infrastructure, then that would sum to \$1.5 million – perhaps enough to cover the power system expansion costs to supply 10 homes converted from natural gas to ASHPs (with resistance backup). But if the 5 million customers were to share the costs for 100,000 ASHPs then they would each pay \$100 per year. With more ASHPs, the costs keep going up until eventually all 5 million have an ASHP and they each pay about \$5,000 per year – the true cost of expanding the electric power infrastructure. (Note that these numbers are illustrative; their uncertainty is high and the analysis simplistic, but the message should be clear.)

¹⁹ For the purposes of this discussion, utilization is defined as the mean power demand as a percentage of the peak power demand over the years 2018 through 2023. To ensure reliability, actual system capacity may be as much as 15% above the expected peak demand. Today, dispatchable NG generation ensures reliable peak capacity.

A similar analysis can be applied to GHG emissions. Over the period 2018 to 2023 the portion of Ontario power generated with natural gas increased from 7% to 14% (see Figure 4.3), with a corresponding increase of GHG emissions. The emissions are expected to increase still further, due to all four Pickering NGS B units being out of service for refurbishment, and emissions will not decrease back to current levels until after 2040. Even without large-scale electrification of space heating, natural gas generation will be used to meet electric power demand at most times when space heating is required, especially when it is very cold.

The average efficiency of Ontario's natural gas generation is about 43%. About 6.7% of Ontario electricity is lost during transmission and distribution to customers, reducing the effective efficiency to 40%. An ASHP operating with seasonal COP = 2.39 (see Section 5.4) and powered by electricity produced by burning natural gas would result in about the same GHG emissions as heating with a high-end natural gas furnace with 96% efficiency. The only difference is that with the ASHP the emissions occur at a power station instead of at the home.

(If a HPWH is installed in addition to an ASHP, then the emissions will be greater than from a high-end furnace and high-end tankless, condensing gas water heater.)

Many people would argue that if Ontario only generates 14% of its electricity with natural gas then that's the percentage that should be assumed for any new load, such as an ASHP. But adding a new load means that more power must be generated and, at present in Ontario, that usually means burning more natural gas – that's especially true in cold weather.

Suppose converting one natural gas furnace to an ASHP causes the power system to emit an additional 1 t CO₂eq/a. (Again, approximate numbers are used for illustration purposes.) Allocating those additional emissions equally to 5 million electricity customers would raise the emissions allocated to each of them by just 0.2 g CO₂eq/a, but the total will not change. If the same is done for 100,000 ASHPs then 20 kg CO₂eq/a would be attributed to each of the 5 million customers, which starts to look significant. Of course, it remains the case that each ASHP will have caused the power system's total emissions to increase by 1 t CO₂eq/a.

So the important question is: How will total GHG emissions change when building heating is converted from natural gas to ASHPs? To answer this, at least for the 2022 reference year, Annex A considers a scenario in which 5% of natural gas heat was replaced by ASHPs (with electric resistance backup for very cold days). The simulation determined the most likely generation mix to meet the existing demand plus the new demand from the ASHPs, and it calculated the net change in GHG emissions. The result is that emissions from at-building natural gas heating decrease by 1.1 Mt CO₂eq/a while power system emissions increase by 0.95 Mt CO₂eq/a – a net reduction of 14%, or 0.15 Mt CO₂eq/a.

The simulation's calculation assumed the furnaces being replaced averaged 85% efficiency. Upgrading those furnaces to 96% efficient furnaces would have achieved an 11% emissions reduction. Since natural gas use for generation has risen more than 50% since 2022, the grid emissions would now be higher; upgrading to better gas furnaces may be the better choice for reducing GHG emissions.

Hybrid solutions, considered in Section 7, may be a still better way to proceed both in terms of power supply and GHG emissions.

5.7. Electrification Pathway Summary

Electrification of space heating with air-source heat pumps, without natural gas backup on cold days, will likely be possible only for a small percentage of Ontario buildings. Early adopters are actually heavily subsidized – perhaps 90% – by all the other electric power customers. Based on the IESO's 2024 APO and emissions forecast, any reduction of GHG emissions until at least 2040 will be small, and might even be negative, since the additional electricity needed to power ASHPs will mostly be from gas-fired generation.

Large-scale decarbonization of existing Ontario buildings by converting from natural gas to ASHPs is almost certainly not feasible. Building retrofits are prohibitively expensive and are unlikely to reduce the heating demand by more than 10 to 20%; adding the needed reliable capacity to the Ontario power system by 2050 is not addressed in present plans and would not be feasible or economical.

The most likely outcome of trying to pursue the electrification pathway at-scale is that expanding the power system to meet the rising peak demand will become untenable and the cost of providing electricity will rise to a level that society cannot afford. In essence, this pathway is a dead-end.

6. Thermal Networks Pathway

Thermal networks **supply** heat to buildings at temperatures suitable for space and water heating. They eliminate the need to **produce** heat at buildings by consuming fuels or electricity. TN providers have responsibility for decarbonization, eliminating reliance on millions of individual building owners (and the electricity provider) as would be the case in the electrification pathway. TNs can use heat from many different sources, which may initially include fossil fuels but can be transitioned over time to non-emitting sources without customer involvement or impact (Manz et al., 2021; Directorate-General et al., 2024; Malcher and Gonzalez-Salazar, 2024).

Flexible options, including large-scale, economical thermal energy storage (TES), make TNs well suited to meet the highly variable demand for heat, including extreme peaks, at whatever scale is needed (Yang et al., 2021; Monie and Åberg, 2023; Sifnaios et al., 2023; Bolton et al., 2023; Vilén and Ahlgren, 2024). Heating with TNs has an important advantage of sparing the electric power system from the highly variable demand and low utilization that would result from large-scale use of at-building ASHPs (as discussed in Section 5).

TNs are economical where the demand for heat per meter of pipe is sufficient to justify the capital investment. Very roughly, that will be the case in non-rural areas that would also have sufficient demand density to warrant installation of a natural gas distribution system. In Ontario, that covers roughly 70 percent of all buildings and ~100 TWh/a of thermal energy. Even some compact rural villages could be well served by TNs, in part because there is no need for the heat to be piped in from some distance as is required for natural gas networks. Electrification of heating with heat pumps, primarily GSHPs, would remain the best decarbonization option for the remaining ~40 TWh/a of heat demand in areas that are not sufficiently dense for TNs to be economical; this is discussed further in Section 7.

Installing new networks of buried pipes carrying energy to most buildings along Ontario's urban and suburban streets may seem like too large an undertaking to be taken seriously. But it has been done before with great success. During the approximate period 1960 to 1980, a natural gas distribution network was installed to serve most of the non-rural Ontario population; houses and larger buildings were connected; and natural gas became the dominant energy source for space and water heating (and also for industrial heat and, more recently, greenhouses). Switching from coal and fuel oil delivered by truck to natural gas delivered through an underground piping network served to greatly reduce GHG emissions. Without the gas network infrastructure, that transition could not have happened. The gas network has been steadily expanded since 1980 to enable natural gas heating of the vast majority of new urban and suburban buildings.

A high-level introduction to TNs is given in the next subsection. That is followed by subsections on: sources of thermal energy used by TNs; thermal energy storage; the contemplated TN deployment scope; and the strategic approach that is believed necessary for successful TN implementation at the contemplated scale. The final subsection provides a summary.

6.1. Thermal Networks Overview

Thermal network (TN) is an umbrella term that embraces district heating (DH), district cooling (DC), and other features of modern thermal energy systems and their integration into the broader energy system, including electric power and renewable energy.

The brief introduction to TNs in Section 2.2 is expanded upon here, beginning with definitions from Wikipedia:

“**District heating** [...] is a system for distributing heat generated in a centralized location through a system of insulated pipes for residential and commercial heating requirements such as space heating and water heating” (Wikipedia, 2023).

“**District cooling** is the cooling equivalent of district heating. Working on broadly similar principles to district heating, district cooling delivers chilled water to buildings like offices and factories needing cooling” (Wikipedia, 2023a).

District energy (DE) refers to DH and DC in combination (DHC), or either one on its own. A DE system (DES) that provides DHC in an integrated manner can have significant efficiency benefits relative to independent DH and DC systems. These systems provide: reliable end-to-end thermal energy services including acquisition and/or recycling of heat (and sometimes cold) from diverse sources; thermal energy storage (TES)²⁰ with a wide range of capacities and with charge and discharge times from hours to years; transmission and distribution piping systems; at-building energy transfer stations (ETS); and central management and control systems.

District energy systems can be small, serving just a few buildings, to very large, spanning and connecting major metropolitan regions. Modern, low temperature systems can economically provide district energy services to most non-rural buildings, large and small.

Annex B provides an extensive introduction to district energy and detailed analysis of the hypothetical heating of "Anywhere, Ontario" with net-zero district energy and its comparison with electrified heating.

Much like electric power systems, TNs can be very large, hierarchical, and complex, integrating many different heat sources, heat transmission lines, local distribution networks, TES of various types and scale, building connections, and even certain equipment within customer buildings (Moser and Puschnigg, 2021).

District heating originated in the ancient Roman empire and then 14th century France (see Section 9). Large, steam-based systems were first implemented in North America in the 19th century (Bertelsen, 2023). Later, high temperature systems used pressurized hot water. The technology evolved and matured, leading to the 4th and 5th generation TNs commonly deployed today. Modern systems achieve lower unit costs and much greater efficiency by operating at lower temperatures, typically 70 C or lower for direct heating applications and even at ambient ground temperature (with uninsulated plastic pipes) for low density communities. Ambient temperature systems require connected buildings to have water-source heat pumps that function much like

²⁰ TES used for district energy systems should not be confused with high temperature TES systems used, like batteries, to store electric power and return electric power.

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Figure 6.1. Evolution of district heating. Figure from (Wirtz et al., 2023).

ground-source heat pumps, but that can achieve higher efficiency ($\text{COP} \approx 4$) through centralized management (Lund et al., 2021). The evolution is shown in Figure 6.1.

Prior to the 3rd generation, TNs produced heat above 100°C through combustion of fossil fuels, municipal waste or biomass. As later generations moved to lower temperatures, they became increasingly able to capture, from a wide variety of sources, heat that would otherwise be lost to the environment. This improves overall energy efficiency and reduces GHG emissions. Large-scale thermal energy storage was introduced to allow captured heat that exceeds the immediate demand to be stored, instead of discarded, enabling its eventual use when the supply is less than the demand. A more comprehensive account of modern TNs and their integration with other parts of the energy system is presented in Friedrich et al. (2024).

The UNEP report *District Energy in Cities: Unlocking the Potential of Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy* identifies modern district energy as the most effective approach for many cities to transition to sustainable heating and cooling, by improving energy efficiency and enabling higher shares of renewables” (UNEP, 2015). The following quotes are from this comprehensive report:

“DISTRICT HEATING is undergoing a resurgence as cities identify its ability to efficiently transform the municipal heating supply to be more cost-effective, cleaner and lower carbon, as well as more local, renewable and resilient. District heating can enable higher penetrations of variable renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar, in the electricity system, using large-scale heat pumps, combined heat and power (CHP), boilers and thermal storage. Such balancing is a cornerstone of energy policies in Denmark and Germany, and several provinces

in China are examining the synergy between district heating and high levels of wind generation.”

“DISTRICT COOLING has huge potential to reduce soaring electricity demand from air conditioning and chillers, which can present problems at times of peak load and require expensive transmission system upgrades, electricity capacity additions and decentralized backup generators to deal with prolonged blackouts.”

“USING ENERGY SOURCES such as fossil fuels or nuclear-powered electricity to provide space heating, hot water or cooling is inefficient and a waste of resources. District energy is the only way to utilize low-exergy, low-grade waste heat or free cooling sources for these end-uses in buildings.”

“Local electricity utilities can benefit from the distributed cogeneration that district energy often provides. In Bergen, electricity companies, facing capacity concerns and network strains, supported the development of district heating because it reduced reinforcement costs and provided additional revenues. The local district heating industry association was created mostly by electricity suppliers. London, Seattle and Tokyo also are investigating the incorporation of electricity suppliers into district energy networks, utilizing waste heat from substations and transit lines.”

Denmark is a world leader in district energy (Johansen and Werner, 2022). The report (Mathiesen et al., 2019) from Aalborg Universitet notes the importance of integrating district energy with other parts of the energy system:

“District heating systems should become integrated with other parts of the energy system. This happens through flexible production at Combined Heat and Power (CHP) plants complementing fluctuating renewable electricity production; use of waste heat from industry and services; and use of electricity in large-scale heat pumps and electric boilers during hours of high production of fluctuating renewable energy.”

6.2. TN Energy Sources

Almost all energy used by society eventually ends up as heat. Combustion of fuels produces heat at high temperature. When used for industrial processes or electricity generation, the end result is that a substantial fraction of that energy remains as heat at lower temperatures and is commonly rejected to the environment – e.g., into the air through a chimney stack or cooling tower, or into a nearby lake or river. This residual thermal energy, which is at too low a temperature to be of further use for the facility where it was produced, will be referred to here as waste or excess heat.

Residential and commercial energy uses, such as for hot water, result in substantial waste heat at lower power from very many sources; but much of this heat is nonetheless recoverable. Many TNs generate most of their heat by burning renewable fuels, often in CHP plants, and increasingly heat is being captured from the environment – sun, air, water and ground (Yuan et al., 2024). A thermal energy utility has many more options and can handle financing better than building owners and the probability of success in decarbonization is much more likely.

Most forms of renewable energy are either variable or interruptible (e.g., solar or wind) or have high capital costs (e.g., biomass or energy from waste facilities) but with considerable economies of scale. Consequently, they are not well suited to implementation for individual buildings. All can become more economic if their output can be captured whenever it is available and used when needed.

Thermal networks address these barriers and create opportunities for optimization by creating large scale heat loads, allowing economies of scale, and, importantly, incorporating short term or seasonal thermal energy storage to manage the temporal and peak power mismatches between supply and demand.

While customers' heat demand may be served with fossil fuel during a TN's development stages, as the customer base grows other sources of renewable energy can be incorporated and fossil fuel phased out. This reinforces the importance of an energy plan. If potential customers see a commitment to decarbonized sources and the logic is plausible, they will be more likely to accept short term service from non-renewable sources.

As the system evolves, converting to lower carbon sources can be a priority. A thermal network can change sources to manage the level of utilization of each and achieve the most acceptable solutions for customers and for the community. During recent years, the Oujé-Bougoumou Cree Nation's biomass district heating system was able to meet 95% of its heating demand from biomass and 5% from oil for peaking and back-up. They are examining seasonal thermal energy storage to enable a more consistent high utilization of biomass and possible elimination of oil use other than for back-up in the event of biomass system failure or maintenance.

Power generation and Industry

Gas-fired power stations in Ontario average about 43% efficiency (see Section 4.1), meaning 57% waste heat; CANDU nuclear stations are about 30% efficient, thus 70% waste heat. This means that Ontario's thermal power stations reject to the environment much more thermal energy, that could be potentially used by TNs to heat buildings, than the electrical energy they provide to the grid. Although not all that heat could be recovered and made useful, it should be possible to economically increase the overall efficiency of nuclear plants to as high as 80% (Oliker, 2022).

The distance that heat can be economically delivered increases with power level since pipe capacity grows as the square of diameter while cost grows more slowly; approximately as a linear function of pipe diameter. Transmission up to 100 km is viable for power of 100 MW_{th} or more, with losses of 2% to 3% (ibid; Kavvadias and Quoilin, 2018). About 10 percent of the global nuclear fleet, including CANDU reactors, have collectively provided heat for local district energy systems for over 500 reactor-years (IAEA, 2019).

The most economical way to exploit heat from thermal power plants, for use by TNs, is to construct or retrofit them to operate as combined heat and power (CHP) plants (Lowe, 2011; Wang et al., 2019; Jimenez-Navarro et al., 2020; Rämä, Leurent and Devezeaux de Lavergne, 2020). For a new nuclear power plant, incorporating the design changes needed to make the plant

"CHP ready", meaning that subsequent conversion to CHP would be quite feasible, would require an investment of about 0.2% of the total plant cost (Friggens et al., 2016).

In the case of major plant refurbishment, such as Pickering NGS B, it is reasonable to expect a comparable cost. Based on natural gas consumption data and a quick calculation, the recoverable waste heat from the four Pickering NGS B units, if converted to CHP as part of their planned retrofits, would be sufficient to heat most buildings in Toronto.

Canada's commitment to triple nuclear power by 2050 (NRCAN, 2023c) should create many opportunities for new nuclear plants – both conventional large nuclear and new small reactors (SMR, MMR) – to be configured for CHP and serve as major heat sources for TNs. It is fully recognized that there are many issues that must be tackled in a strategic manner for this to be accomplished (Friedrich et al., 2024); but the more than doubling of efficiency, huge reduction of natural gas consumption for heating and the associated GHG emissions, and potential doubling of nuclear plant revenue certainly warrant a requirement for careful consideration of nuclear CHP.

It must be recognized that decisions are being made now on the size, location and technology for new generation. Accordingly it is important to get the attention of policy and planning authorities to incorporate CHP-ready designs immediately. By delaying a decision, the opportunity to incorporate CHP and provide the potential for substantial decarbonization of building heating may be lost.

The efficiency of large industrial facilities varies widely depending on the industry and the processes involved. Again depending on individual facilities, the temperatures of available waste heat can span the full range of temperatures of use for TNs. A detailed inventory is necessary to assess what industrial facilities might be worth considering as heat sources for TNs in any given Ontario community. It will also be necessary to assess the potential to use heat that may be available; it may not be economically viable to make use of it. Several levels of such an assessment are shown in Figure 6.2. While a wide range of methods are available for recovering waste heat, their primary benefit may be to improve the efficiency of the involved industrial processes (Jouhara et al., 2018).

Substantial data has been compiled on the availability of excess industrial heat in Europe, and its potential utility for existing and future district energy systems (Papapetrou et al., 2018; Fleiter et al., 2020; Luberti et al., 2022; Davies et al., 2023; Turek et al., 2024). See Figure 6.3 for an example.

In discussions with some industries, it is clear that if there was a potential for selling useful heat to a local thermal network, they could modify their plant optimization to benefit both the industry and the thermal network. In

Figure 6.2. Waste heat potential (Turek et al., 2024).

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Figure 6.3. Industrial heat sources and areas with district energy. Screen grab from sEnergies D5.1 Dataset Web-app (Fleiter et al., 2020).

fact, there are instances, such as the paper mill in Tampere, Finland, where the industry has no heating plant of its own but receives process heat from the community utility that is generated from biomass such as wood chips and peat.

The use of industrial waste heat for TNs faces significant issues and challenges, largely due to the uniqueness of each facility and arrangement and to different planning horizons of TN providers versus facilities with waste heat (Lygnerud, Wheatcroft and Wynn, 2019). For example, a TN provider considering making use of heat from a steel mill may need assurance of long-term availability that the steel company cannot provide.

Figure 6.4 shows the approximate industrial energy use in Ontario by major sub-sector. Electrification of industry may greatly reduce the total energy consumed in some of these sub-sectors (although total primary energy use may not decrease much when the efficiency of electricity generation is taken into account). Potentially recoverable heat would, of course, be considerably less than energy consumed. A wide variety of industry efforts to improve the efficiency of energy use, such as discussed in (Jouhara et al., 2018), should be expected to reduce both the quantity and temperature of potentially recoverable waste heat. There is also substantial risk that major facilities will significantly decrease or cease operations, making significant investments in heat harvesting for TNs a risky proposition. A method to determine the value of industrial waste heat, and thus the motivation of industry to make it available, is developed in (Moser, Puschnigg and Rodin, 2020).

Figure 6.4. Ontario Industrial sub-sector energy use by source in 2019. Data from (NRCan, 2023).

Community waste heat

Waste heat from sources commonly found in communities may be more widely available while industrial waste heat will be limited to industrialized communities. Sources of community waste heat include:

- residential, commercial, and industrial cooling systems (Exergi, 2025)
- untreated wastewater and effluent from wastewater treatment plants (Nagpal et al., 2020; Wilson and Worrall, 2021; C2E2, 2025)
- electric power transformers (Davies et al., 2023).

Very rough numbers ($\pm 40\%$) can be estimated for the amount of thermal energy available. The portion of the available heat that is economically recoverable will vary widely, depending on individual circumstances. When recovered at temperatures below the TN supply temperature – typically 70 C for 4G DH – heat recovery heat pumps (HRHP) will generally be needed to boost the temperature. The capital and electricity costs for HRHPs can be major factors when assessing the

economics of waste heat recovery. However, where 5G DHC is installed, the recovery of waste heat can be greater; and HRHPs will only be installed where analysis indicates a benefit over complete reliance on at-building water-source heat pumps.

Opportunities for heat from cooling systems include air conditioning in buildings of all sizes, data centres, cold storage, supermarkets, and ice rinks. Based on comparison of cooling degree days to heating degree days, waste heat from cooling will be about 10% of the energy used for heating, or 10 TWh/a; about 5 TWh/a of this would be from large buildings at about 35 C. It may be possible to design the cooling equipment to reject heat at a higher, more useful temperature for the thermal network. This would reduce the cooling COP, but would be more than offset by the revenue from the rejected heat.

The thermal energy from hot water entering Ontario sewers will be perhaps 20 TWh/a. Once losses from sewer pipes to the ground have reached a steady state, almost all that heat will find its way to wastewater treatment plants. The temperature will most often be less than 20 C, so HRHPs will be required. The waste water temperature will always be much higher than the ambient air temperature, so COPs to provide heat will be higher than available to ASHPs.

About 0.5% of power passing through large power transformers at distribution substations and major industrial customers is lost as heat, a portion of which should be recoverable at up to 50 C in new or modified equipment (Lagoeiro et al., 2023). In Ontario this is 5 to 10 TWh/a of potentially recoverable waste heat, located near communities where the heat could be used by TNs. Considering the long design lifetimes of power transformers, making the changes to actually recover the waste heat would need to be a planned effort over a period of decades. The payoff would be several percent of the heat needed recovered from the power distribution substations serving communities.

Renewable fuels combustion

Burning renewable (non-fossil) fuels for electricity and heat production with CHP plants is quite common in Europe. Commonly used fuels include municipal solid waste (possibly including fossil-fuel plastics), sewage sludge, biomass, bio-oil and biogas (Wittenburg et al., 2023). Modern CHP plants have stringent controls on non-GHG emissions, so they are accepted within cities. Such plants can provide a transition between natural gas CHP and future fully-renewable, non-combustion heat sources. They may meet all / most of the heat demand for new TNs, allowing waste heat recovery and renewable heat sources to be brought online progressively, over a period of years, and being maintained as standby in the long term for reliable backup and peak heat supply.

In 2021, Canada produced about 5 million tons of wood pellets, most of which were exported (NRCan, 2025; USDA, 2023). Biomass accounts for about 5% of Canada's primary energy use, and is trending down (IEA, 2025). In Canada, biomass is mostly burned for heat at buildings and to produce electricity in central plants, with most facilities smaller than 5 MW. Biomass CHP is recognized as a good option for northern communities. Ontario published a Forest Biomass Action Plan in 2022 that includes CHP, but without indicating the level of ambition (Ontario, 2022).

Because of the additional cost and complexity and more stringent operator requirements for biomass CHP plants, heat only boilers may be the best starting point for smaller new energy systems. As the system grows, economies of scale will justify the replacement or conversion to CHP.

Environmental heat

The sun is the Earth's primary energy source. In Ontario, the annual average solar energy flux, at a radiation temperature of 5250 C, is about 1.5 MWh/m². Solar thermal collectors, tilted to optimize collection efficiency, can capture 500 kWh_{th}/m² or more in the course of a year (Tschopp et al., 2020). Given the very high temperature of sunlight, captured solar energy can be used to supply heat at up to 110 C, avoiding the need for HRHPs to boost the temperature. (Concentrated solar collectors can achieve much higher temperatures for industrial applications.) Seasonal thermal energy storage (STES), discussed in Section 6.4, can economically store heat collected in warm weather for use when it's needed.

The incorporation of STES needs to be fully appreciated as it will transform the business case or viability of solar thermal collection. In Canada, the solar thermal market has almost disappeared; but with STES the otherwise wasted summer production of heat can be stored and used during the winter. The example of Drake Landing, Okotoks, Alberta, North America's first solar powered solar community, was a technical demonstration, and has inspired similar BTES (borehole thermal energy storage) projects around the world. It has been decommissioned, but the system demonstrated that solar thermal energy could be supplied for 97% of the community heating needs. Larger scale projects will be much more cost effective with lower annual heat losses.

IRENA (2021) provides a good overview of solar thermal technologies, with examples of large-scale projects. It gives this very brief introduction: "Solar thermal technologies are highly modular and can be installed on the rooftops of individual buildings for residential use, or in hospitals or hotels. They can also be found in large, MW-scale ground-mounted systems in industry, agriculture and district heating networks."

Solar thermal collectors with a collective surface area of about 200 km² could capture 100 TWh_{th} of heat per year, which is what TNs would need to fully replace natural gas space heating in Ontario. About one third more would be needed for domestic hot water. Power system expansion to provide a comparable amount of energy would require much more land (IESO, 2022a), while solar thermal collectors can often be installed without significantly interfering with existing land uses. An average house needing 20 MWh_{th}/a could be heated by 40 m² of solar thermal collectors, provided the heat could be stored in shared STES.

Combination PV and thermal (PVT) solar collectors can collect heat and produce electricity at the same time, achieving a combined efficiency as high as 80% of the incident solar energy (IEA SHC, 2022). Seasonal storage of the electricity is not feasible, but any that is not locally consumed or stored in short-term batteries can be supplied to the grid or, if economical, used to provide stored hot water.

Heat can be harvested from large water bodies (lakes and large rivers) with the use of industrial water-to-water heat pumps, just as is done with wastewater, but STES will be needed to benefit from warmer water in the summer. As is done with deep lake water cooling for Toronto, cold water (at 4 C) can be drawn from below the thermocline of deep lakes and used for district cooling (Spurr et al., 2014).

Large, centralized air-source heat pumps can economically harvest heat from outdoor air during warm weather.²¹ Large airflows will be required, but the available thermal energy will be bounded only by economics. Raising the temperature above the 70 C needed for 4G DE may be most efficiently done by using water-to-water HRHPs as a second stage. Operation of the heat pumps can be limited to times when surplus renewable electricity is available and the air temperature is above some threshold.

Geothermal heat can be economically harvested for use by TNs where the geological conditions are favourable (Romanov and Leiss, 2022; Tu et al., 2024). This is mostly near crustal boundaries and volcanic areas. Based on geological analysis, it is unlikely that large-scale recovery of geothermal heat would be economically viable in Ontario or elsewhere in Canada east of the Rockies (Limberger et al., 2018).

The abandoned coal mine in Springhill, Nova Scotia is in an area where the mine water is at a constant 24 C. The mine, one of the deepest in North America, is as deep as 1,325 feet (400 metres). The mine water is circulated to local manufacturing and other buildings where it is upgraded with heat pumps.²² There may be similar opportunities across Canada. The option of central heat pumps with back-up or peak heating capacity may be a preferred solution to that used in Springhill.

6.3. Value of Heat

Consultations during this study revealed that many potential sources of low or no carbon energy were largely unaware of the value of rejected or wasted thermal energy. Such sources could be given or sold to a thermal utility for both environmental and economic benefit. Industry may require cooling water but be constrained in the temperature that they are allowed to discharge to the environment. Thermal electric generating stations, including nuclear, reject cooling water at the lowest possible temperature to maximize electricity output. And then there may be lower temperature sources such as sewer water or flooded mines, that could, with large scale heat pumps, upgrade heat to useful temperatures at attractive COPs.

Because sources did not recognize the potential or because thermal networks were not available, the value of selling, instead of rejecting, heat was not recognized. Heat from many industrial processes (eg. blast furnace cooling water in a steel mill or cooling systems in a refinery or upgrader) could be preserved and sold. The availability of a heat market may actually save

²¹ An example large ASHP installation is a condo project in Toronto. But with no linkage to a TN, there is no TES to store summer heat for use in winter and inadequate capacity to meet the heat demand in very cold weather. See <https://www.energy-manager.ca/toronto-condo-heat-pump-retrofit-a-blueprint-for-broader-decarbonization-at-scale/>.

²² <https://news.novascotia.ca/en/2022/12/12/geothermal-potential-heating-cumberland-county>

them money or lessen environmental concerns as rejection to the environment is reduced or eliminated as is the ancillary equipment.

CHP generating stations can extract heat at a higher temperature, lose some electricity, but make the previously wasted heat useful. The ratio of electricity lost to heat extracted at a useful temperature could be considered an equivalent COP. For instance heat rejected at about 95 C may lose 1 unit of electricity for about 8 units of heat made useful – or an equivalent COP of 8. This means that, if the electricity output is priced at \$100/MWh, the heat could be sold at \$12.50/MWh and the generator would break even. If, after the TN is established, the price of heat was increased above the “break even” price, to reflect mutual benefit, the generator could make more money than selling electricity alone. Reportedly (personal conversation with Niels Vilstrup), Danish CHP generators now see heat as their more valuable product.

As thermal networks are developed, they can secure the least cost, most decarbonized, more sustainable heat sources by public RFPs (Request for Proposals) for additional heat supplies. In effect the thermal networks are a means of securing sources that best align with customer or community priorities.

6.4. Thermal Energy Storage

Thermal energy storage (TES), including large-scale seasonal TES (STES), can be of tremendous value to improve the reliability and efficiency of thermal networks and to optimally integrate diverse heat sources (Guelpa and Verda, 2019; Lyden et al., 2022; Mitali, Dhinakaran and Mohamad, 2022; Bott, Dressel and Bayer, 2019; Mahon et al., 2022; Mier González, 2023; Fry et al., 2024). In particular, TES can provide an effective buffer to manage short- and long-term temporal mismatches of heat supply and demand. Heat from year-round sources, such as CHP plants, and from intermittent or seasonally variable sources, such as solar thermal, can be accumulated in TES year round and drawn down as needed to accommodate diurnal, weekly and seasonal demand variations.

Heat from zero-emissions sources that is not immediately needed can be stored in TES, instead of being wasted. When demand exceeds the zero-emissions supply, stored heat can be recovered from TES instead of using emitting or more expensive sources to generate new heat. This helps reduce TN capital and operating costs and total emissions. Having a substantial reserve of stored heat, and capacity to store more, also improves TN reliability and operational flexibility.

For similar capacity, the cost of TES is on the order of one percent of the cost of battery electric storage (BES).²³ TES systems with storage durations from hours to years, including in combination, offer economic and operational benefits. By contrast, economical BES storage durations currently range from 4 to 12 hours.

The coupling of heat production (and its storage in TES) to the electric power system – e.g., through CHP, HRHPs and electric boilers – enables more efficient operation of the power system, including improved utilization of wind, solar and other intermittent renewable electricity generation. The opportunity for improved energy efficiency from coupling CHP power stations

²³ See District Energy Digest #10 (<https://bi-ib.ca/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/District-Energy-Digest-No.-10.pdf>).

and TNs, with the aid of TES, is far greater than any efficiency gain that might be achieved by reducing heat losses from buildings, and the cost would be far less.²⁴ The EU requires, by law, that CHP be considered for all thermal power stations (EU, 2023).

Nuclear CHP plants can be valuable dispatchable resources for the power system; they can rapidly adjust the electrical output (within design limits), while maintaining full reactor power and steam output (and therefore valuable energy production) by varying the amount of heat sent to the TN; the TN operator can then manage the variable heat supply with the help of TES. This means that electrical derating of a nuclear CHP unit is only necessary when system demand can be satisfied from the rest of the generation fleet, e.g. when wind production is high and/or demand is low, instead of curtailing and thereby underutilizing expensive generating assets. Coupling nuclear CHP to TNs will thereby facilitate the elimination of gas-fired generation on the power system and the associated emissions. By increasing the efficiency with which reactor heat is used from 30% to as much as 80%, the societal value derived from a nuclear power plant can roughly double. Relatively low cost TES will enable most of that added value.

TES Technology

Thermal energy is most commonly stored as sensible heat in large volumes of water or the ground (soil, rock). Existing large TES systems have storage volumes exceeding the heat capacity equivalent of a million cubic metres of water. There is no reason why they could not be much larger; increasing size increases efficiency, since losses grow as the surface area while capacity is proportional to volume. TES systems not based on sensible heat (e.g., phase change materials) have also been developed, but the cost of materials involved makes them only suitable for small-scale niche applications with frequent, short charge/discharge cycles. Below, we consider only sensible heat TES.

A representative temperature difference, ΔT , between supply and return for a TES is $\Delta T = 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. (The actual ΔT will be a design decision.) For perspective on scale: TES facilities totalling 4 km^3 of water (or 8 km^3 of ground), with $\Delta T = 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, would store more thermal energy than the 100 TWh obtained by burning natural gas to heat buildings across Ontario for the entire heating season. The scale of TES actually needed would be much less because most heat collected during cold weather can be used immediately, instead of being stored, and much of the storage can be charged and discharged more than once per year. Selection of location, type, scale, and other details of individual TES systems will be part of an overall TN strategic design and optimization process.

TES can also be used for cold storage, which supports efficient district cooling and could greatly diminish peak electricity demand in hot weather. Ice on coil cooling can provide very cost

²⁴ Based on Two Pathways calculations, converting the four Pickering NGS B units to CHP (as part of planned refurbishment) could save more thermal energy than is used by all Toronto buildings. Toronto's estimated retrofit cost to reduce energy demand for existing buildings by 50% is about \$300 billion (Toronto, 2021).

effective and compact thermal energy storage as can chilled water (GDECA, 2023).²⁵ Toronto's Deep Lake Water Cooling uses Lake Ontario as natural TES (Spurr et al., 2014).

The following Figure 56 from (Mangold and Deschaintre, 2015) shows concepts for underground TES, some or all of which might be technically and economically desirable in Ontario. (TTES and BTES are already used in Ontario.)

Figure 56: Overview of available underground thermal energy storage concepts (Sources: Solites)

Underground TES can be very large; e.g., 1 million m³ water equivalent under a school playing field. Not shown above, but of increasing interest, is cavern (or cavity) TES (CTES), which uses large underground caverns – old mines and oil storage facilities, or caverns mined specifically for CTES (Vantaan, 2025).²⁶

Choosing Appropriate TES

Choices regarding TES are influenced by many factors, including: local geography and geology; space requirements and availability; environmental impacts; implementation time; anticipated lifetime; technology maturity; safety; required charge and discharge rates (MW), storage capacity (GWh), and operating temperatures; expected losses; and costs, benefits, and risks. For a large,

²⁵ See, e.g., <https://baltimoreaircoil.com/products/ice-thermal-storage>

²⁶ The latter's capacity is 94 GWh, as compared with the largest battery electric storage system in the world, the Moss Landing Energy Storage Facility in California, that had a total capacity of 3 GWh. That's the one that was recently destroyed by catching fire. Needless to say that's not a risk with water or rock based TES.

Figure 6.5. Solid lines: six years of space heating load duration (LD) curves for Toronto. Dashed lines: constant thermal supply power that, when combined with thermal energy storage, would be able to meet the variable demand for heat. Storage is assumed to be 60% efficient.

complex TN, it is likely that there would be more than one TES technology, and possibly many separate TES facilities. For example, even a fairly simple system is likely to include BTES for seasonal storage and TTES to manage short-term supply and demand fluctuations.

To accommodate a large heat source, such as nuclear CHP, where heat must be transmitted for considerable distance, it will likely be appropriate to have storage facilities near both the source and demand centres. That will allow utilization of the heat transmission line to be kept consistently high throughout the year, even as the heat supply and demand fluctuate. The economics of a transmission line are affected by ΔT and percent utilization. By installing STES capacity at the demand end, it is possible to maintain a constant flow all year round and thereby reduce the needed transmission line capacity. Some TES at the supply (CHP) end of the system will accommodate fluctuations of thermal power supplied by the CHP facility.

The benefit of TES is illustrated in Figure 6.5. Shown are load duration (LD) curves for six years of modeled space heating thermal power demand in Toronto. (The hourly MW values for each year are sorted from highest to lowest demand.) The corresponding dashed lines show the level of constant heat supply that would be needed to meet the annual demand, if TES is used to

manage the difference between (constant) supply and (variable) demand in each hour. To calculate the level of constant heat supply it was assumed that 40% of the heat sent to storage is lost to the environment; the actual losses could be significantly less. On very cold days, the combination of the constant source plus storage could supply all the heat needed to keep buildings warm. At least some of the storage would need to be water-based (tank, pit, cavern) in order to have the high discharge rates (as high as 12,000 MW) needed on cold days. Most of the storage capacity, used for seasonal storage, would likely be BTES.

6.5. Heat Transmission Lines and Corridors

Often, there are desirable sources of zero- or low-emissions thermal energy available but they may not be close to TNs that could use the heat. If the thermal power involved is sufficient, it may be worthwhile to build a heat transmission line (insulated pipeline, usually including cooled water return) to transfer the heat from source(s) to TNs that can use it. The cost of installed piping grows approximately linearly with pipe diameter, but the capacity (and revenue) of a heat transmission line grows as the square of the pipe diameter. Accordingly, in most cases, the cost per unit of delivered energy is lower for greater capacity and pipe diameter. The result is that some sources cannot be economically delivered over long distances to small heat loads but might be very economical for larger loads and transmission line capacity.

The cost of delivering energy in a transmission line is also a function of utilization. If the transmission line is used at only half its maximum potential – i.e., operating, on average, at half of peak capacity – the delivery charge required to cover the capital cost will be double what it could be with full utilization. Locating large-scale TES at each end of the transmission line, to buffer supply and demand variations, will allow the annual energy to be delivered at a lower constant flow, through a lower-capacity line and at a lower cost.

In analogy with major electrical transmission corridors that connect generation to distribution networks, major heat transmission corridors may be appropriate to connect multiple sources, TES facilities, and TNs over distances up to, and possibly exceeding, 100 km.

6.6. Thermal Network Deployment Scope

The TN Pathway would, by 2050, have TNs providing heat for all buildings where that is viable, and GSHPs used almost everywhere else. As noted above, TNs require sufficient density of heat demand to be viable and cost effective. (Methods used to infer heat demand from the limited data available are presented in Section 4; comparative costs of electrification and TNs for Ontario, a typical community, and a typical household are considered in Section 8.) Subject to detailed heating planning for individual communities, a tentative assessment is that TNs will be viable and cost effective in areas with population density starting within the range 10 to 25 people per hectare and going higher. This is consistent with the findings of (Popovski, Ragwitz and Brugger, 2023). At the low end of this range, 5G DE may be most appropriate, while 4G DE will be preferred

Figure 6.6. Percent of people living at a population density less than indicated by the abscissa, for each of the provinces and territories, and for all of Canada. Data is from the 2021 Census. The grey band indicates a rough dividing line between areas suitable for TNs and areas suitable for GSHPs.

at higher densities. Areas with low population density but significant heat demand for non-residential buildings – commercial, institutional, or industrial – may also be suitable for 4G DE.

Figure 6.6 shows the distribution of population densities for all provinces and territories, and for Canada as a whole. Ontario has the most concentrated population, with roughly 70% living in areas suitable for TNs. That includes almost all populated parts of Toronto and other major cities; but also denser areas in most smaller cities and towns.

In areas where thermal networks are determined to not be viable there will most often be sufficient space for the ground loops of GSHPs to be installed. GSHPs are strongly preferred over ASHPs because they retain high efficiency (COP) even on very cold days and will impose correspondingly smaller peak demand on the electric power system. Existing distribution systems will often be adequate for GSHPs, but not ASHPs. This will be true for GSHPs especially if solar thermal collectors are installed to heat DHW and maintain annual temperature balance in ground loops. The annualized incremental cost of GSHPs over ASHPs should be less than the extra cost of

Figure 6.7. Population density in the GTHA. Data from the 2021 Census. The polygon geometry provided for some census blocks extends over water, which causes the indicated density to be lower than if only the land area had been included. Unfilled areas have zero reported population.

providing reliable peak power (generation, transmission, distribution, and in-building equipment) for ASHPs with electric resistance supplementary heat.

Figure 6.7 shows the population density across the Greater Toronto and Hamilton Area (GTHA); the grey boundary between shades of blue and red corresponds to 24 people/ha. (Some census dissemination blocks (DB) shown in Figure 6.7 have polygon geometries (provided by StatCan) that extend over adjacent water. This results in population density values for those DBs being too low in both Figures 6.6 and 6.7.) It is somewhat startling that almost all built up areas have sufficiently dense heat demand to make TNs viable; lower-density (blue hued) DBs within built up areas generally correspond to highways, river valleys, ravines, parks, golf courses and commercial / industrial areas. Adding in commercial, institutional and industrial heat demand would fill some of the gaps and extend the areas where TNs are viable.

Whether TNs serve cooling in addition to heating in a given area will be a local design decision, based on both technical and non-technical considerations. Since 5G TNs require heat pumps in each connected building, they will almost always support cooling. Cooling with 4G TNs would require 3- or 4-pipe distribution systems, rather than the 2-pipe supply and return for heating only. A benefit of supporting cooling is that any connected building can be a prosumer, taking heat from the TN when needed and supplying heat to the TN when the building has excess heat (e.g., from cooling, solar collectors, or waste heat from commercial or industrial activities).

TN service providers will be responsible for overall system design, implementation, operation, and customer connections (piping for building connections and ETS) and ongoing service. Changes to ensure good heat distribution within buildings will range from simple replacement of furnaces with hydronic air handling units, that might be covered by the TN provider, to significant upgrades of hydronic heating systems so they can operate at lower temperatures. Expenses for the latter would likely be borne (mostly) by building owners, but similar upgrades would be required for heating electrification with heat pumps so they should not be perceived as an extra cost associated with TNs.

6.7. Strategic Implementation

Given the thermal power demand of the Ontario buildings currently heated by natural gas (estimated in Section 4), allowing 25% more energy to heat DHW, and using the estimate from Annex B for DE cost per kW of demand, gives a total (overnight) TN implementation cost in excess of \$300 billion by 2050. (We make the simplifying assumption that heat demand for new buildings will compensate for existing buildings that are removed; an increase in the total number of buildings will be offset by better thermal efficiency of new buildings.) This crude estimate could well be wrong by over \$100 billion; nonetheless, the great magnitude implies that implementing TNs will be an enormous undertaking.²⁷

A deliberate, strategic approach to large-scale TN implementation in Ontario could improve decisions, establish the needed capabilities and capacity, and reduce costs and risks. Based on cost reductions achieved with wind power, solar PV, batteries, and other energy technologies, it is not unreasonable to expect societal savings (or avoided additional expenses) as high as \$100 billion from such a strategic approach. Non-monetary benefits would be of comparable importance. The cost of TNs to replace natural gas heating across Canada could exceed \$800 billion (again, with great uncertainty) and the expected societal benefits of strategic optimization could be on the order of \$300 billion. Current geo-political realignment puts a premium on eliminating dependence on the US for supply of natural gas. (The US currently supplies 70% of gas consumed in Ontario. The other 30% is from western Canada but that could optimally service export markets, e.g. for fertilisers, thereby helping to combat world hunger.)

²⁷ For comparison, the cost of electrifying heating for buildings in Toronto (about 30% of all Ontario buildings heated by natural gas), including retrofits and installation of ASHPs but with no provision for expansion and decarbonization of the electric power system, was estimated at over \$300 billion in 2021 (Toronto, 2021). That has little chance of being achieved due to inadequate capability and capacity and excessive cost. Net-zero TNs to heat Toronto would cost about \$100 billion, with greatly reduced need or justification for building retrofits.

Europe and China are at least a decade ahead of Canada on deployment of TNs. Nordic countries – most notably Denmark – are leading the way, but Germany, Poland, Switzerland, the UK, and others are hard at work on modernizing and decarbonizing existing TNs and increasing the fraction of buildings served by existing and new TNs. A major driver of this in the EU is the Energy Efficiency Directive, which includes a requirement for municipalities to undertake heat planning (EU, 2023). (That is planning for the provision of heat for buildings, not dealing with extreme heat events, which are a separate concern. We use the term heating planning to avoid ambiguity – or, even better, thermal energy planning.)

Heating planning requires the formulation of strategy, supported by extensive data. It necessarily involves consideration of electric power, and coupling of the electricity and heat sectors (Jimenez- Navarro et al., 2020; Joint Research Centre et al., 2019). China carries sector coupling even further, with a proposal to: desalinate seawater using heat from a nuclear power plant; pipe the hot, desalinated water 100 km to distant cities where it will be used to heat buildings, with the cooled water then being used for the domestic water supply (Chen et al., 2021).

Canadians will be best served if, as is increasingly done in Europe and China, plans and infrastructure for heating and electricity are tightly integrated, not treated as though they are independent. Otherwise, two thirds of the heat produced from nuclear and other fuels at thermal power stations will continue to be wasted instead of being put to valuable use for heating.

For strategic planning in Canada to properly include sector coupling it must have strong participation at the provincial level, since electricity and natural gas are provincially regulated. Historically, the heat sector has not been regulated, but for logical consistency heat should be added to the purview of the provincial Energy Board. Because the same topics and issues will be of concern across the country, leadership and coordination at the federal level will be desirable.

The strategic approach contemplated here would recognize thermal networks as critical infrastructure, comparable in importance and scale to electric power infrastructure. (As seen above, as much energy is used for heating buildings as electrical energy for all purposes; nuclear CHP power plants could provide society with similar amounts of electrical and thermal energy. And while electricity is literally vital for modern civilization, so is heating in cold climates like Canada).

With the importance of TN infrastructure properly recognized, strategy and programs should be established to make Canada self-sufficient: capable of planning, delivering, and maintaining world-leading, reliable, net-zero TN infrastructure, including optimal integration with the expanding electricity infrastructure. This will include progressive building of capability and capacity (expertise, workforce, education, R&D, industry, supply chain) to address a wide range of pertinent topics, including: governance and regulation; business and financial models; heating planning; TN architecture, with sector coupling; technology; global optimization (multi-sector efficiency, reliability, resilience, cost, social equity); decarbonization; building conversion; economies of scale; and more (Sporleder, Rath and Ragwitz, 2022; Simpson, Long and Zhu, 2024; Lorenzen, 2022; Guo, Yusheng and Kriegel, 2024; Luo et al., 2024). Recognizing the global

opportunity, Canada could even aspire for a leadership position that challenges Denmark, with great potential for adding good jobs, export markets, and value to the Canadian economy.

The development and execution of good strategy requires vision, commitment, and investment. Substantial investments must be made in RD&D to develop a roadmap and provide a solid foundation for the larger investments that must follow. This could include establishing one or more centres of excellence, to address the whole range of topics listed above. Annual TN investments, nationally, should rapidly grow to a scale similar to or greater than investments in nuclear energy (to triple Canada's nuclear power by 2050).

An initial government infusion, sufficient to build core capability by pulling together international leaders and Canadian specialists with needed knowledge and experience and to also build organizational infrastructure, should likely be on the order of \$200 million over three years. Funding will need to increase in subsequent years as TN deployment picks up pace. Without such a government commitment, development of TNs is likely to remain limited to the low-hanging fruit of new developments that give quick a return on investment; decarbonization of existing buildings will fail to meet objectives, and Canada will fail to meet its international commitments for reduction of GHG emissions.

6.8. Transformation of Natural Gas Distribution Utilities

In the transformation from business as usual (BAU) to heating with thermal networks, there are potential winners and losers. But potential losers need not be so if they adapt. Gas distribution utilities buy, distribute and sell a commodity. For now, that is natural gas. In their current business, they have expertise in underground infrastructure, construction, customer service as well as financing and billing for the service provided.

If they were to embrace transformation to a non-fossil fuel dependent energy system, they could transform their business model while also becoming a major driver for decarbonization. Such transformation would also eliminate a barrier to change as preservation of the status quo may be seen as in the best interests of shareholders. Transformation to a thermal utility model may even provide expanded opportunities and a positive image for this business sector.

Their current major advantage is their customer base. They could explain to their customers that they were undertaking a major decarbonization effort and install local distribution piping and convert, or support the conversion of, customer facilities. If net-zero heat supply is not possible on day one, heat could be sourced from portable gas boilers, or similar, for a strictly-limited initial period, allowing time for non-emitting heat sources to be arranged.

Already, thanks to a Province of Quebec decision to limit natural gas heating expansion, Enbridge Gaz Québec is working to secure heat from local industry and serve new developments through TNs in the Gatineau area.²⁸

²⁸ <https://esemag.com/infrastructure/quebec-plans-end-of-natural-gas-heating-for-non-industrial-buildings/>,
<https://enbridgegaz.com/en/>

6.9. TN Pathway Summary

Thermal networks with net-zero GHG emissions would be feasible to implement for heating about 70% of Ontario's buildings, including almost all buildings that currently have natural gas service. This would achieve decarbonization by 2050 with greater certainty and at far less cost than the electrification pathway. TNs would also provide heat for DHW. Depending on local requirements and analysis of options, TNs can be designed to support cooling in addition to heating.

TNs providers, operating as utilities, would have both responsibility and capability to provide zero-emissions heating by 2050. This would eliminate reliance on individual actions by millions of building owners. Owners would not need to undertake costly and disruptive retrofits of their buildings; improving energy efficiency with TNs is far more practical, significant, and cost-effective than improving efficiency with retrofits.

More than sufficient heat for the TNs could be obtained from a wide variety of zero-emissions heat sources – CHP power stations, waste heat from industry and within communities, renewable fuels, and solar and other heat from the environment. (In some cases, industrial heat pumps would use off-peak or surplus power to boost the temperature of low-grade heat.) The actual heat sources chosen in each community will depend on detailed analysis, and could evolve over time. A pragmatic approach might start with heat sources that emit GHGs, but keep them only as long as is needed to convert to non-emitting sources.

The hourly demand for heat varies with the ambient temperature according to the seasons and weather, and generally does not match the hourly supply of heat from the economical sources. Affordable, large-scale thermal energy storage can greatly improve the overall efficiency of TNs, electric power infrastructure (coupled to TNs through CHP), and heat collection from other sources.

It is contemplated that TNs will be viable and deployed in most non-rural areas where the population density is within or above the range of 10 to 25 people per hectare – that would be about 70% of buildings in Ontario and nationally. For the 30% of buildings where TNs are not viable, heating would be electrified, with GSHPs preferred because their peak power demand is a third or less than ASHPs. Implementation of TNs at such a scale will require a strategic approach, led by provincial and federal governments. Significant public investment will be needed to establish suitable strategy and develop the needed capability and capacity to successfully deploy TNs, and decarbonize heating, in line with the strategy.

7. Hybrid/Transitional Solutions

Sections 5 and 6 have considered the electrification pathway and the TN pathway, each imagined as a sole solution (TNs where justified by heat demand density) for building decarbonization:

- Electrification with ASHPs can be done by a small fraction of individual building owners, but scaling up to almost all buildings is neither affordable nor feasible. Early adopters who pursue this pathway in Ontario benefit not only from government grants, but also from massive hidden subsidies by the millions of other electricity customers. Because gas-fired generation is used to meet most of the increased power demand, converting from NG heating to ASHPs will yield very little, if any, net GHG reductions before 2040. Building retrofits are very expensive; and experience in Europe shows that retrofits are unlikely to reduce the total heat demand for existing buildings by more than 10 to 20%. In very cold weather, the electric power demand due to large-scale conversion to ASHPs, even cold-climate models, would be far greater than has been planned for or would be feasible to reliably supply.
- TNs will be feasible and affordable to implement to supply zero-emissions heat to about 70% of buildings, with GSHPs, or renewable sources like biomass or solar thermal, being suitable for the other 30%. But TNs are major infrastructure that require large sums of patient capital and years to implement. Building owners cannot connect until TN service becomes locally available. Large-scale implementation of TNs will require a strategic commitment from provincial and federal governments to support municipalities, which are the natural proponents of TN, but cannot be reasonably expected to do it without support from senior levels of government. Support includes policy, expanded financial instruments, regulations and programs.

A more realistic pathway to decarbonized heating will see a planned evolution of approach over time. It will be a hybrid solution that combines no-regrets, building-specific actions in the short term, with progressive building of TN infrastructure and connection of most buildings as the long-term solution. But rather than a single hybrid solution, planned evolutions are likely to be different when conceived at different scales – province, region, city, neighbourhood – and in different communities. This is analogous to the planning of electric power infrastructure province-wide and by LDCs for the communities they serve.

The following measures for **heating decarbonization in low density areas** can be adopted as rapidly as industrial and financial capacities allow, and should be appropriate for the long term. They keep total societal costs down through long-term avoidance of severe peak demands on the electric power system, such as would result from use of ASHPs.

- Promote and support the installation of GSHPs for buildings that are obviously so isolated that connection to a shared heat network is not viable. Prefer shallow-buried horizontal loop ground heat exchangers over borehole heat exchangers. Also support the installation of solar thermal collectors to provide heat for DHW, and to ensure annual thermal energy balance where borehole heat exchangers are the required/chosen alternative.

- Where clusters of closely spaced buildings have too little heat demand to justify establishment of or connection to a TN utility, support installation of small-scale DE, with shared ground heat exchangers (multiple boreholes) for seasonal TES and shared solar thermal collectors and/or other renewable heat source(s) such as biomass. Drake Landing is a good example (Kosteniuk et al., 2024). The DE system could be 4G or 5G, with 5G only advised in areas where there is already adequate electricity supply for the required at-building heat pumps (e.g., where the 5G DE system would replace electric resistance heating).
- Revise electricity rates to charge all customers separately for peak power (kW) and energy (kWh). Although retail electricity price reform in Ontario has proven intractable due to the process involved, some measures should be taken to prevent those who install ASHPs from benefiting from a significant hidden subsidy from the millions of other customers.

In **areas where the density of heat demand is sufficiently high for TNs to be viable**, and land constraints make installing GSHPs challenging and more expensive, the transition to decarbonized heating will need to occur in a deliberately staged manner:

- New buildings, and buildings undergoing major mechanical refurbishment, should strive to lower the supply temperature required for heating. By enabling the building to be heated with sources of 65 C or less, the efficiency of energy supply systems increases and future TNs can be incorporated with minor modifications.
- Starting immediately, building owners whose conventional air conditioning systems have reached or are approaching end of life should be encouraged to replace them with ASHPs with similar cooling capacity and peak power demand. The ASHPs sized for cooling should meet the buildings' needs for heating as low as +4 C, below which existing natural gas heating would take over. Cold-climate ASHPs, with their additional cost, are not needed. Shutting the ASHPs off below +4 C will minimize efficiency losses from defrosting; and the COP should remain high. If gas heating equipment reaches end of life, then it should be replaced with new, high efficiency gas heating equipment. Operating ASHPs only when the COP is high and upgrading to higher efficiency gas heating equipment will achieve modest GHG reductions (on the order of 15%) while avoiding the need to increase the power system capacity.
- Planning for large-scale expansion of existing and development of new TNs should also start immediately, with an aggressive timeline for progressive implementation and connection of existing and new buildings over the next 25 years. Planning requirements are discussed below and in Section 10. As TN services become available in a community, connection of all buildings should be mandatory even if their existing heating systems are not near end-of-life – this includes the ASHPs and efficient gas heating equipment installed as per the bullet above. Connecting buildings to TNs and eliminating winter use of ASHPs will lessen the load on the electric power system, freeing up capacity for electrification of transportation, industry, etc. If the TN provides cooling service, then the ASHPs can be removed; otherwise they can be kept for cooling.

- As TNs become available in each community, and buildings are converted, natural gas service for space and water heating, and other household uses, should be discontinued. By 2050, TN utilities with zero-emissions heat sources should have become the dominant mode of heating, fully replacing natural gas heating. Any ongoing gas service would be to serve industrial applications, e.g., chemicals and emergency power supply, for which no viable alternative exists. To the extent feasible, natural gas should have been replaced by low-carbon gas (yet to be identified).
- Given the flexibility of natural gas, priorities should be given to uses like back-up or peaking (for electricity and thermal systems) that enable the expanded use of renewable and other decarbonized energy sources. Strategic heating plans should reduce and then eliminate at-building use of natural gas for space heating as rapidly as possible, consistent with realistic implementation schedules for TNs.
- Major zero-emissions heat sources, such as nuclear power stations operating in CHP mode, may not be immediately available when individual TNs are first implemented. Large-scale TES and heat transmission lines must be built to enable efficient use of such large heat sources; and regional connections must be established between initially-separate TNs and to the heat transmission lines and large TES. This is much like a regional electric power system, with high voltage lines and transformer stations connecting large power stations to local distribution networks.
- Introducing use of nuclear CHP and large TES to couple electrical and thermal networks will allow greater utilization of intermittent renewable power (wind, solar). The thermal power sent to TNs can be varied at the convenience of electricity system operators, making nuclear power plants dispatchable and reducing or eliminating the need for dispatchable gas-fired generation to meet peaks and curtailment of renewable power generation. Revenue from heat sales could equal or exceed foregone electricity sales. Improved utilization of renewable generation will have a downward influence on the cost of electricity.

The following subsections address: (7.1) requirements for planning heating decarbonization at all scales; (7.2) the development of needed capability and capacity, particularly for very large scale implementation of thermal networks; (7.3) the need for effective public engagement; and (7.4) some possible local mechanisms for small-scale, local transitions to thermal networks. The Section ends with a brief summary (7.5).

7.1. Planning Requirements

Planning for heating decarbonization is a complex, multi-faceted, and ongoing process. It involves consideration of:

- societal and environmental objectives, constraints and impacts
- technological and industrial capabilities and capacities and their future development
- resource requirements and availability
- integration and alignment with other, interdependent plans.

Mutually consistent plans must be developed for multiple time horizons and updated over time based on changes relating to the above bullets, actual outcomes, new information and analysis.

Good planning requires collaboration amongst:

- different levels of government
- potentially interdependent sectors and utilities
- stakeholder organizations including industry, labour, education, think tanks, and R&D organizations.

Very importantly, plans and their development – initial and ongoing – must include significant community engagement. Good plans risk failure if they are developed by "others" without effective public consultation and engagement.

Plans should indicate both desired, realistic outcomes and the path to achieve them. But plans do not determine outcomes – there is always uncertainty. Good planning includes development and use of empirically-validated models, based on prior knowledge and extensive data, that indicate possible future outcomes and well-informed assessments of the corresponding risks and uncertainties. Those models should also be updated over time, based on new knowledge, data, and actual outcomes, and used to guide changes to the plans.

Plans should be comprehensive, incorporating information and analysis spanning all factors that could materially influence outcomes. Plans must not rely on assumptions that are made for convenience, but without good evidence – such as assuming that ASHP technology will improve so the COP stays high in very cold weather, or that any required net-zero electric power will be available when needed without significant cost increase. Where assumptions must be made, analyses and modeling should explicitly consider and reveal the implications and likelihood of reality differing from what was assumed.

Heating Planning is also discussed, from a somewhat different perspective, in Section 10.

7.2. Capability and Capacity Development

Strong capability and capacity to plan, implement, operate, and decarbonize thermal networks, to manage their long-term evolution, and to integrate thermal energy with other sectors (e.g., CHP), has been developed in many countries. Denmark and other Nordic countries, Germany, Austria, and China are perhaps worth special notice. The capability covers all relevant areas of concern and stakeholder groups (such as listed in Section 7.1). Capability and capacity continue to grow, with strong government support and coordination, especially from the EU, as TNs are increasingly viewed as the preferred solution for decarbonization of building heating wherever viable. The claims in this paragraph are supported by the many references listed in the Bibliography, a small fraction of which are cited in this report.

Although Canada has many TNs and continues to expand their use, the scale is tiny by comparison to the countries mentioned above. More often than not, new TNs focus on the low-hanging fruit of new buildings; existing buildings are left burning fossil fuels. This is still a niche industry in Canada; the capability and capacity of involved companies and individuals are naturally much less than what exists in leading countries like Denmark (which has less than one half the population of Ontario). Specialized piping and other parts are almost all imported.

With potential national benefits of TNs on the order of \$500 billion by 2050, strategic investments should be made to develop and maintain commensurate Canadian capability and capacity, including manufacturing.²⁹ A major objective, and justification, should be to reduce the societal cost of heating decarbonization by much more than the amount invested. But Canada could also have the ambition of self-reliance and international leadership – enabling profitable international sales of both services and products.

Existing Canadian businesses that work on thermal networks lack the resources and vision to do what is suggested above. Federal government leadership will be needed, with a suggested starting level of \$25 million per year, growing to at least \$500 million per year (with provincial and corporate contributions) as rapidly as possible. The scale of investment in TNs themselves, as opposed to capability and capacity, should average as much as \$20 billion per year until 2050, saving twice that in avoided electric power system investments and natural gas purchases. This proposed investment may seem high, but one must recognize that it is to guide and support development of a whole new sector of critical infrastructure that will deliver about as much energy as does electric power infrastructure.

To kick-start development of the needed capability and capacity, the federal government should consider founding a national centre of excellence (or equivalent) for net-zero energy systems, with a strong, but not exclusive, focus on thermal networks. This should rapidly grow to have its own, world-class staff and facilities (offices, labs, computing, shared knowledge base, field testing), but also have strong affiliations with other private, public and non-profit organizations within Canada and internationally. It would build capability and capacity to address all relevant topics, develop strategic plans, and guide and support net-zero energy initiatives – most importantly, implementation of thermal networks with advantageous sector coupling – across the country. Part of its mandate should be to help Canadian industry develop the capability and capacity (including suitably skilled workforce) to design, build, operate and maintain thermal networks at the scale advocated in this report.

7.3. Public engagement

When strategic transformation of energy systems is considered, it is important to engage the public in the general principles that they value (decarbonization, local energy sources, adaptability, economic implications) and then shape an energy systems vision that reflects those values. It is also important that the public may raise issues that justify and are addressed through investigation or analyses. By being listened to, and having work done in response, both awareness and support are developed. European experience illustrates the value of the early creation of information centres with possible system models and information sources that become a concrete demonstration that the public is being listened to and that further questions or challenges are welcomed.

²⁹ Pipe, alone, could be worth many \$10 billions of business for the Canadian steel industry currently suffering from US tariffs.

With respect to hybrid/transitional solutions that will lead to eventual decarbonization of building heating, the public should be helped to clearly understand how they can/should contribute, why, when and what supports are available. This will include explanation of the local heating (and cooling) plan, the alternatives considered, the costs and other impacts of all alternatives and how the preferred local plan fits into the integrated regional and provincial plans for both heat and electricity.

The short- and long-term economic implications for electrical and/or TN infrastructure associated with different alternatives should be clearly explained. Until now, infrastructure implications of the electrification pathway, with ASHPs, have not been adequately assessed or disclosed to the public. These include the need for massive power system expansion to meet cold-weather peak demand, large scale replacement of existing "last mile" electricity distribution infrastructure, and service and panel upgrades to many/most homes.

As decisions become more concrete, it is also important to incorporate exemplary engineering and architectural features into any facilities being developed so that the public has results of which they are proud. While this may cost more than a least-cost solution, well performing and attractive facilities create ongoing support. They can also be appealing examples to other communities considering similar developments. The waste incinerators in Copenhagen (Amager Bakke) and Vienna (Spittelau) are excellent examples and have become attractive destinations for both locals and tourists.³⁰

Such responsive engagement, transparent sharing of information, and a commitment to best operational practices and to attractive architecture, create growing support for projects as well as respect for the decision makers that oversaw the process.

7.4. The Process of Transition to TNs

Thermal networks are highly variable in the density of heat loads, the availability and cost of decarbonized energy, and the proximity of sources to the heat loads. A clear vision of an ultimate, decarbonized system with a plan on how such sources can be incorporated is very important. With such a plan, a TN utility can move from preparing potential customers (lowering demand and temperature requirements), to creating and connecting building clusters (even if initially on fossil fuel), aggregating heat load through interconnection, and then converting from remaining fossil sources to other sources of waste or rejected heat or renewable energy. During this process, the availability of sources and the relationship of supply and demand can be considered and the value of thermal energy storage (short term or seasonal) can be considered, and, in most cases, adopted.

For most of the areas where TNs will be developed, current heating relies on natural gas. If, perhaps after a failure of their own heating system, a large customer decides that they would like TN service but it is not yet available in their area, the local TN utility might take responsibility for that building heating service and install a portable natural gas or oil boiler until the TN can be

³⁰ <https://www.hbs.edu/environment/blog/post/IFC-2024-Amager-Bakke>,
<https://www.visitingvienna.com/footsteps/spittelau/>

expanded to provide service. This way, a customer is secured and an incentive is provided to the TN utility to develop other customers in the area to justify expansion.

Similarly, owners of clusters of buildings may wish to collectively change over to TN service. They might form the basis of a local TN that can initially produce heat with natural gas. There may be several such neighbourhood clusters that can be enlarged and then interconnected to form a larger network that can justify the development of or connection to non-emitting heat sources.

These small-scale, local mechanisms are not substitutes for strategic planning, but they could play a role in the transition. With a TN established, planners can encourage new developments that benefit from, or offer benefits to, the TN utility and to the community. Existing or new industries might sell heat as could data centres. As in Finland, some industries might forego having their own heating plant in favour of heat supplied from the community system. Electric utilities could be encouraged to locate CHP plants, including emerging smaller scale SMR CHP reactors within or near to host communities.

7.5. Hybrid/Transitional Systems Summary

It is clear that, if Canada is to decarbonize, both electrification and thermal networks pathways will take a substantial investment and also a major transformation in thinking on how to move forward.

Successful transformation at-scale will require comprehensive and ongoing strategic planning of roadmaps to adaptable, resilient and affordable decarbonized heating. The plans should address not only the 2050 target but also no-regrets interim measures until TN services can be established in areas where they are deemed the best option. Strong, effective public engagement will be needed to ensure support for the plans and their evolution in response to practical experience, new ideas, and new information.

Priority must be given to developing public and private sector capability and capacity to plan, build, operate and maintain decarbonized heating for all existing and new buildings. Significant investment should be focused on thermal network utilities, which will become critical infrastructure.

Areas deemed not suitable for TNs could focus on building efficiency measures and GSHPs as a reference option, with consideration of other options like solar thermal or biomass home heating. Areas deemed suitable for TNs could focus on buildings to lower heating loads and to lower the temperatures required to serve heating needs. Where building owners need to replace existing equipment before TN service becomes available, they might consider ASHPs sized for cooling and able to provide heat at moderate temperatures, but continue to use natural gas furnaces below about +4 C.

Mixed-use planning should be encouraged to increase the likelihood that heat sources are near heat loads. Thermal networks could be expanded or created to buy and sell thermal energy for heating. Thermal energy storage could be incorporated to manage loads and minimize seasonal peaks.

As TNs develop, integration with larger regional solutions may be advantageous. Plans should include consideration of thermal energy corridors that can buy and sell heat along the

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way, incorporate larger thermal energy storage options and harness larger scale sources such as nuclear CHP or major industrial reject heat sources.

The foregoing approach should allow a smooth transformation from building based-heating solutions to societal solutions that are more adaptable, resilient and affordable leading to both more stable electricity and heating service costs.

8. Distributional Consequences

The purpose of this Section is to analyze the direct and indirect consequences of the two alternative pathways for decarbonizing building heating in Ontario: that is, transitioning building heating from fossil fuel-based heating (primarily using natural gas) to either electrification (using standalone air-source heat pumps) or centralized thermal networks (district energy systems).

The key direct consequences reviewed include:

- Ability to fulfill the need for reliable, affordable, socially equitable and universally available heating
- The financial costs of planning and executing the alternate solutions
- The environmental benefits achieved by implementing the systems.

Indirect consequences include:

- Impacts on the national and provincial economy, including on growth, investment, productivity, employment, incomes, new industries and government fiscal resources
- Effects on employment, job creation and job loss
- Impacts on life safety, health, wellness and the environment
- Opportunities for technological change and innovation
- Social equity
- Cultural, social, and physical impacts on communities and nature.

Ultimately, initiatives of the transformational scale and scope of the two pathways will impact the lives of virtually every Canadian citizen – and will have important repercussions for different groups of stakeholders. This Section 8 summarizes the more detailed review and analysis of distributional consequences outlined in Annex E, which assesses the financial costs and environmental benefits of the solutions proposed, and the potential spin-offs, spillovers, and social and economic consequences of their impacts on different groups and organizations in Canada.

Readers wishing a more comprehensive assessment of the distributional consequences are directed to the corresponding sections of Annex E.

8.1. Purpose

Context & Rationale:

- Emissions Challenge: The heating of buildings is a major source of greenhouse gas emissions in Ontario —accounting for nearly 25% of emissions provincially and more than half in major urban centers like Toronto. To seriously address the issue of reducing emissions to fight climate change, decarbonizing building heating needs to be a major focus
- Heating as an Essential Service: Heating is a fundamental need and an essential service in cold-climate countries such as Canada. Any solution needs to be functionally effective, reliable, safe, affordable, universally available and socially equitable.

- Beyond Climate: The challenges of decarbonizing heating rival the largest infrastructure projects in Canada's history and the costs will extend into the hundreds of billions of dollars and the effects will be felt for decades. The opportunities are also enormous: bolstering economic growth, creating jobs, enhancing energy security, improving our quality of life and positioning us for success in a rapidly changing world.

Strategic Pathways:

The Two Pathways research analyzes two alternative strategies for transitioning building heating from the Business as Usual (BAU) current status quo that primarily using natural gas. The alternatives include:

- **Standalone Electrification (SE):**
 - Uses air-source heat pumps (supplemented as needed by electric resistance heating)
 - Leverages the electrical grid but demands significant upgrades to accommodate peak demand during extreme winters.
 - In Ontario, the heating of buildings uses as much energy as all other sources of electricity demand combined. Heating demand is concentrated in the winter months and is not evenly distributed over the entire year. Full electrification of heating would triple the peak demand for power and cause the system's capacity utilization factor to fall by one half.
- **District Energy Systems (DES):**
 - Uses centralized thermal networks that integrate diverse thermal sources (including waste heat, geothermal and other clean energy sources).
 - Generally more effective for dense urban areas with economies of scale, but requires complex, upfront infrastructure investments.
 - Is generally deployed in urban areas using local sources of energy and so does not require extensive inter-regional transmission networks. Can effectively use thermal energy storage to help balance demand and reduce costs.

Policy Imperative:

- Decarbonizing building heating needs to be considered in the context of a broader exploration of distributional consequences. It is not only a technical and environmental challenge but also a nation-building opportunity. The transition should promote economic growth, create jobs, and improve overall living standards, ensuring that the benefits are regionally and socially inclusive.
- The key themes addressed in this Section and stakeholder groups that are impacted include:
 - **Key themes:** Functionality, Feasibility and Reliability; Financial Costs and Impact on GHG Emissions; Energy Affordability; Funding & Ownership; Economic Impact; Employment Impact; Health, Safety & Environmental Effects; Technology & Innovation; Social Equity; and Community & Cultural Impacts

- Key stakeholder groups: Government & Regulatory Bodies; Utilities & Energy Providers; Building Owners & Operators; Technology & Equipment Suppliers; Construction, Engineering & Installation Firms; Financial Institutions & Investors; Industry Associations and Environmental & Community Organizations; Academic & Research Institutions; Labour Unions; and End Consumers and Local Communities

8.2. Functionality, Feasibility, Reliability & Resilience

Purpose & Scope

This section evaluates the viability of the three heating technologies (natural gas, electric heat pumps, and district energy systems) based on four key considerations: functionality, feasibility of implementation, reliability and resilience.

Technology Comparison:

- **Natural Gas Heating:**
 - **Functionality:** Mature and widely deployed infrastructure; a familiar technology with decades of proven performance supported by a well-established ecosystem
 - **Vulnerabilities:** Aging infrastructure, fossil fuel dependency, limited adaptability to decarbonization targets, and potential supply chain disruptions
- **Electric Heat Pumps:**
 - **Functionality:** Provide decentralized, flexible, and modular heating solutions; effective in moderate climates.
 - **Vulnerabilities:** Efficiency declines in extreme cold; performance depends on proper sizing and robust electrical grid support; shorter operational lifespan requires periodic replacement; if widely adopted, place enormous strain on the electricity grid's peak capacity; vulnerable to power outages
- **District Energy Systems:**
 - **Functionality:** Centralized systems that can harness multiple thermal sources (waste heat, renewable and non-emitting thermal) to deliver efficient heating in urban settings; thermal energy storage enhances ability to deal with seasonal peak demands; proven technology widespread in Europe and growing in Asia
 - **Vulnerabilities:** Centralized infrastructure introduces risks—a failure at the central plant or in the distribution network can disrupt service over large areas; requires planning and implementation of new distribution infrastructure in most North American urban areas

Feasibility Considerations:

- All pathways entail major long term capital investments and are subject to the high implementation risks associated with large-scale mega-projects.

- Grid upgrades for electric heat pumps must manage extreme winter loads and entail capacity increases for generation and transmission infrastructure at a scale not previously undertaken in Canada.
- DES requires detailed local planning and extensive network development; solutions are most effective in urban centres and particularly in planned new development projects.

Reliability & Resilience:

- **Natural Gas:** Benefits from decentralized installations that limit localized failures but are exposed to supply disruptions.
- **Electricity:** Heat pumps are reliable under optimal conditions but are vulnerable to grid outages or weather extremes.
- **DES:** Offers high reliability in urban contexts due to integrated backup systems (e.g., thermal storage), yet its centralized design means that a single fault could have widespread effects.

Implications:

With diverse climatic and operational challenges, an optimal strategy might combine these technologies to play to their respective strengths in different settings (urban vs. rural).

8.3. Financial Costs and GHG Emissions

Overview:

Section 8.3 evaluates the core issues of the financial costs and greenhouse gas emission impacts of decarbonizing Ontario's building heating systems

- Costs and emissions are evaluated and compared at the provincial, municipal and household levels

Analysis Across Three Levels:

- **Provincial Level:**
 - **Methodology:** A macro assessment at the Ontario provincial level of the additional capital expenditures required to decarbonize the electrical grid and shift from natural gas heating to either electrification or thermal networks. The analysis is based on scenarios drawn from the MIDAC research report ("Space Heating and Electrification – Impact on the Electricity Grid" (dated February 4, 2025 and included as Annex A.) The analysis examines alternatives presented in five scenarios ranging from Business as Usual (BAU) to various degrees of electrification and DES deployment
 - **Major Infrastructure Investment:** Ontario's electric grid, already over 85% net zero, must be fully decarbonized if net zero emission goals are to be met in the future. However, meeting peak winter demand—especially if heating shifts entirely to electricity—requires a significant and inefficient expansion of generation and transmission capacity, whose costs need to be assessed. District Energy Systems

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(while not placing significant incremental strain on the electricity grid) require substantial investment at the local level to create new thermal networks to service municipalities. The analysis compares the capital costs and GHG emissions for electrification and district energy options

- **Full Electrification (Scenario 3):** This pathway would necessitate an estimated incremental capital investment of about \$527 billion (2024 dollars) to upgrade grid capacity for the additional winter heating load. While it achieves net-zero heating emissions when paired with a net-zero grid, it drives up consumer costs significantly and reduces the grid operating capacity factor by almost half.
- **District Energy Systems (Scenario 5):** In contrast, a DES approach requires roughly \$264 billion in capital outlays to develop new thermal network infrastructure primarily at the local level —a savings of nearly 50% compared to full electrification. DES relies on localized waste heat and modest grid expansion (even after accounting for auxiliary electric demand), while still achieving net-zero emissions from heating
- **Hybrid Approaches (Scenario 4):** A partial electrification option that supplements ASHPs with natural gas during extreme cold: it reduces grid upgrade costs substantially but offers only modest GHG emissions reductions. It suggests opportunities for transitional savings and/or longer term prospects to optimize system performance using hybrid solutions.
- **Results:** The estimated capital costs of the infrastructure investments in generation and transmission/distribution networks for each of the scenarios is set out in Tables 8.1 and 8.2, together with the estimated impacts on GHG emissions. The costs are illustrated in Figure 8.1. The scenarios assume a two-part process that decarbonizes the grid and decarbonizes heating.

Table 8-1 Provincial level: 2050 capital costs and GHG emissions: Decarbonizing the grid

Part 1: Decarbonize the Grid					
Scenario	Level	Capital Costs (2024\$B)			GHG
		Generation	Transmission/ Distribution	Total	Emissions (Mt/yr)
Sc.1: BAU Business as Usual	Municipal Provincial	N/A	N/A	N/A	62.9 (Grid & Heating))
Sc. 2: NZ Grid Net Zero Grid No Electrified Heating	Municipal Provincial	N/A 239.3 239.3	N/A 107.7 107.7	N/A 347.0 347.0	22.1 (Heating)

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Table 8-2 Provincial level: 2050 capital costs and GHG emissions: Decarbonizing heating

Part 2: Decarbonize Heating					
Scenario	Level	Incremental Capital Costs (2024\$B)			GHG
		Generation	Transmission/ Distribution	Total	Emissions (Mt/yr)
Sc. 3: FE Net Zero Grid; Full Elec. Heating	Municipal Provincial	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.0
		363.7	163.7	527.4	
		363.7	163.7	527.4	
Sc. 4: PE NZ Grid: Partial Elec. Htg NG Furnace Supplement	Municipal Provincial	N/A	N/A	N/A	18.8
		15.6	7.0	22.7	
		15.6	7.0	22.7	
Sc. 5: DES NZ Grid; Full Dist. Energy	Municipal Provincial	83.2	153.1	236.2	0.0
		19.3	8.7	28.0	
		102.5	161.8	264.2	

Figure 8.1 Provincial level: Annual GHG emissions vs. capital costs (SE vs. DES)

• **Municipal Level:**

An “Illustrative Community” model derived from the FVB pre-feasibility study (dated March 28, 2025 and included as Annex B) is used to simulate the cost and performance impacts of each heating alternative for a typical Southern Ontario municipality.- This model considers local energy demand, infrastructure phasing, and the allocation of grid upgrade costs.

- The model demonstrates that the DES option maintains competitive annual operating costs—comparable to the current natural gas (BAU) scenario—while full electrification incurs significantly higher costs, largely due to expensive in-building equipment and the need for large-scale grid investments.
- When the community’s pro rata share of the grid upgrade costs is factored in, the SE approach is approximately three times more expensive annually than the DES pathway.
- Furthermore, DES improves energy security and resiliency by taking advantage of thermal energy storage to reduce the risk of system overloads during extreme weather
- In both the DES (district energy) and SE (electrification) scenarios, GHG emissions are reduced to zero, while the BAU system (natural gas heating) is forecast to generate 434,000 tonnes of emissions annually.
- The comparative costs of the alternative heating systems at the municipal level are set out in Table 8.3 and illustrated in Figure 8.2.

Table 8-3 Community level: Alternate heating systems comparative costs

Illustrative Community: Alternate Heating Systems Comparative Costs						
in millions of 2024\$						
	BAU Business as Usual		SE Standalone Electrification		DES District Energy	
	Amount (\$MM)	Annualized	Amount (\$MM)	Annualized	Amount (\$MM)	Annualized
Operating		109.7		210.8		94.2
Capital						
In-Building	561.0	54.0	2,110.0	203.3	642.0	42.7
Distribution	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2,584.0	163.9
Energy Source	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1,404.0	89.1
Sub-total	561.0	54.0	2,110.0	203.3	4,630.0	295.7
Allocated (Grid)	N/A	N/A	10,352.7	752.1	548.7	39.9
Total	561.0	163.7	12,462.7	1,166.2	5,178.7	429.7

Figure 8.2 Community Level – Cost Comparison Including Allocated Grid Upgrade Costs (\$ millions)

- **Household Level:**

- At the household level, a detailed forecast of monthly energy bills for 2050 is provided, incorporating electricity and natural gas costs, carbon tax implications, and the amortization of in-building heating equipment for each scenario.
- For residential consumers, switching to full electrification (SE) would cause monthly energy bills to rise markedly compared to systems that remain partially reliant on natural gas or transition to DES.
- The DES pathway delivers competitive monthly energy costs—comparable to hybrid natural gas systems and well below the full electrification option —while simultaneously eliminating heating-related GHG emissions.
- This bottom-up assessment reinforces the cost efficiency of DES over direct electrification when viewed from the consumer perspective.
- Unlike the SE or BAU options, the DES alternative builds in the full cost of creating a new generation and transmission/distribution infrastructure
- The monthly energy costs for a typical home under the five scenarios are set out in Table 8.4 and illustrated in Figure 8.3.

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Table 8-4 Monthly Energy Costs for a Typical Home – 2050 Year (2022\$/month)

	Sc.1 (BAU) Business as Usual	Sc.2 (NZ Grid) NZ Grid; No Elec Htg	Sc.3 (SE) NZ Grid; Full Elec	Sc.4 (PE) NZ Grid; Part Elec NG Supplement	Sc.5 (DES) NZ Grid; Full District Energy System
Electricity Bill	87	178	632	201	247
NG Bill	75	75	0	67	0
Thermal Bill	0	0	0	0	284
SubTotal	162	253	632	268	531
Carbon Tax	94	62	0	56	0
SubTotal	256	315	632	324	531
In-Bldg Equip	54	54	193	247	35
Total	310	369	825	571	566

Figure 8.3 Household Level – Comparative Monthly Energy Costs for a Typical Home (2022\$/month)

Strategic Implications & Conclusions

- **Cost-Effectiveness vs. Emissions Performance:** Although both full electrification and DES can reach net-zero heating emissions (when paired with a decarbonized grid), the enormous capital and operating costs of electrification make it less economically attractive, especially during peak demand periods.
- **DES Advantages:** District Energy Systems offer a more economically sustainable and resilient solution. They reduce the financial burden of extensive grid expansion by efficiently utilizing local energy sources and thermal storage, effectively lowering both capital and operating costs.
- **Optimal Pathways:** The document underscores that there is no “silver bullet” for decarbonizing building heating. Instead, a diversified, hybrid approach may be optimal—tailoring solutions to local conditions while balancing environmental objectives, technical feasibility, and financial constraints. Drawing lessons from European digital twin models and integrated energy planning frameworks, Ontario’s municipalities could develop customized strategies that aggregate to a robust provincial transformation.
- **Summary:** the analysis strongly supports the DES pathway as a more cost-effective and resilient alternative to full electrification, offering a substantially lower capital investment and operating cost while achieving net-zero GHG emissions at both community and household scales. A hybrid strategy may also be viable during a transitional period, allowing stakeholders to balance short-term cost pressures with long-term sustainability goals.

8.4. Funding & Ownership Issues

Background and Context

Transitioning Canada’s building heating systems to low-carbon alternatives demands multi-billion dollar investments. Achieving this transformation—whether it involves upgrading power generation and transmission grids or constructing urban thermal networks—requires careful consideration of who funds, owns, and manages these assets. The ownership and financing model selected will influence risk allocation, governance, consumer pricing, and ultimately, public acceptance.

Ownership Models:

The three principal ownership models for large-scale energy infrastructure include:

- **Public Ownership**
 - Characteristics: Direct management by government entities (municipalities or crown agencies), ensuring decisions align with long-term social and environmental goals.
 - Advantages: Lower financing costs due to government credit ratings, stability in long-range planning, and the ability to subsidize rates to enhance equity.

- Drawbacks: Potential bureaucratic inertia, slower responsiveness, and susceptibility to shifts in political priorities.
- **Private Ownership**
 - Characteristics: Fully market-driven operations where commercial entities invest in, build, and operate the systems with profitability as a core driver.
 - Advantages: Higher operational efficiency, rapid innovation, and flexibility in decision-making.
 - Drawbacks: A risk of prioritizing short-term returns over public benefit, which may lead to higher consumer fees and neglect of less commercially attractive areas.
- **Hybrid Models (Public-Private Partnerships & Regulated Utilities)**
 - Characteristics: Shared ownership between public and private sectors, balancing public oversight with private-sector efficiency through contractual risk-sharing.
 - Advantages: Combines the strengths of both sectors, enables lower-cost financing with regulated returns, and supports integrated long-term planning.
 - Drawbacks: Complex negotiations and potential challenges in aligning split incentives over the long term.

Financing Approaches:

Financing approaches include debt and equity alternatives:

- **Equity Financing**
 - Sources: Government equity (or capital investments), private equity and infrastructure funds, and capital provided within PPP frameworks.
 - Benefits: Greater operational flexibility and potential for long-term capital appreciation, although investors assume higher risk due to the absence of fixed repayments.
- **Debt Financing**
 - Instruments: Traditional bank loans, green bonds (tailored for environmentally beneficial projects), project finance debt (with repayments tied to project cash flow), and government-backed loans or export credit agency (ECA) financing.
 - Benefits: Lower risk profile and predictable cash flow requirements though often subject to strict covenants that may limit flexibility.
- **Blended Approach:**
 - A blended financing approach is recommended to balance risk and return while meeting policy objectives and ensuring that the funding framework supports both capital expenditures and ongoing operations.

Aligning Ownership with Network Components and Lifecycle

- Recognizing that the risks and requirements vary across different parts of the energy network (generation, transmission, distribution, and customer interfaces) and over time, ownership and funding models should be matched to each component's characteristics and evolve over the project's lifecycle

- Drawing on European experiences—from Norway’s mix of competitive generation, regulated transmission, and municipal distribution to Estonia’s phased transition from state to hybrid systems—provides insights into how governance can adapt to technological and market developments.

Social & Regulatory Considerations:

- A central theme is ensuring that the chosen funding and ownership structures promote social equity.
- Key recommendations include:
 - Conducting rigorous cost–benefit and equity impact assessments that account for externalities (e.g., health benefits, emissions reductions).
 - Designing tariffs with tiered pricing, decoupled fixed and variable charges, and targeted subsidies to protect vulnerable populations.
 - Engaging stakeholders transparently—including consumer advocacy groups—to ensure that pricing and cost allocation are fair.
 - Implementing flexible regulatory oversight capable of periodic review and dynamic adjustment in response to technological evolution and changing cost structures.
 - Exploring innovative hybrid financing mechanisms (such as green bonds and public banks) to limit the fiscal burden on consumers.

Financial Model Case Study:

- FVB developed a financial model based on the performance and cost parameters assembled to examine the feasibility of a clean, 4th generation, thermal energy network to provide for all the building heating in an illustrative community of approximately 150,000 residents.
- Capital expenditures of about \$4.6 billion (\$2024) are estimated to build out the initial DES network for the illustrative community, including for energy sources, distribution systems, and in-building heat exchangers.
- The range of returns (unlevered IRRs of 5% to 8%) confirmed the expectation that while private funding may well be interested and useful in helping to realize wide-spread thermal networks, the risk/return ratio likely demands policy assistance (at least in the initial implementation stages). Once the system is stabilized, and the regulatory approvals, development and marketing/adoption risks have been resolved, private capital may provide a useful exit strategy to recoup the original investment.

8.5. Macro-Economic Impacts

Section 8.5 examines the macroeconomic impacts of decarbonizing Canadian building heating. The analysis covers four broad themes: investment and infrastructure renewal, job creation and GDP growth, new industry and trade dynamics, and fiscal implications.

Investment and Infrastructure Renewal:

- The transition is expected to mobilize over \$500 billion in capital investments across power generation, transmission, and thermal networks.
- Modernization efforts will enhance grid efficiency, reduce energy losses, and attract both public and private investments.

Job Creation and GDP Growth:

- Large-scale infrastructure projects will generate hundreds of thousands of direct jobs (in planning, engineering, and construction).
- Indirect job creation through multiplier effects across supply chains could increase overall employment by 1.5–2.5 times the direct job count.
- These investments will stimulate aggregate demand, boost GDP, and lead to productivity enhancements across sectors.

New Industries and Trade Dynamics:

- Shift in Trade Balances: With decreased reliance on fossil fuels for domestic consumption, there is potential for reconfigured trade dynamics. Canada may even boost fossil fuel exports—as seen in other successful national strategies—and, at the same time, reduce import dependency by ramping up domestic production of clean technology components.
- Exporting Clean Technologies: Canadian innovations in heat pump design, smart grid management, and district energy planning open new export markets, particularly in regions with similar cold-climate challenges.
- Emergence of New Industries: The transition will spur growth in the clean technology sector, expand service industries related to energy planning and consulting, and help create a more resilient and energy self-sufficient domestic market.

Fiscal Implications:

- Short-term fiscal pressures include higher public borrowing and increased government debt.
- Long-term benefits are expected through a broader tax base, increased revenues, and enhanced fiscal sustainability as productivity rises.
- Impact on Incomes and Inflation: Increased household income due to job creation is anticipated to boost consumer spending. While the large-scale fiscal stimulus might generate short-term inflationary pressures, greater efficiency and productivity gains are expected to counterbalance these effects in the long run.

Conclusion:

Despite initial borrowing and potential inflation, the macroeconomic benefits—increased GDP, job creation, and industrial competitiveness—of investment in decarbonized heating infrastructure support a robust and sustainable economic future.

8.6. Employment Impacts

Section 8.6 explores more deeply the employment impacts associated with transitioning Canadian building heating. It addresses different dimensions of employment effects, from job losses in traditional sectors to new opportunities in clean energy and infrastructure projects.

- Oil and Gas Sector Vulnerability:
 - Approximately 600,000 jobs are currently related to the oil and gas industry. Transitioning from natural gas heating risks 50–75% of these jobs, especially affecting downstream services such as distribution and maintenance.
- Mitigation Strategies:
 - Strategies such as shifting to export-oriented models and implementing comprehensive just transition policies (retraining, income support, labor market initiatives) are essential.
- Growth in New Energy Industries:
 - Clean Energy Sector Expansion: Forecasts suggest that clean energy jobs in Canada could grow significantly—from approximately 430,500 in 2020 to around 639,200 by 2030—as investments in renewable generation, advanced grid technologies, and thermal energy solutions (including heat pumps and district energy systems) expand.
- Key Opportunity Areas:
 - Renewable Electricity Generation: Opportunities in construction, installation, and long term operation across wind, solar, hydro, and emerging nuclear technologies.
 - Grid Modernization: New roles in digital control, smart meter deployment, cybersecurity, and IT integration.
 - Thermal Energy Systems: Expanded employment in the installation, design, operation, and maintenance of district energy networks.
- Multiplier and Supply Chain Effects:
 - The development of these sectors will not only create direct jobs but also stimulate indirect positions through enhanced local supply chains and induced employment resulting from increased household spending. Regions, including areas traditionally reliant on fossil fuels, can benefit from robust retraining and local economic diversification initiatives.

Infrastructure and Construction Benefits:

- Major Construction Projects: Investments in upgrading Canada's power grid, constructing renewable generation facilities, and developing urban district energy networks are expected to create substantial employment opportunities. These include roles for civil and electrical engineers, construction laborers, project planners, and digital control specialists.
- Employment Multipliers: Historical evidence and international examples (such as the employment impacts from major infrastructure projects like bridges and urban transit systems) indicate that each direct job can generate an additional 1.5 to 2.5 jobs in local supply chains, manufacturing, consulting, and auxiliary services.

- **Regional Synergies:** While urban centers (e.g., Toronto, Montreal, Vancouver) and regions with established engineering excellence are likely to experience concentrated job growth, fossil fuel-dependent regions (e.g., Alberta and Saskatchewan) have significant potential to transition, provided effective retraining and diversification policies are in place.

Overall Impact:

While there will be significant job losses in traditional sectors, robust policies and investments are expected to lead to a net increase in employment and regional economic diversification.

8.7. Health, Safety & Environmental Impacts

Section 8.7 focuses on three key areas: improvements in public health, environmental enhancements, and evolving safety considerations as our building heating systems decarbonize.

- **Health Benefits:**
 - **Improved Air Quality:** Eliminating on site combustion significantly reduces emissions of particulates, nitrogen oxides, and volatile organic compounds. This leads to fewer respiratory illnesses such as asthma and chronic bronchitis—providing marked benefits to children, the elderly, and those with preexisting conditions.
 - **Cardiovascular and Mortality Reductions:** Lower exposure to combustion byproducts is linked to decreased incidents of heart attacks, strokes, and hypertension, potentially averting tens of thousands of premature deaths over the coming decades.
 - **Economic and Quality of Life Gains:** Reduced healthcare costs and improved indoor air quality enhance overall well being and productivity, especially benefiting vulnerable and marginalized communities.
 - **Climate-Related Health Improvements:** Mitigation of climate change, through reduced emissions, may lessen the severity of heatwaves and other extreme weather events, further contributing to public health
- **Environmental Benefits:**
 - **Climate Change Mitigation:** Switching from natural gas significantly cuts greenhouse gas emissions, aiding the achievement of net zero targets and reducing the frequency and severity of extreme weather events.
 - **Enhanced Air, Water, and Land Quality:** Reduced extraction and combustion lower pollutant emissions and risks—improving ambient air quality, reducing water contamination, and minimizing land degradation.
 - **Biodiversity and Ecosystem Benefits:** Healthier ecosystems result from improved environmental quality, supporting more resilient biodiversity and sustainable urban development.
 - **Water Management:** A decline in water intensive fossil fuel extraction contributes to more sustainable water use and reduced environmental risks associated with contamination and overconsumption.
- **Safety Considerations:**

- Risk Reduction from Fossil Fuels: Transitioning away from natural gas eliminates hazards associated with on site combustion, such as explosions, fires, gas leaks, and toxic carbon monoxide emissions. It also diminishes upstream risks in fuel extraction, processing, and transportation.
- New Safety Challenges: While electric heat pumps and district systems remove combustion risks, they introduce concerns such as electrical hazards, grid overload, and the “single point of failure” risks in centralized systems. Robust safety protocols—including rigorous installation, continuous monitoring, cybersecurity measures, and updated building codes—are essential to manage these issues.
- Comparative Safety Dynamics: Although alternative energy sources (such as nuclear, hydro, solar, and wind) bring their own unique challenges, overall, the reduced reliance on combustion-based processes represents a significant improvement in safety for both buildings and communities.
- Synergistic Benefits through Sector Coupling
 - Enhanced Efficiency and Safety: By integrating systems—such as combined heat and power (CHP) plants and waste heat recovery—overall efficiency is increased and fuel combustion needs are minimized.
 - Dynamic Integration: Surplus renewable electricity can be used for export - or to drive heat pump operations, along with thermal storage solutions, that improve operational resilience, reduce reliance on backup fossil fuel systems, and create a redundant, multi-source energy network.
 - Advanced Digital Controls: Cutting-edge sensors and automated controls further enhance safety and environmental performance by enabling real time monitoring and fault detection.
- Conclusion:
 - The transition offers significant public health, environmental, and safety benefits—provided that new technical risks are carefully managed.
 - Better Health Outcomes: Reduced respiratory and cardiovascular risks along with decreased premature mortality.
 - Stronger Environmental Integrity: Lower emissions, improved air and water quality, and enhanced ecosystem resilience.
 - Improved Safety: Eliminating traditional combustion hazards while managing new risks through modern technological safeguards.
 - Integrated Benefits: Sector coupling maximizes efficiency and resilience, delivering additional societal gains

8.8. Technology & Innovation

Overview:

Decarbonizing building heating in Canada requires a coordinated mix of advanced and integrated technologies. This Section 8.8 outlines the emerging innovations and research opportunities that

will drive the transition from natural gas systems to electrified heat pumps and district energy systems. The discussion spans breakthrough technological developments, avenues for research and development, and strategies to operationalize and commercialize these innovations—in turn positioning Canada as a global leader in sustainable energy

Technological Innovations:

- **Advanced Heat Pump Technologies:** Improvements in compressor designs and low-GWP refrigerants enhance efficiency and cold-weather performance.
- **Smart Controls and IoT Integration:** Real-time monitoring and AI-driven analytics (including digital twins) optimize system management and predictive maintenance.
- **Thermal Energy Storage:** Cutting-edge storage solutions (using phase change materials or insulated tanks, aquifers, boreholes, pits and caverns) enable surplus heat capture for peak demand.
- **Smart Grid and Microgrid Integration:** Enhances coordination between renewable energy and heating demands, ensuring grid stability and maximizing clean energy use.
- **Innovative District Energy Systems & Hybrid Models:** Modern networks integrating multiple renewable thermal sources and waste heat recovery boost efficiency and resilience.
- **New Materials and Energy Management Platforms:** Advanced insulation and environmentally friendly refrigerants, paired with AI algorithms, drive demand response and lower emissions.

Research & Commercialization Opportunities:

- Areas of focus in electrification R&D include refining heat pump performance, integrating renewables, and enhancing energy storage.
- District energy research involves developing interoperable control systems, leveraging waste heat recovery, and designing robust cybersecurity protocols. There is also significant opportunity in simulation and digital twin modeling to innovate multi-energy integration and inform supportive regulatory frameworks.
- Commercial opportunities span planning, engineering, consulting, capacity building, and innovative financing approaches that support broader deployment. Expert services for integrated system planning, feasibility studies, and digital infrastructure development are vital. Consulting in waste heat recovery, renewable integration, and advanced controls can support large-scale implementations. Training programs, cybersecurity consulting, regulatory support, and innovative financing models (including public–private partnerships and asset leasing) will be crucial for rolling out clean energy infrastructure across Canada. These initiatives not only support domestic decarbonization but also open export opportunities for Canadian expertise.

Conclusion:

Canada's transition to electrified heating and district energy systems is a dual opportunity: advancing technological research to boost efficiency, safety, and environmental performance, and building a robust ecosystem for business and export in the global market for sustainable energy solutions. Embracing these innovations will not only meet domestic emission reduction targets but also transform Canada into a world leader in sustainable energy technology and integrated smart energy systems.

8.9. Social Equity

This section emphasizes that social equity is a critical pillar during Canada's transition from natural gas heating to low carbon technologies. Ensuring that benefits are distributed fairly and that vulnerable populations and regions are not unduly burdened is essential for building public support and achieving a resilient energy transition.

Social Equity Frameworks: The analysis is structured around four key equity concepts:

- **Horizontal Equity:**
 - **Concept:** Households in similar circumstances should have equal access to benefits, information, support, and financial incentives.
 - **Challenges:** Differences in building age, design, and efficiency can lead to highly variable retrofit costs—even among households in similar income brackets. Renters may have less control over system upgrades compared to homeowners, resulting in an unequal distribution of benefits versus burdens.
 - **Comparison:** District energy systems typically serve defined geographic areas, potentially offering standardized benefits within urban neighborhoods, whereas electrification, which works on a building-by-building basis, can produce variable outcomes even among similar households.
- **Vertical Equity:**
 - **Concept:** Policies must adjust the distribution of costs and benefits to reflect differences in household resources, providing greater support for lower income households.
 - **Challenges:** Both advanced heat pumps and district energy installations involve high upfront costs that can disproportionately affect low-income users if not adequately subsidized or financed over time.
 - **Policy Tools:** Targeted subsidies, grants, and innovative financing mechanisms are critical to distribute financial burdens more equitably.
 - **Comparison:** While district energy systems can spread capital expenditures across a network, uniform cost recovery may still unfairly impact low-income customers; individual electrification projects require significant upfront investments that risk increasing financial inequity without robust support.

- **Spatial Equity:**
 - Concept: Geographic location should not dictate access to modern, sustainable energy solutions.
 - Challenges: District energy systems are most viable in dense urban areas, leaving rural or remote regions potentially underserved. Similarly, grid upgrades necessary for electrification may preferentially benefit urban areas due to economies of scale, thereby exacerbating regional disparities.
 - Policy Focus: Tailored incentives, technical assistance, and targeted subsidies are needed to improve access in remote and underinvested regions.
- **Inter-Generational Equity:**
 - Concept: Today's transitions should not impose unsustainable costs or burdens on future generations.
 - Challenges: Large-scale investments may create upfront debt or infrastructure lock in, risking stranded assets or deferred maintenance burdens that future ratepayers must shoulder.
 - Conversely, investments made today in new energy infrastructure could impose significant debt or financing burdens on current taxpayers while delivering environmental and health benefits predominantly in the future.
 - District Energy Systems offer long-term benefits if they are designed with adaptability in mind; however, if retrofits or replacements become necessary down the line, future ratepayers could bear substantial costs.
 - Electrification might initially appear less burdensome, but accelerated grid upgrades to support high demand could defer significant costs to future generations
 - Policy Tools: Long term financing instruments (e.g., green bonds, revolving loan funds) and flexible, life-cycle based planning are essential to ensure that current decisions remain adaptable and financially sustainable over time.

Conclusion:

- A fair transition away from natural gas heating requires embedding these four equity principles in policy design. Key strategies include:
 - Standardizing Program Guidelines: Create clear, transparent eligibility and support criteria to ensure uniform access for similar households.
 - Progressive Financial Supports: Introduce tiered subsidies, low-interest loans, and innovative financing tailored to lower-income households.
 - Regional Tailoring: Develop area-specific measures to ensure that both urban and remote regions can benefit equitably from modern heating solutions.
 - Future-Proofing Investments: Incorporate adaptive and long-term financing instruments that balance immediate costs with sustainable benefits for future generations.
- By addressing horizontal, vertical, spatial, and inter-generational equity, policymakers can secure a more balanced and inclusive decarbonization pathway, ensuring that the social

benefits of cleaner, efficient energy systems are shared broadly while mitigating disproportionately higher costs borne by vulnerable populations.

8.10. Social & Cultural Impacts on Communities and Nature

Many of the things that make life most pleasurable and “worth living” are difficult to quantify: beauty, nature, tranquility, family, community, heritage, culture, friendship, celebration ... Major changes like those involved in a significant energy transition can either disrupt or enhance much of what we value in life and what gives us joy. The section below summarizes several key social and cultural impacts associated with transitioning from fossil fuel heating to electrification and district energy systems and suggests possible strategies to protect community wellbeing and quality of life.

Heritage and Identity:

- Retrofitting historically significant buildings might conflict with preservation efforts, potentially altering culturally important heritage and architectural aesthetics.
- The placement of large, centralized facilities could disrupt sacred or community spaces, affecting cultural practices.

Impact on Natural Habitats and Urban Landscapes:

- Extensive energy infrastructure (from grid expansions to large-scale installations) can fragment natural habitats, reduce biodiversity, and alter local microclimates. The visual intrusion and environmental disruption from large-scale energy projects risks marring the natural beauty and tranquility of wilderness, fields, forests and landscapes that many communities rely on for their quality of life and sense of place.
- Visual and acoustic impacts (industrial eyesores, noise pollution) in urban areas may diminish local well-being and erode a sense of community.
- Infrastructure projects may physically segment neighborhoods, reduce pedestrian connectivity, and hinder social interaction.

Community Engagement and Mitigation Strategies:

- Robust stakeholder engagement (involving local communities, Indigenous groups, and heritage organizations) is essential to identify and protect culturally significant sites.
- Mitigation measures such as adaptive design, impact assessments, and community-centric planning can help preserve cultural and natural assets.

Conclusion:

- Balancing the technical demands of decarbonization with the preservation of cultural heritage, natural aesthetics, and community identity is key. Strategies that integrate community input and adaptive infrastructure design can ensure that energy transitions enhance, rather than diminish, the social and cultural fabric of Canadian communities.

- Ultimately, the goal is to harmonize progress with the well-being of urban communities and the natural environment. Addressing the twin challenges of industrial disruption and urban/rural aesthetics is not merely about reducing technical impacts—it's about preserving the intangible qualities that make neighborhoods and wilderness areas vibrant and livable. As cities evolve, striking a balance between energy and industrial development with human-scale, community-centered environments remains central to sustainable urban planning.

9. District Energy's Legal, Regulatory and Financial Frameworks

Please note that in this Section 9 and the next Section 10 all sources are indicated in footnotes. Each source is accessible through a live [link](#) in a footnote. Some of the sources are also in this report's Bibliography, but more are not.

This section overviews the legal and regulatory framework within which district energy systems (DES — singular or plural according to context, also the companies that operate them) can be developed and maintained in Ontario, and how DES can be financed. DES are definable as *systems that provide buildings with thermal energy for heating and sometimes cooling from centralized sources through networks of insulated pipes that are usually underground*.

With a brief nod at the federal context, this section focuses on provincial (Ontario) legislation, which constrains (or not) how municipalities, usually the main governmental actors in DES, can perform. The section should be reviewed together with Section 10, which speaks to how Ontario and other municipalities could have stronger roles in planning for the use of thermal energy in buildings, and in implementing the plans, thereby facilitating attainment of net-zero objectives.

9.1. Canadian Context

Constitutional considerations

Under Canada's constitution, the primary responsibility for permitting and regulating DES lies with provincial governments through clauses of Section 92 of the *Constitution Act, 1982*.³¹ Under the title "Subjects of exclusive provincial legislation," the several clauses of Section 92 list matters on which provincial laws prevail, including the following:

- (8) Municipal Institutions in the Province.
- (10) Local Works and Undertakings other than such are as of the following Classes:
 - (a) Lines of Steam or other Ships, Railways, Canals, Telegraphs, and other Works and Undertakings connecting the Province with any other or others of the Provinces, or extending beyond the Limits of the Province:
 - (b) Lines of Steam Ships between the Province and any British or Foreign Country:
 - (c) Such Works as, although wholly situate within the Province, are before or after their Execution declared by the Parliament of Canada to be for the general Advantage of Canada or for the Advantage of Two or more of the Provinces.
- (13) Property and Civil Rights in the Province.
- (16) Generally all matters of a merely local or private Nature in the Province.

³¹ See [link](#) for the Constitution of Canada.

The first of these clauses is important because municipalities are usually considered to be the governmental locus of the development and maintenance of DES,³² other than those that serve the buildings of one business or institution.³³ If commercial DES were to become widespread in Ontario, this would likely happen through the initiatives of numerous municipalities facilitated by successive provincial governments.

Creatures of provinces

Courts have almost always interpreted the above constitutional assignment of responsibilities as meaning that municipalities are “creatures of their provinces.”³⁴ Strong, authoritative legal arguments have been made against the “creatures” doctrine.³⁵ They note that several Canadian cities – including at least five in Ontario (Hamilton, Kingston, London, Ottawa, and Toronto) – were incorporated before the existence of their respective provinces – as were several towns and villages, and thus were not creations of their provinces.

During the last 30 years, Canadian municipalities appear to have been unleashed a little from their provinces, beginning in 1994 with Alberta, then British Columbia in 2003 (except, oddly, Vancouver), and Quebec in 2006. These three provinces have each seen abolition of a “laundry list” of “narrow, specific, and restrictive delegations of powers” in favour of “more general authorizations.”³⁶ A lesser loosening is said to have occurred in five of the other seven provinces (Manitoba, New Brunswick, Prince Edward Island, Ontario, and Saskatchewan), although recent happenings may raise questions as to whether Ontario should be included among the five.³⁷ The current legal capacity of Ontario municipalities with respect to financial and other matter relevant to DES is noted below.

³² Municipalities are usually considered to be the governmental locus of the development and maintenance of DES because of their responsibilities for local land-use planning, building attributes, and local infrastructure. For further discussions of the relevant roles of municipalities see [link](#) and [link](#).

³³ Examples of DES serving an institution’s buildings are the University of Toronto’s system serving its downtown campus ([link](#)) and the system serving the federal government’s buildings on both sides of the Ottawa River ([link](#)). Canada’s largest system, owned and operated by Enwave Energy Inc., serves several institutions (the Ontario Government’s complex and several hospitals) as well as more than 150 mostly commercial buildings ([link](#)), all in downtown Toronto. Enwave was initially the Toronto District Heating Corporation, a crown corporation formed at the request of the City of Toronto ([link](#)). Also see Note 64.

³⁴ The “creatures” doctrine was established in the United States in the 1860s as Dillon’s Rule ([link](#)). It was reinforced as an element of Canadian law through a 1993 decision of the Supreme Court of Canada ([link](#)).

³⁵ For arguments against the “creatures” doctrine, see the sources at [link](#) and [link](#).

³⁶ See the chapter by Benoît Frate et al, “Getting Rid of the Laundry List: Exploring the Roots and Effects of the *Municipal Powers Act* in Quebec” in the 2024 book described at [link](#). There it is also explained that B.C.’s 2003 legislation granting municipalities broad service and regulatory powers did not apply to Vancouver, which had had separate powers since the granting of a charter in 1953, powers that did not include the “more general authorizations.”

³⁷ Actions of the Ontario government that have been said to override municipal authority include amalgamating Toronto municipalities in 1998, altering the composition of Toronto council in 2000 and 2018 (the latter during an election), preventing the imposition of road tolls, disallowing the adoption of an alternative electoral system, overriding local planning with Ministerial Zoning Orders, and removing lands from the provincial Greenbelt, as

DES in Canada

There are more than 200 DES in Canada providing about 2.2% of all space heating. More than three quarters of these serve the buildings of only one institution or business. No more than a quarter are commercial ventures selling thermal energy to customers via thermal networks located in the public domain (usually municipal road allowances). About 65 of Canada's DES are in Ontario, including twelve that are commercial ventures.³⁸

Among these twelve is Canada's oldest system – London District Energy – dating from 1880, which along with that of Denver, Colorado may be the second oldest continuously operating system in the world.³⁹ The oldest such system appears to be in south-central France, a commercial geothermal system in Chaudes-Aigues dating from the 14th century.⁴⁰

9.2. Federal Legislation

Even though provinces have primary oversight over district energy systems, some federal legislation is relevant. It includes the following:

Energy Efficiency Regulations: All regulated products must meet federal energy efficiency standards to be imported into Canada or shipped from one province to another for the purpose of sale or lease. Note that Ontario has its own energy efficiency regulations, for the most part harmonized with the federal regulations.⁴¹

Environmental Regulations: Two federal laws can be significant for district energy systems: the *Canadian Environmental Protection Act* and the *Greenhouse Gas Pollution Pricing Act*. The latter *Act* remains in effect, even though the so-called carbon tax at the retail level no longer applies, but the *Act* could well be changed during 2025.⁴²

Straddling borders: Section 92.10(a) of the *Constitution Act* gives the federal government a potentially direct role in the oversight of DES that cross provincial borders (see above), such as the DES shared between Ottawa and Gatineau. This would include borders with the U.S. Such oversight would be exercised through the Canada Energy Regulator.⁴³

set out in the chapter by Taylor, "Metagovernance of Place," in the 2024 book described at [link](#). This laundry list of provincial overrides could also include removal of existing bike lanes and prevention of installation of other such safety amenities ([link](#), [link](#)).

³⁸ An online DES inventory of DES in Canada ([link](#)) is maintained by the Canadian Energy and Emissions Data Centre (CEEDC) at Simon Fraser University. See also the source at [link](#).

³⁹ For the London system, see [link](#), and the CEEDC source in Note 38 for its age. For the Denver system, see [link](#).

⁴⁰ For the system in south-central France in Chaudes-Aigues – which means "hot waters" – see the source at [link](#). There may have been district energy systems in Roman times, perhaps extensions of the prevalent building-specific central heating. A possible example is Bath, UK, then known as Aquae Sulis (waters of the Celtic goddess Sulis), where there is evidence of lead piping that may have been used to conduct hot water to several buildings ([link](#)). Today, heat from spring water serves several buildings, including Bath Abbey ([link](#)), but there is no evidence of continuous district heating as at Chaudes-Aigues.

⁴¹ For federal and Ontario's energy efficiency regulations, see respectively [link](#) and [link](#).

⁴² For the 2023 amendments to *Canadian Environmental Protection Act*, see [link](#). For the *Act*, see [link](#). For discussions about the *Greenhouse Gas Pollution Pricing Act*, see [link](#) and [link](#). For the *Act*, see [link](#).

⁴³ Information about the mandate and responsibilities of the Canada Energy Regulator is at [link](#).

Federal funding of DES, especially their development, could be relevant. Possible sources of funding by the federal government are noted in a later section. Also, if heat from nuclear reactors is used for district energy –not touched on much here – aspects of this use could come under the aegis of the Canadian Nuclear Safety Commission.⁴⁴

9.3. Ontario Legislation

Overview

Such are the powers of Canadian provinces, the Ontario government could move unilaterally and quickly to establish and maintain DES in every part of the province for which deployment would be considered feasible – perhaps serving about 70% of the buildings to be standing in Ontario in 2050.⁴⁵ It could establish one or more crown corporations with powers to develop, operate, and generally regulate DES, expropriate private land, commandeer municipal land and other resources, engage in government-backed borrowing, and share equity in created DES with private investors. The new authority could also require connection to and use of DES where they exist, and ensure decarbonization of buildings in areas not served by DES.

The justification for such draconian action would be that there's no other way of achieving timely decarbonization of emissions from buildings in Ontario. A government could well be committed to this justification but avoid so acting because it feared the electoral consequences. It could be left with three alternatives.

An alternative would be for an Ontario government to change or dispense with decarbonization targets, which may also be unpopular. Another (unlikely) alternative would be to give Ontario municipalities the necessary powers and resources to do what a crown corporation would have done. The third would be to ignore the issue or hand the problem to Ontario municipalities without allowing sufficient authority and resources – which may amount to the same thing.

Of course, a provincial government may not see the need for building decarbonization. Or it may believe there's another viable path to it. The government could assume, for example, that decarbonization can be achieved through widespread electrification of heating – which may be

⁴⁴ Specifically, the Canadian Nuclear Safety Commission (CNSC) would regulate how heat is extracted from the nuclear facility to ensure that the heat's media do not contain radioactive materials. It would not be involved in the transmission or use of the heat. For information about the CNSC, see [link](#).

⁴⁵ This rough estimate is based on several factors, notably consideration of district energy's deployment in Denmark, where it now meets almost 70% of space heating demand ([link](#)) – i.e., almost all the buildings normally used by the non-rural population, which is just over 70% of the total population ([link](#)). Ontario's non-rural population share is higher, about 80% ([link](#)). At least two things suggest that the non-rural penetration of district energy in Ontario by 2050 would have a lower limit than near 100% even if climate considerations impel the maximum feasible penetration. One is that many new buildings could be built to passive house standards, meaning they will require no extra energy ([link](#)). Another is that the lower development densities at the fringes of Ontario's urban areas could make possible the use of ground-source heat pumps. Accordingly, 70% penetration in 2050 may be a reasonable target.

the current strategy.⁴⁶ Such electrification would likely be achieved through use of heat pumps, even though present plans for expansion of Ontario's electricity system would not provide for sufficient capacity.⁴⁷

Relevant Ontario laws and regulations

Unless new Ontario legislation exempted developers of DES from particular requirements, the development and maintenance of DES would require regard for the Ontario laws briefly described below, and associated regulations. These would apply whatever the developer: one or more crown corporations as described above, municipalities and their enterprises, or entities wholly in the private sector

Energy Board Act: This sets out the way in which the Ontario Energy Board (OEB) regulates the natural gas and energy sectors and thus may affect DES to the extent these fuels are used.⁴⁸ Furthermore, DES may be affected by sections of this *Act* concerning energy distribution systems and natural monopolies. (Also see the *Electricity Act* below.)

Building Code Act: Through the *2024 Ontario Building Code* (OBC), this *Act* sets out how buildings should be constructed and maintained in Ontario.⁴⁹ It likely has little direct impact on district energy – only on the buildings facilitating a thermal network – but a potentially large indirect effect, through its effects on the energy use in new buildings served by such networks, or on buildings undergoing renovation. The Ontario Association of Architects noted in 2018 that “Ontario continues to promote some of the most progressive regulations in North America for improvements in energy conservation in buildings and reductions of GHG emissions. With each iteration of the OBC, the requirements related to energy performance have increased.” This trend

⁴⁶ During 2025, the Ontario government plans to release the province's first “Integrated Energy Plan with a generational horizon out to 2050, to ensure the energy sector is aligned behind the government's pro-growth agenda to reduce costs and province-wide emissions.” An interim document, *Ontario's Affordable Energy Future: The Pressing Case for More Power*, outlines “the challenges facing the province as demand for energy continues to rapidly grow, as well as the province's path to managing this demand.” ([link](#)) The interim document makes no mention of greenhouse gases or the need to avoid adverse climate change. This is consistent with an earlier statement by the province's Auditor-General that “climate change and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions is not yet a cross-government priority” ([link](#)) The interim document leaves the impression that natural gas will still be used until 2050 and perhaps beyond, with reductions in use resulting from some electrification of space heating.

⁴⁷ Ontario's Independent Electricity System Operator (IESO) appears to have projected that by 2050 less than 10% of dwellings will be served by heat pumps (see [link](#)). This is consistent with IESO's projection that peak use of electricity will grow by 50% ([link](#)) coupled with the Boltzmann Institute's projection that replacing natural gas heating with heat pumps could raise peak demand by more than 300% ([link](#)).

⁴⁸ For the mission and mandate of the Ontario Energy Board, see [link](#). For the *Energy Board Act*, see [link](#). In 2012, the Association of Municipalities of Ontario (AMO), in its submission to the *Ontario Distribution Sector Panel*, “recommended that the *Ontario Energy Board Act 1998* be amended to allow for rate-regulated district energy utilities, which presumably would have monopoly franchises.” ([link](#)) Since then, AMO has focused more on decarbonization generally rather than on building decarbonization through district energy deployment in particular (e.g., [link](#)).

⁴⁹ For the *Building Code Act*, see [link](#). For information about Ontario's Building Code, see [link](#) and [link](#).

seems to have ceased with the 2024 OBC. Although it has some 2,400 changes from its 2012 predecessor, none of these is to do with energy efficiency requirements.⁵⁰ DES are not mentioned in the OBC, although some of what is covered – e.g., requirements concerning the penetration of water pipes through fire separations, revised in the 2024 OBC – could be relevant to the deployment and maintenance of DES.

Environmental Assessment Act: This provides a regulatory framework to ensure that projects with potential environmental impacts undergo appropriate scrutiny before approval. The *Act* defines “environment” to include natural, social, cultural, built, and economic components.⁵¹ District energy projects are usually subject to the Municipal Class Environmental Assessment (MCEA) process.⁵²

Electricity Act: This sets out how municipal corporations may be involved in electricity generation and distribution.⁵³ The *Act* also provides the Ontario government – specifically the Minister of Energy and Mines – with the authority to produce an integrated energy plan for the province, and to issue directives to the Independent Electricity System Operator (IESO) and OEB concerning the implementation of the plan. Despite the name of the *Act*, and the *Act*’s general preoccupation with electricity, such an integrated energy plan may include goals and objectives respecting the role of all “energy resources, as well as energy efficiency, storage, and demand management, in building a clean energy economy.”⁵⁴ In October 2024, the Ontario government released a vision paper⁵⁵ to guide development of the province’s first Integrated Energy Resource Plan (IERP), due to be issued in 2025.

⁵⁰ The Ontario Association of Architects’ quotation is at [link](#). The observation that none of the changes in the 2024 OBC concern energy efficiency is at [link](#).

⁵¹ For Ontario’s *Environmental Assessment Act*, see [link](#). For information about environmental assessments see [link](#).

⁵² For descriptions of the MCEA process see [link](#) and [link](#). For a presentation on the MCEA process required for the 2020 expansion of Toronto’s Deep Lake Water Cooling system, see [link](#). For an indication that the 2024 streamlining of the MCEA does not apply to district energy projects, see [link](#).

⁵³ For Ontario’s *Electricity Act*, see. Section 144 of the *Act* requires that any generation or distribution of electricity must not be done directly by a municipality except through “a corporation incorporated under the *Business Corporations Act*.” The *Act* makes an exception for “a renewable generation facility that does not exceed 10 megawatts.”

⁵⁴ The quotation is from Section 25.29 (2)(b) of the *Electricity Act* at [link](#). Sections 25.29 and 25.30 of the *Act* concern integrated energy plans and their implementation. If Ontario municipalities were to be given a statutory role in planning for space heating (see Section 10 of the present report), this could be achieved through appropriate amendments to Sections 25.29 and 25.30 of the *Act*.

⁵⁵ There’s a comment on the vision paper in Note 46. As well as no mention in that paper of GHGs and the need to avoid adverse climate change, there is also no mention of district energy or of any energy source other than electricity and natural gas. The vision document does, however, speak to “planning for all sources of energy.” During the consultation period, Boltzmann Institute directors attempted to redress these omissions, with some focus on avoiding meltdown of the electrical system and protection of low-income households through deployment of DES.

Energy Consumer Protection Act: This sets rules that apply to how customers of DES can be recruited. It prevents, for example, automatic renewal of contracts and signing-up during door-to-door visits.⁵⁶

As well as the above, there is relevant Ontario legislation directed particularly or mostly at municipalities, including:

Planning Act:⁵⁷ This sets out how Ontario's municipalities – albeit with much detailed provincial oversight⁵⁸ – can shape land use and development within their boundaries. This *Act* allows a municipality to plan for development density and form creating the energy demand density and diversity required for feasible DES. More directly, municipalities can include policies favouring DES in its Official Plans and can take steps towards deployment of DES in site-specific development agreements with developers – short of actually requiring connection to an available DES. The *Planning Act* is the most important of more than 50 Ontario statutes that can affect land use in Ontario.⁵⁹

Municipal Franchises Act: This sets out how a municipality may allow a public utility to use its streets and other public lands for laying pipes, etc. The current definition of public utility in the *Act* includes only natural gas and other combustible gases but could readily be amended to include DES piping networks.⁶⁰

Municipal Act: This is the basic rulebook for all but one of Ontario's 444 municipalities.⁶¹ Toronto has its own basic rulebook, the *City of Toronto Act*,⁶² which gives it broad authority to pass by-laws in several areas, including some relevant to the establishment and maintenance of DES. These include by-laws concerning the environment and health, how services can be provided by the City. Like all municipal actions, such by-laws can be overruled by the Ontario government or legislature; examples are given here in Note 37. Other Ontario municipalities may have special legislation on specific matters: for example, the *Town of Moosonee Act* overrides some of the *Municipal Act* as it would apply to that municipality.⁶³

⁵⁶ Ontario's *Energy Consumer Protection Act* is at [link](#). Further information from the OEB is at [link](#).

⁵⁷ Ontario's *Planning Act* is at [link](#), with detailed information at [link](#).

⁵⁸ There are basically five ways in which the Ontario government can shape or override municipal planning: (i) plans must be consistent with stated Ontario government policies and plans, particularly with Provincial Planning Statements issued under Section 3 of the *Act*; (ii) plans must usually be approved by the relevant minister (of Municipal Affairs and Housing); (iii) Ministerial Zoning Orders overriding plans may be issued – often but not always at the request of a municipality; (iv) legislation overriding plans may be passed; (v) by influencing the Ontario Land Tribunal (OLT) which adjudicates appeals of zoning and other land-use decisions by municipal councils. (The OLT is notionally independent but undoubtedly influenced by provincial priorities.)

⁵⁹ According to the Ontario Auditor-General's 2024 report on the OLT ([link](#); and see Note 58), the OLT's mandate encompasses being the appeal body in respect of over 50 Ontario statutes, as well as the *Ontario Land Tribunal Act* ([link](#)).

⁶⁰ The *Municipal Franchises Act* is at [link](#).

⁶¹ The *Municipal Act* is at [link](#). A brief account of its context is at [link](#).

⁶² The *City of Toronto Act* is at [link](#). A fairly complete description is at the City of Toronto's website at [link](#).

⁶³ The *Town of Moosonee Act* is at [link](#).

Toronto District Heating Corporation Act: This brought together five steam-based district heating systems in downtown Toronto in the early 1980s.⁶⁴ Four were brought under TDHC's management together with interconnections and related infrastructure completed by the City of Toronto in the 1970s. The four were systems serving (i) several hospitals, (ii) the provincial government's Queen's Park complex, (iii) the railway companies' and other buildings at and near Union Station, and (iv) a commercial system owned and operated by Toronto Hydro. The University of Toronto's system remained connected but managed separately. The original *Act* and corporation — now Enwave Energy Corporation — have undergone major changes since then: to accommodate part ownership by a pension fund and then full ownership by the private sector, and to provide district cooling as well as district heating. (Also see Note 33.)

9.4. Municipal Activity

DES in Ontario

This part will set out what a municipality could do, considering the foregoing, to establish and maintain one or more *commercially active* DES within its boundaries, alone or in cooperation with another public entity or a business corporation. It will also discuss how such establishment and maintenance might be funded. It begins with a review of how some of Ontario's existing systems are and have been structured, excluding the especially complex case of the TDHC described in the previous paragraph. All the DES described in what follows operate within the various Ontario statutes noted above. None has required special legislation such as the *Toronto District Heating Corporation Act*.

Eleven corporations operating commercial DES systems in Ontario are briefly described below. The first five (in Markham, Hamilton, Oshawa, the Regent Park area of Toronto, and North Bay,) are municipally owned, albeit with complex ownership structures, and in one case — Regent Park — partially in private ownership at its inception. The next two (in Sudbury and Ottawa-Gatineau) are equally owned by the municipality and a private-sector entity. The next three (in Windsor, Guelph, and Cornwall) were originally established by the municipality but are now wholly under private-sector ownership. The final DES, in London, which dates back to the nineteenth century, seems always to have been in the private sector, but the earliest records of it appear to be unavailable.

Markham District Energy (MDE) was established by the City of Markham in 1999 as a wholly owned subsidiary of **Markham Energy Corporation**, owned in turn by the City.⁶⁵ MDE was created taking advantage of Sections 10 and 11 of the *Municipal Act*, which allow municipalities to deliver services they deem necessary or desirable for their communities. This includes establishing a public utility delivering energy other than electricity. MDE's two DES serve or are to serve a total

⁶⁴ The *Toronto District Heating Corporation Act*, at [link](#), appears to be still in force although no longer evidently operative. The legal evolution of the crown corporation, TDHC, to the private-sector entity, Enwave Energy Corporation can be followed through [link](#), [link](#), and [link](#).

⁶⁵ MDE's website is at [link](#). Markham Energy Corporation became Markham Enterprises Corporation in 2015 (see [link](#)).

of 1.2 million square metres of floor residential, commercial, and institutional floor space about a quarter of which is under construction.⁶⁶

Another municipally owned DES is the one owned and operated by **Hamilton Community Enterprises** (HCE), a subsidiary of **Hamilton Enterprises Holding Corporation** (HEHC, [link](#)), which is wholly owned by the City of Hamilton. HCE provides district heating and cooling to some 230,000 square metres of residential, commercial and institutional floor space in downtown Hamilton.⁶⁷

EnerFORGE is the operating name of **Oshawa PUC Energy Services**, a wholly owned subsidiary of **Oshawa Power and Utilities Corporation** (usually known as Oshawa Power), which is wholly owned by the City of Oshawa. EnerFORGE owns and operates a 24 MW cogeneration plant supplying heat and electricity to Durham College and University of Ontario Institute of Technology. It also operates the DES in Toronto's Regent Park, described next. With equity partner, **Ottawa Renewable Energy Co-operative**, EnerFORGE recently acquired a portfolio of renewable energy assets in Bruce and Huron counties, some 250 kilometres west of Oshawa.⁶⁸

The DES serving the large Regent Park development in Toronto is owned by **Regent Park Energy Inc.** (RPEI), a wholly owned subsidiary of **Toronto Community Housing Enterprises**, itself a subsidiary of the **Toronto Community Housing Corporation** (TCHC), owned by the City of Toronto. EnerFORGE (owned by the City of Oshawa, see above) operates the system for RPEI, which provides heating, cooling and hot water to 20 buildings – to be expanded to 50 – in what was Canada's largest public housing development, undergoing redevelopment as mix of public and private housing. In 2005, TCHC partnered with Corix Utilities to develop, own, and manage the system, sharing equity 60%/40%, but in 2012 TCHC bought Corix's share and remains the sole owner.⁶⁹

The **Community Energy Park** in North Bay is a DES owned by **North Bay Hydro Services Inc.**, in turn owned by **North Bay Hydro Holdings Ltd.**, which is wholly owned by the City of North Bay. The DES serves a set of unrelated institutional buildings with electricity and hot water from a cogeneration facility and solar panels.⁷⁰

Sudbury District Energy Corporation is a public-private partnership established in 1998 and involving the City of Greater Sudbury, **Greater Sudbury Utilities** (which is owned by the City), and

⁶⁶ MDE operates three combined heat and power (CHP) plants, Warden, Birchmount, and Bur Oak, providing respectively 5.2, 2.6 and 3.25 MW of electrical output and 12, 10, and 3.75 MW of thermal output (see [link](#)).

⁶⁷ For HCE and its district energy, see [link](#) and [link](#). For Hamilton Enterprises Holding Corporation, see [link](#). For the City of Hamilton, see [link](#).

⁶⁸ For the activities and ownership arrangements of EnerFORGE, see [link](#). For the Ottawa Renewable Energy Co-operative (OREC), a for-profit corporation, see [link](#). For the announcement concerning the purchase of assets from Oshawa, see [link](#).

⁶⁹ For the Regent Park redevelopment, see [link](#). For EnerFORGE's role, see [link](#). For Toronto Community Housing Corporation (TCHC), see [link](#). For the original arrangement between TCHC and Corix Utilities, see [link](#).

⁷⁰ For North Bay's DES see [link](#) and [link](#).

Toromont Power Systems, which has a 50% equity stake in this DES. The system provides heating cooling and electricity to several buildings in Sudbury's downtown core and beyond.⁷¹

The **Zibi Community Utility District Energy System** in Ottawa is an equal partnership between **Hydro Ottawa Holding Inc.**, owned by the City of Ottawa, and Zibi Canada, a private-sector entity responsible for management and development of the Zibi community, a 14-hectare development on both the Quebec and the Ontario banks of the Ottawa River.⁷² Zibi is an Anishinaabe word for river. The evolving Zibi community has been described as the region's "first zero-carbon emission community," in part due to waste heat recovery from the nearby Kruger paper plant exploited by the Zibi DES, which also uses the Ottawa River for cooling. At the end of 2024, the development was about one third completed with nine commercial and residential buildings occupied, all served by the expanding Zibi DES.⁷³

District Energy Windsor was sold to **Enwave Windsor Holdings LP** in 2021 by **ENWIN Utilities Ltd**, owned by the **Windsor Utilities Commission**, in turn owned by the City of Windsor. This DES provides cooling and heating services to Casino Windsor as well as government and commercial buildings in Windsor's downtown.⁷⁴

The DES in Guelph, Ontario, began operation as the **Galt District Energy System** in 2013, developed, owned and managed by **Envida Community Energy**, a subsidiary of **Guelph Hydro Inc.**, then owned by the City of Guelph. Guelph Hydro became part of **Alectra Utilities** in 2019, owned by several municipalities. The DES, which cost \$8.1 million to develop in 2013 was sold by **Guelph Municipal Holdings Inc.** in 2022 to private-sector **Cascara Energy** for \$8. This company continues to operate the system – which provides heating and cooling to a cultural centre and commercial and residential buildings from a thermal plant – with plans for expansion.⁷⁵

CDH District Heating Limited, the DES in Cornwall, began operation in 1995. It is a subsidiary of **Cornwall Street Railway Light and Power Company Limited** – known as Cornwall Electric – in turn a subsidiary of Fortis Ontario Inc., headquartered in Fort Erie, Ontario, which had purchased the company from **Enbridge Energy distribution Inc.** in 2002. The City of Cornwall owned Cornwall Electric from 1977 to 1998, across the period of development and commissioning of the DES. Dating from 1887, Cornwall Electric is one of the oldest electricity distribution companies in Canada. Most of its electricity comes from Quebec. It operates a small cogeneration system, providing hot water for the DES – in 1995 the first in Canada to serve a commercial district heating system, a year ahead of London. The system feeds 5 MW megawatts of electricity into the local

⁷¹ For Sudbury's DES, see [link](#).

⁷² For Zibi Canada, see [link](#). For Hydro Ottawa Holding Inc., see [link](#).

⁷³ For information about the Zibi DES, including a video, see [link](#). For the end-of-2024 report on the Zibi community, see [link](#).

⁷⁴ For information about the Windsor DES, see Enwave's website at [link](#), and also [link](#).

⁷⁵ For the initial development of the Galt DES, including its cost, see [link](#). For the sale of the DES to Cascara Energy, see [link](#). For information about Cascara Energy, see [link](#) and its website at [link](#). For what Cascara Energy paid for the DES, see [link](#). For the absorption of Guelph Hydro by Alectra Utilities, see [link](#).

grid and provides 7 MW of heat to city buildings, schools, and a hospital via a 4.5-kilometre underground distribution network.⁷⁶

London District Energy LP operates under the name **London District Energy GP Inc.** It is wholly owned by **Enwave Energy Corporation**, which in turn is equally owned by **Ontario Teachers' Pension Plan** and a group of Australian pension funds. As noted above, this steam-based system appears to be one of the oldest continuously active DES in the world, perhaps always owned and operated in the private sector. One of the system's three steam lines is to be closed during 2025, as being too old to operate feasibly, withdrawing service to 17 of the system's 60 customers. The long-term reliability of the other two lines is under review.⁷⁷

As well as the above existing commercial DES, some of which are expanding, there are several that have been investigated or planned, or are under development. Notable are Enwave's DES to serve the massive **Lakeview Village** development on the Mississauga side of its border with Toronto at Lake Ontario and Northcrest's plans for a DES to serve the even larger proposed development at the site of the **former Downsview Airport**. As well as these two private-sector ventures — which must of course work closely with their respective municipalities — district energy is being or has recently been investigated by or for several Ontario municipalities, including — perhaps among others — Burlington, Clarington, Kitchener, Oakville, Mississauga (City Centre), Richmond Hill, and Thunder Bay.⁷⁸

Municipal legal capacity

The above brief survey suggests that there is nothing in existing Ontario legislation that prevents a municipality or one of the corporations it owns from developing a DES, alone or in partnership with a private-sector entity. Moreover, a DES established as a public-private partnership can become wholly municipally owned (as in the case of the Regent Park system) or wholly private-sector owned (as in the case of Guelph's system).

The ability of Ontario municipalities to enter into partnerships concerning DES may be attributable to the conferring of “natural person” powers to municipalities by an amendment to the *Municipal Act* that came into effect in 2003. Section 9 provides that “a municipality has the capacity, rights, powers and privileges of a natural person for the purpose of exercising its authority under this or any other Act.” This means that, subject to exceptions in Section 17 of the *Act* and elsewhere, mostly concerning financial matters (see below), municipalities have the legal capacity, rights, powers, and privileges akin to those of individuals and corporations.⁷⁹ However, Ontario municipalities may be subject to an unusual degree of provincial counteracting of their decisions, as briefly reviewed in Note 37. Such lack of stability of function could deter potential partners.

⁷⁶ For more information about Cornwall's DES, see [link](#). For the fascinating history of Cornwall Electric, see [link](#).

⁷⁷ For the history and current predicament of London District Energy, see [link](#) and [link](#).

⁷⁸ For the Lakeview Village and Downsview Airport proposals see [link](#) and [link](#). For the municipal explorations mentioned in this paragraph see the following: Burlington ([link](#)), Clarington ([link](#)), Kitchener ([link](#)), Oakville ([link](#)), Mississauga City Centre ([link](#)), Richmond Hill ([link](#)), and Thunder Bay ([link](#)).

⁷⁹ See Note 61 and the paper prepared for the Ontario Municipal Administrators Association at [link](#).

Constraints on municipal action

It's mostly financial matters that limit a municipality intent on establishing a DES, although there can be other restrictions such as the already noted limit of 10 MW on the size of municipally owned plants that generate electricity. Municipal-private partnerships may not have this limit but may require approval from the Ontario Energy Board.

Regulation of DES

DES are essentially unregulated utilities in Ontario, and the question is raised as to whether DES would benefit from regulation of price, performance, and other matters, as electricity and natural gas are regulated in Ontario (by the Ontario Energy Board) as DES are in British Columbia.⁸⁰ It may be instructive to look at Denmark and Sweden, both of which have widespread deployment of apparently successful DES, even though DES in Denmark are highly regulated and those in Sweden are much less regulated, particularly with respect to price.

In Denmark, DES are required by law to be non-profit entities (there are a few minor exceptions). Over 80% of the 354 systems are consumer cooperatives. The remainder are municipal utilities. (Each type has roughly half the total heating share; municipal systems are larger.) Return on capital is limited, but DES can secure 100% funding at low interest rates for periods of up to 25 years. Municipalities may require connection and prohibit disconnection. Electrified heating is banned in new housing. Energy providers and trunk transmission facilities may include private equity.⁸¹

Almost 80% of the 180 Swedish DES are municipally owned, with an increasing amount of private-sector investment in these DES. There is little public financing support. Price and profit are unregulated, with no municipal or other authority to compel connection or prevent disconnection. The marketplace prevails with the main government intervention being adjudication of disputes between companies and customers.⁸²

In spite of their contrasting systems, Sweden and Denmark are the two EU countries having made the most progress towards net-zero greenhouse gas emissions from energy use in buildings. Sweden made slightly more progress between 2005 and 2022 – with a reduction by about 68% compared with 64% for Denmark – but Denmark could well make the most progress by 2030, with expected reductions from 2022 of 93% vs. 86%.⁸³ Thus, what may be more relevant is overall cultural context and geography rather than the particulars of DES regulation.

⁸⁰ For a discussion of DES regulation in Ontario and B.C., see [link](#).

⁸¹ For Danish DES, see [link](#).

⁸² For Swedish DES, see [link](#).

⁸³ For actual and expected reductions in greenhouse gases by Denmark and Sweden, see [link](#).

9.5. Funding DES

Funding from municipal and other governmental sources

The limitations on municipal borrowing and investment are too complex to be set out in detail here. In general, municipalities may not incur debt service costs or other such liabilities that exceed 25% of their own-source revenue (mostly property taxes and user fees), a limit known as the Annual Repayment Limit (ARL). Municipalities may borrow only for capital expenditures, which could include DES infrastructure. The Ontario Land Tribunal (see above and Notes 58 and 59) may grant exemptions. To avoid debt service charges, municipalities have tended recently to fund infrastructure with development charges, adding to the costs and complexity of infrastructure funding.⁸⁴

Both municipalities and municipally owned corporations – but not municipal-private partnerships – may borrow with advantageous terms from the Ontario Infrastructure and Lands Corporation (OILC), often known as Infrastructure Ontario, for most capital spending on infrastructure including spending on DES. The terms include low interest rates, repayment periods of up to 30 years, and other features as may be negotiated. A municipally owned corporation is not subject to the ARL. Its municipal owner may be if it guarantees a loan to the owned corporation from OILC or from another source.⁸⁵ The arrangements and requirements set out here and above go far towards explaining the often-complex corporate structures of municipal corporations.

Funding of Markham District Energy Inc.

Rather than go into details about other funding sources, it may be more useful at this point to illustrate how one municipality's DES have been supported — without funding from OILC. Markham District Energy (MDE), structured as indicated above, owns and operates two DES. The project cost for establishing MDE, which began operations in 2000, was \$11 million, of which about half came from the City of Markham and half from the Federation of Canadian Municipalities' Green Municipal Fund (GMF) — a \$1.5 million grant and a \$4 million loan. In 2022, the Canadian Infrastructure Bank (CIB) invested \$135 million in MDE, matched by an equal loan by the bank CIBC.⁸⁶ In 2024, MDE received a further \$8.2 million from GMF, which included a \$1 million grant.

Further federal investments were made in 2024: \$16.7 million from the Low Carbon Economy fund and support for a “contract for difference” (CfD) by the Canada Growth Fund. The CfD

⁸⁴ For the Ontario government's position on municipal debt, see [link](#). For a useful article on the relative merits of municipal debt and development charges, see [link](#).

⁸⁵ For OILC loan guidelines for municipalities and their corporations, see [link](#).

⁸⁶ Three CIB rules appear to be that (i) it supports only revenue-generating projects (i.e., not planning exercises); (ii) that private capital must be involved (e.g., the CIBC loan in the case of Markham DE); and (iii) it does not lend money to municipal corporations – i.e., directly to municipalities – but does lend to business corporations owned by municipalities (e.g., Markham DE).

protects MDE against falls in the industrial carbon strike price.⁸⁷ Meanwhile, since the inception of MDE, the City of Markham has, from its own resources, provided strategic planning for MDE and other services.

Private-sector funding

CIBC's loan to MDE is Ontario's most substantial example of private-sector investment in a municipally owned DES other than the unusual case of TDHC, now Enwave, for which the evolution to a private partnership was facilitated by special provincial legislation (see above). The case of TDHC-Enwave is instructive because it illustrates the financial challenges of DES and what may be its attraction to an investor.

TDHC was established as government entity in the early 1980s with an initial investment by governments, chiefly the then City of Toronto, of under \$100 million. By the time of the sale by Brookfield to pension funds in 2021, what was TDHC's DES – now expanded, chiefly with the addition of cooling services – appears to have been worth more than \$2.0 billion.⁸⁸

Patient capital is required. Once a DES is established and is providing consistent returns regardless of economic cycles, it can be an attractive investment. Thus, in Sweden, where most DES began as municipal corporations, there has been significant privatization as municipalities seek to generate substantial revenue.⁸⁹ However, in Germany, municipal governments have bought previously privatized systems to ensure better compliance with net-zero and other environmental policies.⁹⁰

Two pre-conditions for adequate private-sector investment in a DES and thus its development and expansion could be: (i) cooperation from each municipality in which the DES is located, not the least because piping could need to be laid in municipal road allowances and other rights-of way; and (ii) requirements to make use of a DES where available, to secure a revenue stream. The first of these can be particularly important when a DES is to serve existing buildings, or new buildings on existing streets. Serving existing buildings may present the most challenges

⁸⁷ For the history of Markham's two DES, see [link](#). For the investment by the CIB and CIBC, see [link](#). For the Federation of Canadian Municipalities' GMF, see [link](#). For the Low Carbon Economy Fund, see [link](#). For the Canada Growth Fund and its CfD, see [link](#). (The value of a CfD to a DES could be that its energy charges are tied to customers' avoided cost of gas, to drop if carbon levies are removed. In that event, the CfD indemnifies the DES by restoring its revenue to what it would have been. Conversely, if carbon levies cause the price of gas to go above the strike price, the DES must return some of the increased revenue to the Canada Growth Fund. The aim is to protect the finances of the DES, thereby making it more attractive to investors.)

⁸⁸ The Canadian portion of Enwave – chiefly its Toronto facility – was sold by Brookfield for about C\$2.8 billion, 50% to Teachers Pension Plan and 50% to IFM Investors, an Australian company investing on behalf of >700 institutions worldwide ([link](#)). The U.S. portion of Enwave was sold separately to U.S. and Australian interests. In respect of the sales of both parts of Enwave, Brookfield was reported as claiming that its net proceeds were US\$1 billion and it had earned an internal rate of return or over 30% on its investment since purchasing Enwave in 2012 and “a multiple of invested capital of over six times” ([link](#))

⁸⁹ For what has been happening to DES in Sweden, see [link](#) and [link](#).

⁹⁰ For the trend to remunicipalization of DES in Germany, see [link](#).

for implementation of the second pre-condition – mandatory connection to DES (see below) – because owners may lose the opportunity to choose how their buildings are heated and cooled.

The City of Richmond's Lulu Island Energy Company (LIEC)

As well as the above Ontario DES funding arrangements, one from British Columbia – where municipalities appear to have more legislative and fiscal flexibility – may be instructive. Richmond wholly owns LIEC, which is developing district energy systems in several of its neighbourhoods. LIEC, in turn, has signed a 30-year concession agreement with an arm of Corix Utilities Canada (Corix), a private-sector district energy system developer. System build-out is supported by debt financing from the CIB and private-sector lenders while, in parallel, Corix provides equity financing. Business arrangements provide that Corix will earn a target return on its equity investment; this target return is benchmarked to the regulated returns established for other utility companies in B.C. (typically 8-10%).⁹¹

In the early years of DES development, revenues are not sufficient to cover costs, which are defined to include Corix's target equity return. Accordingly, excess costs are in a deferral account, which accrues interest, and the associated balances are forecast to be recovered in later years as DES revenues grow. The expectation is that costs in the deferral account will be recovered over a 10 to 20 year period. If the deferral account has not been drawn down by the end of Corix's 30-year concession agreement, the City must compensate Corix for unrecovered costs. Thus, the City lays an important role in back-stopping Corix's investment and associated debt financing. In addition to guaranteeing that Corix can earn its return, the City mandates that new developments connect to the DE system, which minimizes risks related to market growth.

Corix has developed other DE systems under similar terms in co-operation with local development agencies in other jurisdictions. A common feature of these developments is that DES connection is mandated either through bylaw or as part of land sale agreements.

Mandatory connection to DES

In Ontario, existing municipal powers under the *Municipal Act* provide substantial authority for requiring connection of new development to DES. There seem to be three areas of uncertainty as to the extent of these powers: (i) whether they extend to existing buildings or only to new development or redevelopment; (ii) whether they extend to requiring *use* of DES services or merely to requiring the ability to connect to DES services; and (iii) whether they extend to privately owned DES or only to municipally owned DES. Clarification is needed in the legislation or its interpretation. In the meantime, for new development or substantial redevelopment, municipalities can achieve more certainty concerning district energy readiness and use by appropriate statements in official plans and zoning by-laws and, above all, by making them a feature of development agreements with landowners.⁹²

⁹¹ This summary of LIEC's business arrangements is based on discussions with representatives of Corix and reviews of LIEC's financial statements and supporting municipal bylaws.

⁹² For municipal development agreements, see [link](#) and [link](#).

Canadian municipalities in which connection is mandatory for new buildings include the Cogswell DES in Halifax, the Southeast False Creek DES in Vancouver, and the Metrotown and Edmonds DES in Burnaby.⁹³ In Scandinavia, municipalities are mostly empowered to enact mandatory connection in zones they designate. Mandatory connection for existing buildings usually applies only when they are renovated, or their heating systems are replaced. Moreover, exemptions can be granted when connection costs are high (>15% of a building's value) or alternative systems are accepted as achieving lower carbon emissions. A patchwork of incentives offsetting connection costs is available. Other European countries are moving towards mandatory connection, as DES become a favoured method of space heating and cooling.

There's growing concern in the European Union about mandated connection on account of the monopolistic nature of district energy, particularly when a DES is controlled by the private sector. Thus, there could be a paradox: private-sector DES may need non-governmental investment more but may be less able to secure it because of resistance to their having the power to require connection.⁹⁴

The UK's *Energy Act 2023* introduced mandated connection requirements to DES in zones designated by the national government. Municipalities act as zone coordinators for heat network zones with authority to require connections by all new buildings, existing individual public-sector and non-residential buildings with annual thermal energy use of 100 MWh or more, and residential buildings already connected to a DES (thereby preventing withdrawal). Based on this legislation, a Heat Network Zoning Pilot Program is being conducted in 28 cities and towns in England. The aim is to facilitate investment risk by ensuring demand.⁹⁵

Funding DES in China

China may have the world's largest district heating market, reported as having over 200,000 kilometres of thermal networks supplying almost 9 billion square metres of building floor area.⁹⁶ Much of the investment in DES comes from government sources, notably the State Power

⁹³ Mandatory connection to the Cogswell DES was made possible by in 2017 when the Nova Scotia legislature amended the Halifax Regional Municipality Charter accordingly ([link](#)). British Columbia municipalities have been empowered to require connection to DES since 2003 ([link](#)). For the DES mentioned here see [link](#) and [link](#). Whether existing buildings within these DES boundaries are being required to connect is unclear.

⁹⁴ For a Eurocentric discussion of mandated connection and other DES matters, see [link](#).

⁹⁵ For information about the UK's *Energy Act 2023*, see [link](#) and [link](#).

⁹⁶ For the extent of China's DES, see ([link](#)). The European Union appears to have thermal networks totalling about 150,000 kilometres serving about 70 million people ([link](#)). The amount of floor space served is unclear, but the known average of 34 square metres of residential floor space per person ([link](#)), suggests that some 2.4 billion square metres of floor space is served, or 3.6 billion if it is assumed that a third of district energy serves non-residential buildings ([link](#)). These figures suggest that, compared with the EU, each kilometre of China's network serves on average more than twice the amount of floor space – a difference that may deserve further examination.

Development Corporation (particularly for CHP, including nuclear CHP), the China Development Bank, and the Export-Import Bank.⁹⁷

Perhaps excepting projects using nuclear heat, there seems to be a strong role for public-private partnerships in China. An example is the City of Zhangjiakou in Hebei province, next to Beijing, population about 4.2 million. After a competitive bidding process, the inefficient state-owned district heating company was replaced by the private-sector Beijing Yuantong Heat Company Limited (BYHC), in an arrangement that gives 90% of the equity of the City's DES to BYHC and 10% to the municipality for period of 25 years.⁹⁸

Funding DES in the European Union

There are some 10,000 DES in the EU each serving an average of about 7,000 residents. The largest is in Bucharest, Romania, serving 1.2 million residents (followed by the integrated system of Greater Copenhagen, serving about one million residents). Bucharest's DES had deteriorated and was the recipient of a grant from EU funds, equivalent to about C\$400 million. The grant was considered necessary both for the DES to be consistent with the EU directive favouring district energy and to ensure the financial viability of the DES. Most DES in the EU are very small, the smallest perhaps being that of Fons Denmark, a cooperative serving 47 of the 79 households in the village.⁹⁹

A generous grant, such as made to Bucharest's DES, is illustrative of generous EU funding for DES, particularly those in Central and Eastern Europe.¹⁰⁰ National programs can also be generous, but more often have a substantial low-interest loan component. An example is Germany's Wärmewende Program. It distributes the equivalent of about C\$4.5 billion annually to municipalities to expand climate-neutral DES, combining 40% grants with loans bearing 0.5% interest.¹⁰¹

Public-private partnerships have become a strong feature of DES in the EU, with a large variety of arrangements according to member country. However, the German city-states of Hamburg and Berlin have repossessed their DES from the private sector. In The Netherlands, where most DES are in private-sector hands, there's consideration of a proposed law that would require majority ownership by a municipality or other public entity.¹⁰²

⁹⁷ For an overview of investment in district energy in China see [link](#) and [link](#). For the broader context of the role of financial institutions in Chinese climate policy, see [link](#).

⁹⁸ For a description of the complex public-private partnership arrangement for the DES in Zhangjiakou, China, see [link](#).

⁹⁹ For Bucharest's DES and the 2021 direct grant from EU funds equivalent to about C\$400 million, see [link](#). For the EU directive favouring district energy, see [link](#). For the Fons DES, see [link](#).

¹⁰⁰ EU funding programs for DES include Connecting Europe Facility Energy ([link](#)), Horizon Europe ([link](#)), and national programs funded chiefly by the EU, e.g., that for Croatia, which includes funds from the EU's Cohesion Program, its National Recovery and Resilience Plan, and the Modernization Fund ([link](#)).

¹⁰¹ Germany's Wärmewende program is described at [link](#) and [link](#).

¹⁰² For the purchase from Vattenfall of district energy systems in Berlin and Hamburg, see [link](#) and [link](#). For the progress of The Netherlands' *Collective Heat Supply Act*, see [link](#).

Funding DES in the UK

It may be particularly instructive to consider DES funding in the UK, because municipalities there are, if anything, even less autonomous and thus less able to direct their own affairs than municipalities in Ontario.¹⁰³ However, the UK government expresses strong support for municipal action in respect of DES, as part of a broad commitment to decarbonization. As noted above, it has taken the important step of allowing some municipalities to require connection to DES within their area.

Compared with what is available in the EU, only modest government funding of DES is available in the UK. The funding is more to plan and initiate DES to provide a basis for private-sector investment, or to help established DES seek private investment for rehabilitation and expansion. A confusing array of modest funding schemes is available, an example being the Green Heat Network Fund.¹⁰⁴ ([link](#)).

The paucity of government funding and lack of municipal resources has meant that public-private partnerships have become a cornerstone of district energy development in the UK. A pioneering partnership has been that of the City of Bristol. The partnership is and the program more generally are known as Bristol Leap. Bristol is a port city almost 200 kilometres due west of London, with a population of just under 500,000. Bristol is known for having abolished its executive mayor position in 2024 and for its Green Party being the strongest of any major British city (34 of 70 seats on the City Council).¹⁰⁵

The Bristol Leap partnership had been in development for several years and in effect since January 2023, the initiative of the previous, Labour-Party-led council, which also had strong Green Party representation. Here's the timeline:

- 2018 City Council declared a climate emergency; the city to be carbon neutral by 2030
- 2019 Bristol Leap concept adopted; worldwide search for a private partner began
- 2020 180 expressions of interest were received, including 52 from outside the UK
- 2021 Eight bidders were selected for detailed examination
- 2022 Negotiations conducted with Ameresco Inc., with Vattenfall AB as subcontractor
- 2022 Joint venture company established (JV Co.); 5-year business plan agreed

¹⁰³ Share of total tax revenue is a measure of the extent to which municipalities are beholden to other governments. In England, less than 10% of all taxes are raised by municipalities, with the remainder being raised by the national government ([link](#)). In Ontario, shares of total taxes collected raised by the 444 municipalities, the provincial government, and the federal government are roughly 16%, 28% and 56% ([link](#), [link](#)). In Sweden as in Canada, income tax is the main revenue source and almost the sole source for the City of Stockholm and Stockholm County (which is responsible for transit and health and includes 25 much smaller municipalities). Of income taxes collected in the City of Stockholm, roughly 50% are raised by the City, 30% by the County, and 20% by the national government. Only residents with incomes more than about C\$100,00 pay national income tax, whereas residents with incomes as low as about C\$5,000 pay at least a little in local income taxes. For information about Stockholm, see [link](#) and [link](#).

¹⁰⁴ For the UK's Green Heat Network Fund, see ([link](#)).

¹⁰⁵ The best, regularly updated source on the municipal and other politics of Bristol, UK is the relevant Wikipedia page at [link](#).

- 2023 First 20-year partnership commenced
- 2024 5-year private-sector funding raised from C\$900 million to C\$1.4 billion
- 2024 Vattenfall's status changed from subcontractor to equity partner.¹⁰⁶

The essentials of the partnership agreement are these:

- Capital commitment only from the private sector partner(s); nothing from the City
- JV Co., responsible for planning, organization, and delivery, owned 50-50 by city and partner(s)
- Bristol Leap involves numerous decarbonization initiatives, including renewable energy generation, energy efficiency upgrades and electric vehicle infrastructure. Consolidation and expansion of the Bristol Heat Network is the largest expenditure category, totalling about C\$550 million of the expected C\$1.4 billion investment during the first 5-year phase.¹⁰⁷
- Asset transfer of the current Bristol Heat Network at investment value to Vattenfall, who is to have full operational responsibility for the expanded network for 20 years (with what happens then to be determined during the final 5-year phase of the partnership)¹⁰⁸

Bearing on the above will be the beginning of statutory regulation of DES in the UK, from April 2025. The primary focus of the new regulations is consumer protection. Providing a stable and attractive environment for investors is a secondary focus.¹⁰⁹

Such is the attractiveness of the Bristol Leap model, the UK government is hoping to foster replication in 15 cities by 2030, with such public-private partnerships dominating the estimated C\$42 billion of investment required by then in DES in the UK. Sustained success would require addressing workforce gaps (an estimated 85,000 engineers needed) and stabilizing appropriate energy supplies.

9.6. Conclusion

A DES is usually initiated by a municipally owned corporation, or by one jointly owned by a municipality and a private sector entity, or by a private-sector entity cooperating closely with one or more municipalities. All these arrangements seem possible under existing Ontario law. The second case – joint public-private ownership – seems preferable because municipalities don't have the money or sufficient experienced staff.

A huge amount of investment would be needed to support the extent of DES deployment in Ontario required for net-zero attainment. Interest in the Bristol Leap model offers hope that, with proper planning, the required investment could become available. However, interest in providing such investment may happen only if the Ontario government were to provide a stable context for municipal DES development and deployment.

¹⁰⁶ For the timeline of the Bristol Leap initiative, 2018-2024, see [link](#), [link](#), and [link](#).

¹⁰⁷ For the share of the investment in the Bristol Leap initiative going to expansion of the Bristol Heat Network, see, [link](#).

¹⁰⁸ For details of the Bristol Heat Network and its transfer to Vattenfall, see [link](#) and [link](#)

¹⁰⁹ For details of the UK's Heat Networks (Market Framework) (Great Britain) Regulations 2025, see [link](#).

10. Municipal Roles; Thermal Energy Planning

Please note that in this Section 10 and the previous Section 9 all sources are indicated in footnotes. Each source is accessible through a live [link](#) in a footnote. Some of the sources are also in this report's Bibliography, but more are not.

First, this section touches lightly on the various ways a planned or operating district energy system (DES – meaning either the actual system or the operating company, singular or plural according to context) can interact with relevant municipal governments.¹¹⁰ From Section 9 and other places in this report, it may be clear that Ontario municipalities are unlikely to be directly owning and operating DES, although they may well own or partly own corporations that have ownership. In many respects, such corporations would be like any other business within the area of the municipalities they operate in. They would be subject to the particular rules and practices of those municipalities. In every case, these rules and practices will follow from municipal by-laws enacted pursuant to provincial statutes and regulations.¹¹¹

Second, this section discusses in more detail how municipalities may plan for deployment of DES and for their expansion. It notes what happened at a conference held on March 20, 2025, as part of the Boltzmann Institute's Two Pathways project. The event had the title "Should Ontario Municipalities be Required to Engage in Heating Planning." The definition used at the conference was this:

Heating planning involves estimating the average and peak thermal requirements (heating and cooling) of all current and anticipated future buildings in an area, identifying potential sources of thermal energy, and matching likely demand and potential supply in a comprehensive heating and cooling plan to be updated every five years."

Heating planning was used as a term preferable to the more commonly used *heat planning*, to avoid confusion with planning for hot weather. A better term, proposed by a conference participant, could be *thermal energy planning*, which is more precise and covers increasingly important space cooling as well as space heating. Thermal energy planning is used often in this section.

The 105 participants in the March 20 conference were composed thus: municipalities and their agencies, 25; private sector businesses, 21; university graduate students and faculty, 19; Boltzmann Institute, 8; environmental organizations, 7; provincial government and agencies, 4, European interests, 4; and unspecified others (described by a participant as "interested lay folks"), 17.

¹¹⁰ A DES may have to deal with more than one municipality because its networks extend into more than one, or because it is located in a place with a two-tier municipal structure, e.g., the DES in Markham is in both the City of Markham and the Region of York, both of which have municipal governments.

¹¹¹ For a lucid account of how Ontario municipalities function from legal and related perspectives, see the paper prepared for the Ontario Municipal Administrators Association at [link](#).

10.1. Municipal Roles other than Planning

Here's a check list of the matters, other than planning, about which an envisioned or operating DES may or will need to consider when interacting with its municipal government(s) — the provincial legislation that enables these municipal activities is described in Section 9:

- ❑ **Land Use and Zoning Approvals:** A DES must comply with the municipality's Official Plan (see below) and zoning by-laws. If the proposed facilities (e.g., energy centres, piping infrastructure) don't conform, the DES may need a zoning amendment or minor variance.
- ❑ **Site Plan Approval:** New developments typically require site plan approval under the *Planning Act*, ensuring that infrastructure meets design, environmental, and compatibility standards.
- ❑ **Building Permits:** Construction of physical infrastructure must comply with the *Ontario Building Code* and local building by-laws, requiring permits from the municipality.
- ❑ **Encroachment Permits:** Installation of distribution piping in municipal rights-of-way (e.g., under roads or sidewalks) requires encroachment agreements or permits. These agreements often come with fees, construction standards, and restoration obligations.
- ❑ **Franchise Agreements**, pursuant to the *Municipal Franchises Act*, and **Municipal Access Agreements** are alternatives to encroachment permits.
- ❑ **Noise By-Laws:** Regulating operational noise from plants or construction activity.
- ❑ **Traffic and Construction By-Laws:** Governing road closures, construction times, and traffic impacts.
- ❑ **Environmental Regulations:** While primarily under provincial jurisdiction, municipalities may have additional environmental expectations (e.g., air quality standards, idling rules).
- ❑ **Development Charges and Agreements:** DES are more likely to be the beneficiaries of such charges and agreements negotiated as part of development approvals, but they could constrain DES.
- ❑ **Sustainable Design Guidelines:** Again, DES are likely to be beneficiaries of such development guidelines but may also be constrained by them.

10.2. Existing Municipal Planning Roles

Official Plans and Secondary Plans

Ontario municipalities are required by the *Planning Act* to adopt Official Plans that are consistent with the current Provincial Planning Statement. An Official Plan sets out the municipality's objectives for growth, land use, infrastructure, housing, environmental protection, and several other matters – typically for a 20- to 30-year period. Official Plans must be reviewed and updated within 10 years of initial adoption and every five years thereafter. A Secondary Plan is an amendment to an Official Plan that provides more detailed prescriptions for a defined part of a

municipality. All decisions by a municipality on land use, zoning, development and redevelopment, and infrastructure must align with its Official Plan.¹¹²

A municipality may make reference in its Official Plan to energy management in general and to district energy in particular, in the last case giving the municipality a policy foundation to promote, require or support DES as part of land use and development decisions. In general, such references apply only to new development and redevelopment, as would any requirement that may flow from them.¹¹³

Community Energy Plans (CEPs)

Numerous municipalities have developed one or more CEPs, although such plans are not specifically referenced in provincial legislation or guidance. The provincial government had a Municipal Energy Plan Program covering eligible costs of such planning, last updated in 2017, which may have spurred the development of CEPs and similar documents.¹¹⁴ The Provincial Planning Statement – issued under the *Planning Act* – includes the following (italics in the original):¹¹⁵

2.9.1 Planning authorities shall plan to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and prepare for the *impacts of a changing climate* through approaches that ... b) incorporate climate change considerations in planning for and the development of *infrastructure*, including stormwater management systems, and *public service facilities*; c) support energy conservation and efficiency

3.8.1 Planning authorities should provide opportunities for the development of energy supply including electricity generation facilities and transmission and distribution systems, *energy storage systems*, district energy, *renewable energy systems*, and *alternative energy systems*, to accommodate current and projected needs.

A City of Toronto document – *Downtown Energy Strategy*– provides a concise description of a CEP as an “area-based approach that considers energy early in the land use and infrastructure planning process, and identifies opportunities to integrate resilient, low-carbon energy solutions at the building and neighbourhood scale.” Toronto’s website has a page on Community Energy Planning that includes the following: “... examples of community energy planning include the

¹¹² See the provincial government’s guide to official plans at [link](#).

¹¹³ For example, in Toronto’s Official Plan is a policy supporting “... processes that contribute towards an energy-neutral built environment including district heating and cooling” Another part of the Plan states that “Secondary Plans for Centres will assess opportunities for ... district energy and [combined heat and power generation].” See [link](#) for a 2021 presentation on Toronto’s climate policies that references these two parts of the City of Toronto’s Official Plan. For links to each of the several documents that together compose the current version of Toronto’s Official Plan go to [link](#). (The presentation shows the cover of a document with the title “East Harbour Community Energy Plan,” but no such document appears to be publicly available.)

¹¹⁴ For information about Ontario’s (former?) Municipal Energy Plan Program, see [link](#). As well as Toronto (see Notes 113 and 116), municipalities that have or have had one or more CEPs or similar policy and planning statements include Burlington, Guelph Halton Region, Hamilton, Kingston, Oxford County, Sudbury, Waterloo Region, and Windsor ([link](#)),

¹¹⁵ The 2024 Provincial Planning Statement is at [link](#).

extensive greening of homes and buildings, and the development and use of district energy systems,” the last being described in another part of the website as “a key component of Toronto’s climate action plan.”¹¹⁶

The development of CEPs in the Durham Region has been the subject of an extensive academic study of what was characterized as “collaborative governance.” This development was described as “a governance innovation where strategic energy planning decisions are made at the local level, resulting in publicly available planning documents.”¹¹⁷ The authors concluded, “... initiatives like Community Energy Planning provide a useful template for involving diverse actors and can contribute to more just and democratic transitions, these processes alone may be unlikely to overcome such complex and systemic challenges.”

CEPs where available can be considered useful steps towards more rigorous heating planning, as defined above (perhaps more accurately known as thermal energy planning).

10.3. Municipal Thermal Energy Planning (TEP)

Origins of the Boltzmann Institute’s TEP conference on March 20, 2025

In May and June 2024, the Boltzmann Institute conducted a study tour of 12 DES in northern Europe. The study tour was conducted independently of the Two Pathways project but was of considerable use to the project. A report on the study tour noted:

Two strong conclusions from our dozens of discussions with people at the forefront of moving Europe towards carbon neutrality are these:

1. There’s widespread optimism that decarbonization by 2050 of space heating – a major source of emissions in most of northern Europe and Canada – as well as space cooling is achievable and affordable. This will likely happen only if district energy systems served by non-carbon or otherwise-wasted heat sources are implemented in most urbanized places. (The optimism can be contrasted with the pessimism we sometimes noted as to whether decarbonization of transport, industry, and other sectors is similarly achievable.)
2. The most important step towards decarbonization of space heating and cooling in an urban area is usually development of a heating plan: identifying on a neighbourhood basis what the thermal demands will be in the years until 2050 and how they will be met.

Several more conclusions are set out at the end of this report [on the study tour].¹¹⁸

The second of the above two conclusions inspired the all-day conference on March 20, 2025, described at the beginning of this section and its inclusion as a component of the Two

¹¹⁶ Toronto’s 2018 *Downtown Energy Strategy* is at [link](#). Its website account of Community Energy Planning is at [link](#). The elaboration of district energy systems is at [link](#).

¹¹⁷ The study of Durham Region is reported behind a paywall at [link](#).

¹¹⁸ A 33-page report on the Boltzmann Institute’s 2024 study tour of 12 DES in eight northern European countries is at [link](#). There’s a briefer report in the June 2024 *District Energy Digest* at [link](#).

Pathways project. The remainder of this section sets out briefly what transpired at this conference and draws conclusions from it.¹¹⁹

German experts' presentations

A highlight of the morning of March 20 was a pair of presentations by two German experts on thermal energy planning – Dorian Holtz and Rafael Wittenburg of Theta Concepts GmbH, Rostock. The session was moderated by James Cotton of McMaster University.

The two experts shared their experience of working on plans for more than 30 municipalities with from 1,400 to 610,000 residents.¹²⁰ This has been done within the framework of a European Union (EU) directive and two items of German federal legislation.¹²¹ German municipalities with more than 100,000 residents are required to have thermal energy plans by mid-2026; others by mid-2028. Town and villages with less than 10,000 residents are allowed a modified procedure. Thus all 10,780 municipalities in Germany are affected. All receive up to 100% funding for the plan development – about 80% on average – from between about C\$1.50 to about C\$10.00 per inhabitant (less per capita for larger than smaller municipalities).

The EU directive requires thermal energy planning by municipalities with more than 45,000 residents (see Note 121). It also requires all municipalities to focus first on improving the energy efficiency of buildings. Holtz and Wittenburg noted that whereas the potential for achieving very low levels of energy use in new buildings is huge, renovation of existing buildings is expensive and of limited cost-effectiveness. The feasible renovation rate is normally below 1-2% annually and the realistic energy-saving potential normally has a maximum of 10-20%.

According to Holtz and Wittenburg, thermal energy plans have three essential phases and components:

- Determining actual and likely thermal energy demand for each existing and expected building from now until 2045 (Germany's net-zero target year; the EU's is 2050).
- Figuring out how the required thermal energy can be supplied, within the targets for progressive carbon-neutrality.
- Matching demand and supply in a feasible decarbonization plan with 5-year sub-targets, all developed with widespread consultation.

Regarding space heating, they see settled parts of municipalities as being mostly in one of five categories: (i) already have district heating; (ii) new district heating is clearly the best-suited

¹¹⁹ See [link](#) for links to the program for the March 20, 2025, conference; for answers to ten questions about heating planning (thermal energy planning); and for a 17-minute video on the Two Pathways project that was shown at the event.

¹²⁰ The slides presented by Dorian Holtz and Rafael Wittenburg of Theta Concepts GmbH are at [link](#).

¹²¹ The EU directive is the *Energy Efficiency Directive* (see [link](#)). It requires EU countries to promote heating and cooling plans in municipalities over 45,000 residents and requires district heating systems to use 50% renewable energy and waste heat by 2035 and 100% by 2050. Other EU directives relevant to space heating and cooling are the *Renewable Energy Directive* ([link](#)) and the *Energy Performance of Buildings Directive* (see [link](#)). The two items of German legislation are *Heating Planning Act* and the *Buildings Energy Act* (see [link](#) and [link](#)), in effect since early 2024.

heating approach, technically and economically; (iii) new district heating could be the best-suited heating approach; (iv) continue with (or even convert to) individual heating systems (e.g., heat pumps); and (v) make use of a possible supply of green (i.e., carbon-neutral) gas. This emphasis on district heating where feasible comes with targets for making all district heating carbon-neutral by 2045. It also comes with substantial support for district heating improvement and expansion.

Holtz and Wittenburg said a powerful tool in thermal energy planning is construction of a digital twin of the municipality, based on geospatial data and the best available information about building energy use.¹²²

Here are some of the conclusions of the German experts from the thermal energy plans they have facilitated and developed:

- Each plan is unique and done better with strong stakeholder involvement
- Efficient data handling is key, achieved through automation, standardization, and use of digital twins.
- Economic factors must prevail, with the goal of long-term savings.
- The strength of thermal networks is their ability to allow exploitation of wasted and other energy sources, including from sewage, lakes and rivers.

Responses about these two sessions to the post-event survey – described below –were favourable except for some concern about the relevance of German experience to Ontario. This response was typical: “Excellent presentations. While the circumstances are different, the Europeans are clearly years ahead. We could learn much from their disciplined approach and practical experience.”

How heating planning is conducted today

The remaining morning session at the March 20 event was concerned with “How heating planning is conducted today.” It was described in the conference program in this way: “Much of today’s planning is done by Enbridge, whose natural gas heats about 70% of floor space in Ontario and by Ontario’s Independent Electricity System Operator (IESO), which will oversee the main source of energy for space heating if electrification of heating is to be the main means of its decarbonization.”

At almost the last minute, Enbridge’s representative could not participate. Instead, Professor James Cotton of McMaster University – who had moderated the previous two sessions – was asked to explain how he would guide Enbridge through the energy transition. His presentation was entitled “Decarbonizing our Buildings: Commoditizing Waste Energy and the Impact of Infrastructure for Social Good.” IESO’s representative was Tom Aagaard. His

¹²² *The International Journal of AI for Materials and Design* is to have a special issue on “Cooling, Heating, and Thermal Energy Storage Systems: Harnessing the Power of Digital Twins” ([link](#)). The editorial for this special issue is already available at [link](#).

presentation was entitled “IESO Demand forecasting Overview – Space Heating.”¹²³ The moderator was Gabriella Kalapos, (Clean air Partnership).

A significant feature of Cotton’s presentation from a thermal energy planning perspective was exposition of New York State legislation, the *Utility Thermal Energy and Jobs Act*,¹²⁴ as having these features:

- The legislation allows public utilities to own, operate, and manage thermal energy networks, as well as supply distributed thermal energy, with Public Service Commission (PSC) oversight.
- Allows gas and electric utilities deliver thermal energy services through district thermal energy networks.
- Creates a regulatory process for piloting thermal energy networks and developing appropriate regulations for thermal energy networks, which transfer heat in and out of buildings as needed in a district network with low or zero emissions
- Requires the PSC to initiate and support the development of thermal energy networks for the purpose of meeting the GHG emissions and equity goals.
- Mandate that these networks are constructed by a skilled and trained workforce with the goal of employing utility workers transitioning to new systems

The legislation thus paves the way for existing utilities in New York State to become utilities providing thermal energy services.

Cotton introduced his presentation by noting Ontario’s current huge peak power demand by space and water heating in relation to the current electricity peak demand. The latter is about 22 GW compared with the average electricity demand of about 16 GW. Space and water heating’s peak is about 67 GW – now provided mostly by natural gas – compared with average demand for these purposes of about 22 GW. One conclusion is that a massive amount of electricity generation, transmission, and distribution infrastructure would be required to electrify heating, enough to provide for a fourfold or greater increase in peak electricity demand. Another conclusion that can be drawn is that the price of electricity would thereby be much increased, with strong impacts on low-income households and small businesses.

Aagaard’s presentation reinforced Cotton’s observation by noting that “The 2025 Annual Planning Outlook projects 523,000 heat pumps by 2050, which represents approximately 7.6% of all households.” This suggests that only a small fraction of 2050 households are projected to have converted to electric heating. He expected that a “majority of households will continue to use natural gas heating systems unless government policies require otherwise.”

Post-event survey responses expressed regret at Enbridge’s absence, and appreciation for Aagaard’s and Cotton’s presentations. The latter’s focus on “the potential for clean infrastructure in Canada” was especially noted, as was the possibility that IESO has doubts about the likelihood of widespread electrification “rather than championing the movement” (i.e., the electrification of space heating).

¹²³ James Cotton’s March 20 presentation is at [link](#). Tom Aagaard’s presentation is at [link](#).

¹²⁴ New York State’s *Utility Thermal Energy and Jobs Act* is at [link](#).

Advice from the Two Pathways project

The first afternoon session was to “set out the importance of and major results from the Two Pathways project, indicating how the experience could serve as advice to those about to undertake heating planning.” The panellists were three participants in the project: Kelton Friedrich (McMaster University), Sanda Yee (FVB Energy), and Martin Green (Boltzmann Institute). The project manager, John Stephenson (Boltzmann Institute) served as moderator.

A focus of the discussion was the complexity of the challenges related to decarbonization of space heating and cooling and the need for good leadership, policy, and funding arrangements to address a large encompassing issue that is beyond individual solutions and actions. With sufficient resources and collaboration among stakeholders, all technical and financial issues can be solved. Pipe can be routed through congested roadways, building infrastructure can be designed to accommodate district energy, financial grants, investments, structuring and business cases can be developed to ensure a cost-positive proposition. Low carbon networks will likely be a key component of many such decarbonization strategies, but there is not a single silver-bullet solution. The key issue is people and developing consensus strategic decarbonization by implementing low carbon networks in addition to electrification because there is not a single silver bullet solution.

Post-event survey responses concerning this session were generally favourable. The effective collaboration of three institutions bringing different skills and perspectives to the project was complimented. Also: “This panel, together with the accompanying video, was great for bringing the underlying issues into focus.” Green’s slide was welcomed as effectively reinforcing the previous session’s suggestions as to the lack of feasibility of mass electrification.¹²⁵ The main criticism of the session was that although the emphasis on thermal networks was considered reasonable there was insufficient regard for alternatives, thus countering a primary objective of thermal energy planning, which should be to consider all feasible alternatives.

Governmental perspectives on municipal thermal energy planning

This session suffered from the unavailability of expert input from the provincial and federal governments due in part to the distractions of the provincial election in February 2025 and the federal election in April 2025. Key panellists were thus all from municipal governments: Ian McVey (Durham Region), Graham Seaman (City of Markham), and Christine Tu (Peel Region). The moderator was Michael Wiggin (Boltzmann Institute).

In the panellist’s discussion, there was some emphasis on Peel’s systematic approach. It includes an approved Climate Change Master Plan that recognizes the importance of transitioning to diversified and low-carbon energy sources, including district energy systems. As part of this commitment, Peel is actively advancing plans for a system that will harness waste heat from one of its water resource recovery facilities. To support this vision, the Region is also developing a Thermal Network Strategy to fully explore opportunities for sustainable growth and redevelop-

¹²⁵ Martin Green’s slide is at [link](#). The 17-minute video on the Two Pathways project is at [link](#).

ment. This, effectively, marks the emergence of municipal-scale heat planning, an area of growing importance that aligns naturally with local government responsibilities.

Points made during the discussion included concern about what could be the huge individual and societal costs of widespread electrification of space heating. Thermal energy planning could well – if the German examples are followed – result in better solutions providing for lower costs and greater reliability. Although such planning is appropriate for large and small inhabited areas, there could be merit in having the strongest focus at what may best be described as regional rather than local levels. Broad, systematic regional thinking and planning could be a natural next step in the work already being done in many Ontario municipalities.

Post-event survey responses complemented the candidness and level-headedness of the panelists about the challenges faced by municipalities, although more about the political context of the challenges would have been welcomed. Panelists said they'd support a strong thermal energy planning role for municipalities if there were appropriate provincial policy direction together with legislative support and funding. A strong conclusion was that provincial decision-makers, in particular, are much in need of practical advice – even education – about the issues discussed.

Non-governmental perspectives on municipal thermal energy planning

Panelists for this session were Michael Conte (FVB Energy), Dennis Fotinos (Noventa Energy), Jerry Huang (Oshawa Power), and Darryl Neate (Real Property Association of Canada - REALPAC). Stephen Taylor (Boltzmann Institute) was the moderator.

This group of industry professionals discussed the importance of how thermal energy planning should be top of mind for municipalities and private sector developments as a means to improving efficiency of our heating and cooling systems, lowering dependence on fossil fuels, and increasing the resilience of our communities through ever-increasing climate threats. A critical first step is establishing the thermal grid that allows for energy to be shared – rather than generated and discarded – and facilitates the adoption of renewable energy technologies at scale.

Post-event survey responses were uniformly favourable about this panel discussion, with much praise for the evident skills and knowledge of the panelists – “Wow, these folks know their files!” — and regret that more time than the allocated hour had not been available.

A typical response was: “Terrific high-energy panel discussing the role of the private sector in planning, executing, operating, and living with the outcomes of heating strategies. Good discussion of major spillover benefits (and costs) on the national economy and on the lives of local residents.” Panelists emphasized the need for effective thermal energy planning, but with uncertainty as to how this might best be secured.

Wrap-up session

Bryan Karney (University of Toronto) provided a well-regarded overview of the day's proceedings. The post-event survey responses on his presentation included these: “Art and science combined nicely”; “Very creative, energetic and skilled – knows the energy space and the need to focus more on cultural change/leadership than technology”; “A lyrical and informative session

wonderfully condensing the days events, leaving some thought-provoking ideas to mull over”; “Quite a wonderful summary. Very lyrical”; “Excellent and inspiring wrap-up of the event – hopefully providing great encouragement and direction for the next generation of researchers and decision-makers.”

Survey responses to questions about the March 20 conference

Completion of a post-event survey was requested of the conference’s approximately 105 participants and returned by 22 of them. The survey provided opportunities for comment on each of the sessions. These responses have been summarized above in the accounts of each session.

The survey also requested responses to three multiple choice questions. Responses to these questions are summarized in Table 10.1. These responses suggest that municipally led thermal energy planning is regarded as essential, but funding for it should perhaps come from other sources (perhaps from the federal government, as it is mainly the case in Germany).

Respondents to the survey were invited to make further comments on the event or about municipal thermal energy planning. Many of these responses emphasized the need for more coordination among governments – federal, provincial, municipal – on decarbonization of in-building energy use, especially for space heating. A follow-up conference in 2026 would be welcome, both to review progress to provide more focus on the *implementation* of thermal energy plans.

Table 10-1. Responses to multiple-choice survey questions re. event on March 20, 2025

Question	Responses			
	No	Likely not	Likely yes	Yes
1. Will meeting the 2050 net-zero target require heating planning, as defined above?	0	2	7	13
2. Even if you expressed concerns about heating planning as defined above, please indicate whether such planning, if required, should be done by municipalities?	0	0	8	14
3. It seems that useful heating planning could cost about two dollars per capita per year, less for larger municipalities and more for smaller ones, whether most of the work is done in-house or by consultants. Should this cost be borne by municipalities?	4	7	5	6

Other comments on the March 20 event

Some 15 participants commented on the event by email rather than by survey response. These comments included regard for the organization of the conference, which was frequently described as enjoyable (perhaps unusually for the type of event). The high level of audience engagement and participation was noted as was the appeal of the event “to both the engineering experts as well as interested lay folks.” The elaboration of what is happening in Ontario regarding

district energy was appreciated, with particular praise for the work of Markham District Energy and Noventa Energy. There was concern that some of the engineering challenges of district energy were glossed over – even though the event was about thermal energy planning rather than engineering specifics.

Conclusions from the March 20 event

The most plausible conclusion from the March 20 event is that it tapped an unmet need for substantive discussion of building decarbonization and went some way towards meeting that need. There seemed to be strong support for municipal thermal energy planning, although many participants may have already been so disposed. Participants may have been more equally divided as to whether municipalities should fund the energy planning. There was much interest in district energy, chiefly as the main but not the only outcome of such a planning process.

What could perhaps have received more attention on March 20 is not only whether the Ontario government should require Ontario municipalities to engage in thermal energy planning – there was strong agreement it should – but how else that government could help municipalities with such planning work beyond funding it. As noted in Section 3 of this report a key requirement for any progress in planning for building decarbonization would be adequate access to relevant data. Current energy providers could be compelled to provide municipalities with such data, with suitable protection for commercial interests.

10.4. Conclusions from this Section

Municipalities have substantial responsibility for planning how their communities unfold, which to date has often included development of Community Energy Plans. Discussed here is a more intensive kind of energy planning – known as thermal energy planning – that would look to how every existing and expected building could be heated and cooled in decades to come, taking account of potential non-carbon and/or otherwise wasted sources of thermal energy. Such energy planning is becoming the norm in Europe, where it is believed to be an essential step towards building decarbonization. Reaching a goal of building decarbonization in Ontario would likely require thermal energy planning, which could best be done by municipalities.

11. Application to Indigenous Communities

Remote and Indigenous communities are very varied in size, density, building types and available energy options. Also, the pressing issues within those communities are many and varied. Accordingly, seeking a community partner with decarbonization as an objective met with limited success. However, there were clearly issues that were attractive about thermal networks.

Two communities that agreed to cooperate were Bingwi Neyaashi Anishinaabek (BNA), also known as Sand Point First Nation, and the Oujé-Bougoumou Cree Nation (OBCN). BNA is located at the south east side of Lake Nipigon in northern Ontario and OBCN is located in Quebec, about 650 km north of Montreal, just west of Chibougamau.¹²⁶

BNA was seen as valuable because they had made a clear commitment to a district heating system because fossil fuels are expensive, the electricity service to their area has frequent power interruptions, and they have a free wood source from the Papasay sawmill that they operate. OBCN established a district heating system in 1992 to make use of locally available waste wood materials – initially sawdust and shavings but now wood chips. In both cases, the use of wood wastes was seen as compatible with their sustainability values and likely to be cheaper than fossil fuel or electricity alternatives.

While BNA is just starting, with negotiations for financing underway, it is still a useful example of the value of the biomass district heating option for northern and remote communities. OBCN, on the other hand, has over 30 years of operating history and provides many lessons learned as an early adopter of this technology. While BNA did not have detailed financial information yet available, OBCN agreed to let us use their community as a basis for showing what it would cost to build and operate if a similar system were to be built today – a system that incorporated all of the lessons learned over the many years of operation and also used the up to date technology and design practices available today. The combination of the two community summaries should provide some useful lessons for other communities considering district heating options today.

Given that Indigenous communities are very variable in density, building type and condition, and the availability of skills and local energy source options, the analysis of the OBCN based example included a sensitivity analysis of the effect of i) building density, ii) the cost of competing fuels, and iii) the cost of biomass fuel options. The following provides a summary of the findings in the two examples. A detailed analysis of the OBCN based system is included as Annex D to this report.

In the examples considered here, biomass was the chosen renewable energy alternative, but other communities may consider heat from current diesel generators to avoid the importing of oil, or solar thermal panels.

For larger communities, Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage (STES) is emerging as an important, potentially game-changing technology. The winter peak heating loads are very high

¹²⁶ The websites for BNA and OBCN are at <http://www.bnafn.ca/> and at <https://ouje.ca/>.

but of short duration. At a certain scale, when surplus heat production is available, including heat from solar panels during summer months or heat from diesel generators that is not needed when heat loads are low, large scale STES units can store heat for months to meet peak demands. STES could displace oil boilers that might normally be used for the peak heating months and the installed heating capacity could be reduced.

It may be too early to design STES into the system as options are currently being developed, but as options become available the community can expand and use STES to reduce the installed heating capacity requirements.

11.1. Overview of benefits of thermal networks

One of the most attractive features of a thermal network is that it transfers responsibility from the building owner to a community utility. For the community heating utility the options are many, including (at least in transition) using heat from community diesel generators, biomass boilers or solar thermal or solar PVT (Photovoltaic thermal) collectors. With a thermal network in place, the community can now consider technologies that may not have been available or cost effective at the building level. Increasingly, options like solar thermal can be coupled with biomass and thermal energy storage to manage loads and even use summer excess heat to meet winter heating loads.

Normally, fossil fuels and electricity are from sources outside of the community. A thermal network enables a community to switch to local or regional energy sources and thus improve the local economy and job creation.

Local wood wastes, for example, might be a desirable source, but it may be useful to develop a community energy harvesting or production system to either grow and chip fast growing trees or make a business of participating in area forest management by collecting and chipping “slash” – wood residues left after lumber is removed.

The construction and operation of a thermal network also requires new skills during construction, operation and expansion. Accordingly, there may be new opportunities for young people wanting to stay in the community.

Every community is different and the opportunities different, but it will be important to consider the benefits and skills requirements and develop a clear picture of implications for the community. Some of the required skills may not yet be available so it will be important to

Figure 11.1 Typical shallow buried district heating

Figure 11.2 Proposed BNA district heating system – south extension

set priorities for training or education and to make sure the system can be built and operated with the highest degree of independence.

11.2. Bingwi Neyaashi Anishinaabek

Both BNA and OBCN were communities that had lived in their ancestral lands from time immemorial. The people of BNA were displaced over the years; first by flooding when the Nipigon River was dammed. Communities around Lake Nipigon were flooded; houses, cemeteries and cultural buildings were inundated and people were forced to move. Later, in the 1950s, the Province created the Lake Nipigon/Black Sands Park and residents were again forced to move and homes were burned down. But finally, in 2010, land was allocated for BNA and planning started for a sustainable community that now has about 25 housing units, including 13 homes, 2 duplexes (4 units) and 2 fourplexes (8 units). BNA expects to build approximately 80+ homes over the next 25 years. This does not include community buildings: Government Office, Roundhouse, Elders Complex, Community Centre, Police/Fire/Ambulatory building, Health Clinic, training centre.

The current buildings use electric baseboard heating or electric furnaces and have back-up wood heating in case of electricity interruptions or to displace electricity use. While a 3-phase electricity line was installed to connect the community to the grid, the Hydro One line to which it is connected has had a history of interrupted service. In planning for a more sustainable and affordable heating system, BNA is committed to a biomass based district heating system. This

WHAT WE'LL SEE DOWN TWO PATHWAYS TO ZERO EMISSIONS FROM BUILDINGS

Figure 11.3 Proposed BNA district heating system – north extension

decision was an obvious choice because of the availability of local wood resources, particularly the wood waste from the community owned Papasay sawmill. For now, they see the waste wood as a free source of fuel, but allowance will be necessary for handling, chipping and transport to future wood boilers.

Detailed costing was not available to us at the time of this report writing because BNA is in the process of design and negotiation for program support. However, the following heating plant details were provided

Boiler Plant #1

1. 2- 500 kW Boilers
2. 1- 1000 kW Boiler
3. Chip Storage bin c/w Toploader
4. 2- Buffer Tanks
5. 1 Ash removal conveying system c/w Ash bin.

Boiler Plant #2

1. 2- 200 kW Boilers
2. Chip Storage bin c/w Toploader
3. 2- Buffer Tanks
4. 1 Ash removal conveying system c/w Ash bin

Two boiler plants were envisaged because the community is separated by a stream and the two parts are not interconnected in the current plan. Development and operating plans are:

- Boiler Plant #1 will service most of the community to the north of the creek, including residences and commercial buildings.
- Boiler Plant #2 will be located on the south side of the creek and will service residences and a few commercial buildings.
- Each plant will have the ability to be built in a phased approach to match the number of houses that will be serviced, as the community grows.
- The chips will be produced at the sawmill property and seasoned in a weatherproof structure.
- Chips will be hauled to each Boiler Plant and stored at the plant in a chip storage bay.
- Chips will be reclaimed by a Toploader and fed to the boilers by conveyor.
- Ash will be collected by ash conveyors from each boiler and sent into an exterior ash bin that can be loaded onto a truck and hauled to its final disposal area.

Discussions with the community indicate that they see the biomass district heating systems as a very desirable option for their community and that it is compatible with community sustainability values.

11.3. Oujé-Bougoumou Cree Nation

As with BNA, the community had been displaced many times by mining and forestry operations. However, the OBCN had never ceded its territory and in 1989 occupied the townsite and blocked the access road. By 1990, negotiations with the federal government were launched in an effort to secure its financial participation in building a new permanent village for the community. This process resulted in the Oujé-Bougoumou-Canada Agreement of May 1992, which called for the Government of Canada to provide funding toward the construction of the village of Oujé-Bougoumou.

In 1991, while the community was already under construction, the community explored biomass district heating using wastes from area sawmills. Normally, such a low-density community would have been an unlikely candidate for district heating, but developments in the fabrication of pre-insulated PEX (high density polyethylene) pipe with surface treatment to act as a barrier to oxygen made construction of

Figure 11.4 The Oujé-Bougoumou community

such low-density systems possible. PEX pipes are flexible and can be installed using local labour.

A feasibility study was conducted in 1991 and by November, 1992, the system was in operation. There were a number of challenges over the years and these will be detailed in the lessons learned section. Initially, given that district energy systems were relatively new in Canada, the buildings were designed separately from the distribution system. The building designs used more water

Figure 11.5 Oujé-Bougoumou biomass heating plant

than the system was designed for. For a number of years, there were some pressure problems in some parts of the system and adequate heat supply was a problem for a few buildings. Over the years, this was corrected and the system now operates well.

Since its beginning, the system has gradually expanded to serve approximately 175 single-family residences and 30 larger public buildings. The peak heating demand is now about 3.3 MWth with an annual energy requirement of about 11,000 MWh. In recent years, the system has been able to run on about 95% wood chips, with oil only occasionally used for peaking during extreme cold weather or a back-up during service interruptions in the biomass systems.

The system evolved over a number of years. Initially, there was one biomass boiler (1.2 MW) and one oil boiler for back-up or peaking, but this was gradually expanded to add another biomass boiler (1.5 MW) and the oil boiler was moved to a separate building. As the community grew, two more oil boilers were added for additional security in case the biomass system was interrupted. In 2016, a welding related fire in the heating plant put the biomass heating plant out of order but the separate oil-fired boilers were able to meet heating loads and service was not interrupted. After the fire, support was provided from NRCan and the First Nations Infrastructure Fund to rebuild the biomass plant, to implement modifications to the system piping and controls, to replace remaining steel pipe in the distribution system with PEX pipe and to expand to service new buildings. A 1.25 MW biomass package plant was added to provide some biomass heating while the original heat plant and boilers were restored.

For purposes of this report, and based on lessons learned, an estimate was prepared to illustrate what a similar system would cost today and the cost savings compared to alternatives. Also, a sensitivity analysis was conducted to show how key variables might affect system cost and economics. These variables included i) energy density (a more compact community), ii) fuel prices for biomass and oil.

11.4. District heating for Oujé-Bougoumou today

The Oujé-Bougoumou district heating system has been built over a period of over 30 years. There have been problems, to be elaborated in the lessons learned section, and a variety of designers and approaches taken. To make the example useful for present day readers, it was decided to cost out the system in today's dollars and costs, using best practices and incorporating lessons learned during the many years of operation. Based on past experience, if the same system were built today, it would be designed to use local wood chips to supply about 95% of the energy with 5% coming from oil for peaking and back-up during biomass heating plant maintenance or other interruptions.

For comparison, it was assumed that the BAU (business as usual) option would use electric heating for residential buildings with oil heating for larger public, cultural and recreational buildings. Both capital and operating costs were calculated to allow a comparison of options. The layout of the system is provided below.

The community started with houses at the west end of the community near to the shore of Lake Opemisca. The district heating system expanded over the years to the size and layout shown above.

The details of the analysis of the system, if it were to be built today, is summarized in the Report prepared by FVB Energy, the OBCN's engineer, and available as Annex D.

Figure 11.6 Layout of the existing Oujé-Bougoumou district heating system

The system would cost an estimated \$28.7 million more than the BAU cost with electricity heating for residences and oil heating for larger community and cultural buildings. This results in a payback of about 22 years.

It is important to note that the BAU option would require additional investments by Hydro Quebec to generate and distribute about 3.5 MWe of electricity. At the time of this writing, no estimate was obtainable from Hydro Quebec and this cost has not been included. However, it is understood that Hydro Quebec is approaching capacity limits in the next year or so and electricity prices may be adjusted to reflect necessary investments. This should be taken into account for other remote or Indigenous communities. The benefit of the district heating system is that lower cost energy supplies can be secured.

The 22 year payback of the system was based on current fuel oil costs and electricity rates. With these costs, the savings in annual operating costs was about \$1.29 million. To make the example useful to other communities, a sensitivity analysis was conducted.

11.5. Sensitivity analyses

The sensitivity analysis (Table 6 in Annex D) showed that a major driver of costs was the community thermal energy demand density. A 50% higher density could reduce the payback to about 16 years while a density reduction to 50% could increase costs to as much as 54 years. Higher fuels oil costs (50% higher) would also reduce the payback to about 15 years. In some communities, such as BNA, the wood fuel costs could be very low, almost free, and this might also reduce the payback time to about 15 years.

Fossil fuel costs of all kinds (oil, natural gas or propane) would have been higher if carbon pricing were still in effect. Some equivalent strategy may emerge to encourage fossil fuel use reduction and communities should keep an eye on these developments.

11.6. Environmental Impact

Importantly, moving to a large share of biomass with minimal oil use for peaking and back-up (about 5% of annual energy) could reduce the GHG emissions by about 90% - from 2260 tonnes/year CO_{2e} to about 220 tonnes/year CO_{2e}.

11.7. Lessons learned

Aside from factors affecting economic performance, there were many other issues that affected the ongoing operating costs, customer comfort and overall system security. To assist other communities, especially those new to district heating concepts, a summary of lessons learned was compiled. These appear in a compact summary in the accompanying Annex D, but many are elaborated more fully below based on other experience with the community, and feedback from the system operational manager.

At the time of construction in 1991/1992, district energy was relatively new to Canada and design approaches were not standardized. Since construction, the advisors or consultants have changed and some issues were not obvious until problems arose. The following issues, if addressed in new systems, might avoid similar problems and some unnecessary costs.:

1. **Design Standards:** The designers of buildings had no clear guidance to ensure that building systems would be compatible with the district energy system design. Building systems designed to extract maximum heat from the district heating supply – with the greatest temperature difference (delta T) between supply and return flow – can minimize the required flow volume, size of pipe, and thus cost. Many building systems were designed with low delta T which resulted in the need for high flows through the buildings to provide enough heat. This resulted in incompatibility between the high delta T design of the district system and the low delta T designs of the building heating systems. The resulting flows through the district heating pipes were higher than designed for. This led to excessive pressure drops – the buildings that were furthest away from the heating plant did not have enough pressure differential to induce flow through the building heating system. The result was that some buildings did not have enough, or, occasionally, any, heat.

Action: This caused significant heating performance problems over several years. To improve this, it is critical that the DH system has firm connection guidelines and a peer review process with new customers (i.e., designers). Modifications to existing buildings took a long time and incurred expenses that could have been avoided.

2. **Staff training:** The introduction of a district heating system required new and different skills than were initially available. This resulted in problems for some staff, or some staff with greater training having to take too much responsibility. This also created problems for managers who had to oversee work and make sure that necessary tasks were done. Operations staff commitment and training of local staff to operate and maintain the system on a consistent basis has been challenging.

Action: To remedy this, more training of operation staff, and, as importantly, key staff taking ownership and pride of the district heating system. This could be combined with clear job descriptions and training plans for each position. Starting earlier to find staff with commitment and to provide training could reduce operational and management challenges.

3. **Water treatment:** Water needs to be treated to remove oxygen and control pH so that steel pipe or other metal components do not corrode. This is a hidden problem because, if not practiced, by the time corrosion problems show up there may be too much damage done and irreversible corrosion damage. Pipe corrosion resulted in leakage that affected the insulation value of the foam around the pipes and often required the replacement of steel pipes. This also resulted in make-up water requirements that were excessive and the possible contamination of groundwater, depending on the water treatment practices. Leakage related to corrosion was aggravated by lack of quality control on welded joints.

Action: To refurbish the system, most of the steel pipe was removed and replaced with PEX pipe, where possible. Steel pipe still had to be used in larger piping (over 100 mm ID) around the heating plant. To protect the remaining steel pipe and fittings, a new water treatment system was installed to remove oxygen and the water is regularly tested to make sure that the pH is kept within proper limits. Welding was improved through training

or the hiring of certified welders. Even with all PEX piping, water treatment is a priority to protect other parts of the system (including in-building systems).

4. **Pitting Corrosion:** Part of district heating design is making sure that minimum velocities are periodically maintained in all pipes – especially steel pipes. To overcome pressure drops in some sections of the system some larger pipes were installed. However, for long periods of time, velocities were very low and deposits accumulated on the bottom of pipes. Even with water treatment, acids can form below deposits and pitting corrosion can occur.

Action: Some of the larger pipes were removed and replaced with PEX pipes where possible and water treatment was implemented. Designs of future piping ensure that adequate velocities are periodically achieved.

5. **Plant separation:** Initially, the biomass and oil boiler were located in the same building. With expansion, the oil boilers for peaking and back-up were moved to a separate building and an additional biomass boiler was installed. In 2016, there was a fire caused by a welding contractor, but heating was maintained because the oil boilers were able to operate independently.

Action: Having separate biomass heating plants & peaking/back-up heating plants provides security considering the (generally) higher fire risks with the biomass technologies. Separate plants and the use of industrial grade biomass heating is also important for increased reliability and longevity.

6. **Enhanced customer building connection and substations (ETSS):** The original building heating design had the district heating system water directly connected to the building heating system. There were control problems and the risk of leakage on the customer side or contamination of the district heating water by customers.

Action: The building connections were modified with isolating heat exchangers (indirect) connections and improved flow/temperature controls. This includes using control valves that can handle high(er) differential pressures (dP) and/or the use of dP valves.

7. **DHW hot water control and potential for scalding:** There have been ongoing problems with instantaneous DHW configurations, with frequent heat exchanger leaks and poor flow and temperature controls. In many cases, the flow to provide water heating was larger than necessary causing excess flows in the district heating system.

Action: DHW should be configured with some storage, in a charging configuration with proper temperature and flow control valves.

8. **Operating procedures and reporting requirements:** While there was some initial training by suppliers on how to operate the heating plant, many of these lessons needed to be maintained and reinforced. This was complicated by changes in staff over the years. Also, some important issues had large cost implications – like the high cost of using oil boilers when there were problems with biomass boilers. Staff needed to be more aware of the cost consequences of not attending to some problems quickly.

Action: Establish operating procedures and reporting requirements for the plant operators, including key performance indicators, (preventive) maintenance procedures, etc. Key performance indicators would make it clear to staff (and eventually, administrators) if there were operational issues requiring urgent attention.

9. **General capacity building/training:** There will be better operation and a higher level of independence if staff can assume more responsibility including repairs or modifications to equipment and construction of new pipelines. If training is not available to all staff, there will be higher dependence on outside contractors. Also, if only some staff are trained or experienced then, they may be required to do a disproportionate share of the work. This can lead to staff burn-out and turnover.

Action: Develop staff job descriptions and training plans for each position. This may include ongoing training, formal training at technical colleges or institutes as well as onsite training by contractors or manufacturers' representatives. For heating plant operation, it would be the goal of obtaining operator licenses, e.g., Class 4 for heating plant coupled with interaction with area certified boiler operators.

10. **Communications with the community:** There are some challenges as not all residents/customers appreciate the value of the district heating system to the community nor of the need to support community debt or operating costs through adequate rates structures and regular payments by customers. While the history of communication is not documented, it would be important to make sure that customers valued the service and supported it. If they were served by external electricity utilities or oil companies, non-payment would result in interruption of service. The community has been reluctant to deal with non-payment resulting in the community having to fund periodic budget shortfalls.

Action: Early and continuous communication with customers is important and needs to be maintained and a business plan to set rates that will support the system's operation. Since every community is different, and the share of costs that must be covered by the community, the communications and business planning must be tailored by the community itself. Strategies and communications approaches that work in one community may not work in others.

11.8. Conclusions

Communities considering district energy should carefully consider the key variables. Attention to wood fuel prices and community layout could have a significant effect on the cost to the system. But also, some locations may experience very high costs to bring in heating oil and this may make a project using lower cost energy supplies much more attractive. In some northern communities the environmental and financial cost of bringing in heating oil can be very high and a district heating system may make these systems more attractive. Initially, in communities served by heat from diesel generators, a big efficiency improvement could be made by using the heat for a thermal network, as in Fort Simpson. This heat and electricity could be later replaced by other sources – possible biomass or emerging MMR CHP (Micro Modular Reactors with Combined Heat

and Power). Where seasonal thermal energy storage is an option, solar thermal panels may be attractive.

Oil cost, however, could have a major impact. The recent cancellation of carbon pricing has led to a price reduction, but other measures are under consideration to encourage reductions in fossil fuel use. The final approach is unclear but should be monitored and considered.

12. Implications for LDCs

Ontario has about 60 electricity local distribution companies (LDCs) whose customer counts range from hundreds to over a million, depending on the communities served. Decarbonization of building heating will result in different electric power demand, no matter what pathway is followed in any given LDC. Significant electrification of heating in an LDC could result in peak demand growing so much that almost the entire distribution network would need to be replaced/upgraded to have several (up to 5) times the existing peak capacity.

High level analysis of available data was undertaken to illustrate where, within each LDC, different approaches to decarbonization of building heating might be appropriate. These included GSHPs in areas where the population density is less than 24 people/ha and either ASHPs or TNs where the population density is higher.

Available data included:

- census data on population and dwelling counts at the DB level
- numbers of dwellings by type, at the FSA level, from StatCan
- hourly temperature records from weather stations at given coordinates across Ontario
- hourly power consumption recorded by smart meters and customer counts, aggregated at the FSA level, for residential customers
- province-wide monthly natural gas usage for residential, commercial and industrial sectors
- 2021 annual LDC customer, rate class, energy and peak power statistics from the OEB for most LDCs
- geographic geometry data for DBs and FSAs from StatCan and for LDCs from the OEB.

Detailed data on the buildings within the service area of each LDC could not be obtained (due to both cost and policy). Neither (due to policy) was any detailed data available on natural gas usage at the LDC or smaller scale, or for time periods shorter than one month, to allow more reliable determination of heating demand.

An individual report was produced for each of 55 LDCs for which adequate data was available. Those reports are all available as LDC Annexes to this Two Pathways report.

Included in each LDC report are tables and plots showing key data and analysis results relevant to electric power demand that the LDC may need to serve. They include an indication of the fraction of residential (and other) customers that should be able to install GSHPs and the complementary fraction that could convert to either thermal networks or ASHPs.

The electric power demands of thermal networks are considered small. Conversion of existing buildings to thermal networks may sometimes reduce both their annual and peak electricity usage. No attempt has been made to quantify the electric power impact of thermal networks since that would depend on detailed heating plans and multiple technology choices.

The most significant plot for each LDC shows the magnitude and hourly characteristics of the fully diversified electric power demand that could result from heating electrification with GSHPs, wherever viable, and ASHPs elsewhere. For most LDCs, this heating-only demand has

peaks that are several times historical demand peaks on the LDC's network. Restoring power following a prolonged outage in cold weather could be particularly challenging, since all heat pumps (or backup resistance elements) would be drawing maximum power at the same time, and possibly continuing for hours. The demand on individual circuits and the whole LDC could be significantly above the normal diversified demand.

Due to the above-mentioned data challenges, the analysis for each LDC must be treated with caution. Some of the tabular data, together with more detailed data that the LDC will likely have, would enable more accurate calculations by LDC staff. LDCs with existing thermal networks will have correspondingly lower additional power demand due to heating electrification. Despite these cautions, what is shown in the LDC Annex reports is indicative of the potential impacts of heating electrification.

13. Conclusions

This section first sets out conclusions from the preceding sections, 1-12. It then presents our overall conclusion from comparing the electrification pathway for achieving building decarbonization with the thermal network pathway. Finally, it provides broader conclusions and a synthesis towards a sustainable future.

13.1. Conclusions from sections

Section 1 presents the key findings from the Two pathways project. It concludes that heating buildings without natural gas – or any other fossil fuel – is a major, underappreciated challenge for Canada’s ambitions to achieve decarbonization, i.e., zero or near-zero emissions of greenhouse gases (GHGs), also known as net-zero GHG emissions. Canada-wide, space heating is responsible for about a fifth of GHG emissions. In the Toronto region, and likely in many of Canada’s other urban areas, more than half of total GHG emissions are from space heating. (Space cooling is responsible for much smaller, although growing, shares of GHG emissions.)

Section 2 concludes that there are two broad approaches to the challenge of providing adequate space heating without burning fossil fuels. One is the electrification pathway, for which space heating is provided mostly by heat pumps at buildings. This pathway can achieve zero or near-zero emissions of GHGs only when electricity generation is from non-carbon sources. These sources are notably solar, wind, hydroelectric, and nuclear, and can include biomass and biogas. Another approach is the thermal networks pathway, whereby heat from diverse, non-carbon sources is delivered to buildings, usually as hot water, by an underground network of pipes, i.e., a TN. Present policy in Canada favours the electrification pathway. Policies in Europe, China, and elsewhere favour TN pathways where feasible. Optimal strategies may well involve deployment of both TN and electrification pathways, with the former in areas of higher population density and latter elsewhere – mostly using ground-source heat pumps. TN pathways can exploit otherwise-wasted heat, in the short term even from carbon-fuelled activity. Strategic integration of the electricity and thermal network infrastructures can yield significant benefits to both – a strategy known as sector coupling.

Section 3 describes the methods used in this project and does not have explicit conclusions. Two conclusions can be implied from this section: Important data could not be obtained, either because suitable records do not exist or due to the information owners not facilitating or allowing access. The complication and uncertainty that would have been incurred by attempting to model future years were deemed so great as to not be worthwhile.

Section 4 substantiates the conclusion that space heating is the main source of building-related GHG emissions, with heating water for washing, cooking, etc. as the second source. Noted further is the challenge of reducing the demand for thermal energy in existing buildings, which will likely compose about 70% of Ontario’s building stock in 2050. Retrofitting is expensive, slow to scale, and unlikely to materially affect demand by 2050. The salient although much underappreciated characteristic of building thermal demand is its huge variability: peak thermal

power requirements during multi-day cold spells can be several times peak electrical power requirement at any time.

Section 5 examines the electrification pathway and notes the following: Chiefly because of the need to meet peak thermal power needs with equipment that becomes inefficient during the coldest weather, widespread deployment of air-source heat pumps would require massive, likely infeasible, expansion of Ontario's electricity generation, transmission, and distribution. The cost of providing electricity would rise to a level that households, businesses, and society in general could not afford. In essence, the electrification pathway is a dead end.

Section 6 focuses on the TN pathway, which is estimated to be cost-effective for up to 70% of Ontario's building stock located mostly in urban and suburban areas. The remaining 30% of buildings, in lower density areas, would be heated with electrically powered ground-source heat pumps (GSHP), supplemented as needed by solar thermal collectors. The major challenge of providing for peak thermal energy demand in the coldest weather can be met with a strategy realizable only with TN pathway deployment: provision of affordable large-scale energy storage. The cost of thermal energy storage is on the order of one percent of the cost of electricity storage (e.g., batteries). With adequate thermal energy storage, not only can peak demand be met affordably, seasonal storage becomes affordable. Summer heat can be saved cost-effectively for winter use. Thus, a TN strategy for just about all Ontario buildings now served with natural gas would achieve decarbonization by 2050 with greater certainty and at far less cost than replacing natural gas furnaces with air-source heat pumps. The societal cost of a TN pathway for the 70% of building space now served by natural gas would be about half of the cost the electrification pathway with air-source heat pumps. A TN pathway can be designed to provide space cooling as well as space heating and domestic hot water.

Section 7 concludes that a staged, hybrid transition is needed to meet the goal of decarbonization of Ontario's building energy use by 2050. As well as a gradual conversion to district energy in most settled areas, there would be a focus on deployment of ground-source heat pumps in low-density and rural areas. While planning for long-term infrastructure, regular air-source heat pumps, sized to replace end-of-life air conditioners, would reduce GHG emissions at temperatures above about +4 C while avoiding the need for expensive power system upgrades.

Section 8 compares many of the impacts of the electrification and TN pathways. It concludes, as does Section 6, that the electrification pathway would require much more investment and notes higher inflationary and fiscal impacts. Both pathways can meet the essential need for heating of buildings – though SE requires infrastructure investment on a scale not before seen in Canada. Both pathways can lead to net zero, but DES is much more cost-effective (about half the cost of the electrification pathway) and can be deployed in a more modular, less risky manner. Neither solution is perfect for every situation and hybrid approaches tailored to specific local requirements will probably give the best overall result. The resources required for undertaking these types of transformational changes are daunting but also create major positive impacts on the national and provincial economies, including on growth, investment, productivity, employment, incomes, and new industries as well as important consequences for life safety, health, wellness and the environment.

Section 9 notes the likely strong role of municipalities in any articulation of the TN pathway. Present Ontario legislation is adequate for TN deployment but the financial position of municipalities is not. Sufficient private capital seems available in a way that could be used for TN development. A barrier to its use could be a record of arbitrary action by provincial governments that could discourage long-term investment.

Section 10 extends consideration of municipal involvement in TN deployment with a focus on the importance of thermal energy planning, a three-stage process involving detailed estimate of a district's thermal demand and its potential thermal supply, and formulation of an actionable staged plan to link the two, where feasible using TN. It concludes that such thermal energy planning is a prerequisite for large-scale decarbonization including required infrastructure investment. The provincial government could facilitate such energy planning by ensuring that municipalities have access to the data they require.

Section 11 concludes – chiefly adducing evidence from Oujé-Bougoumou in Quebec – that district energy is technically and economically feasible for many Indigenous communities, especially where there are major cold-weather challenges. Also, district energy is more adaptable, makes greater use of local resources and offers the flexibility to incorporate emerging technologies.

Section 12 touches on the decarbonization-related challenges faced by local electricity distribution companies (LDCs). It concludes that with the electrification pathway LDCs would have to provide for dramatically higher peak demand requiring costly upgrades. The TN pathway would have minimal impact on LDCs, and may even free up capacity for EV charging and other electricity uses.

13.2. Overall conclusion from our analysis

The analyses set out in this report point to an overwhelming conclusion: current policies favouring wholesale electrification of space heating fail to properly consider the major expansion of electricity supply that would be required and associated costs; deployment of thermal networks that serve most building space in Ontario – and in Canada generally - will not only be less costly, but likely the only viable pathway to net-zero heating of buildings. The extent of feasible TN deployment in a particular region, municipality, district or neighbourhood needs to be determined by rigorous application of the kind of thermal energy planning described in Section 10, conducted by municipalities with support from other governments.

Our analyses suggest that such thermal energy planning will point to substantial TN deployment for some or all these reasons:

- **Capital costs:** Overall for Ontario, a strategy centred on TN deployment is estimated to require less than half the investment required for wholesale electrification of space heating. At the building level, owners' capital costs will be lower because most such costs would be borne by the district energy utility.
- **Operating costs:** Substantial cost increases for building owners and operators are expected with the electrification pathway. Smaller increases are expected with the TN pathway.

- **Grid impact:** The TN pathway will make more efficient use of existing and new electricity system infrastructure. Wholesale electrification will require much upgrading to generation, distribution, and in-building equipment that will have low rates of utilization.
- **Technical feasibility:** The electrification pathway would seem to require massive and unrealizable labour and equipment requirements. Experience from elsewhere suggests that requirements for the TN pathway are manageable.
- **Time to deploy:** Time to deploy: For electrification, the expectation that owners will retrofit their buildings to achieve major reduction of heat demand is unrealistic, and not consistent with evidence from Canada and elsewhere. Electricity providers have no plans to supply the power that would be required by ASHPs deployed at-scale; power system limitations are likely to forestall such conversion to ASHPs. Conversion to TNs does not rely on building retrofits; progressive implementation of TN utilities must be done strategically, but, supported by large-scale thermal energy storage, is both feasible and economical.

13.3. Broader conclusions and synthesis for sustainability

Our comprehensive analysis leads to several overarching conclusions:

- **Tailored, hybrid Implementation:** Neither pathway is a panacea. Instead, the optimal decarbonization strategy involves a hybrid approach—using district energy systems in urban and high-density areas for cost-effective, integrated thermal storage and energy recovery, alongside selective electrification in rural settings via ground-source heat pumps. This tailored strategy ensures that technological, economic, and infrastructural choices align with local conditions and priorities.
- **Economic and societal benefits:** The transformational changes required by either pathway are substantial but come with profound opportunities for national revitalization. Beyond energy efficiency and reduced GHG emissions, these initiatives can drive new investments, technological breakthroughs, employment, and improved fiscal conditions for governments. The associated infrastructural upgrades promote technological innovation and have significant positive impacts on public health, community well-being, and social equity.
- **Long-term infrastructure and policy support:** Achieving net-zero emissions and ensuring a reliable, sustainable energy future require coordinated policy reforms, long-term infrastructure planning, and active municipal involvement. Robust thermal energy planning, streamlined permitting processes, and supportive fiscal policies are essential. The eventual benefits—both direct and spillover—will influence every Canadian citizen's daily life for decades to come.
- **Nation-Building Opportunities:** The scale and scope of decarbonizing building heating transcend technical challenges—they embody opportunities to reshape how energy is produced, distributed, and consumed. If managed strategically, these initiatives can catalyze the creation of new industries and set a precedent for transformative, sustainable development across the nation.

In summary, while the electrification pathway offers a vision of a fully decarbonized grid and heating, it faces significant technical and economic hurdles that make it a high-risk, high-investment option. In contrast, the district energy (TN) pathway, supported by affordable thermal storage and modular deployment, presents a far more viable, cost-effective, and equitable solution in urban environments. A careful, hybrid deployment—sensitive to regional needs and supported by proactive policy and planning—offers the most promising path to achieving Canada’s ambitious decarbonization targets.

Moving forward, further research and stakeholder engagement are essential to refine these models, explore innovative financing mechanisms, and ensure that the transformative changes foster resilient communities and a sustainable future.

Appendix - Energy Basics

Whether it is delivered as electricity, heat or in some other form, all energy used by modern societies has to come from primary sources. Those primary sources are nuclear and chemical materials stored at accessible depths beneath the Earth's surface, primeval heat from deeper in the Earth, and radiant energy from the sun. Solar energy, combined with rotational and orbital inertial motions of the Earth and the moon, leads to weather, winds and tides, and redistribution of water to higher elevations. The sun also powers photosynthesis and production of wood and other biological materials that can later be used as fuels.

Large-scale extraction and combustion of fossil fuels - coal, oil, methane, propane, etc. - to produce heat and, from heat, electricity has resulted in GHG emissions and unacceptable global warming. Such use of fossil fuels must be curtailed as rapidly as possible to avoid a climate catastrophe. That leaves nuclear fuels, heat from deep in the Earth, and the sun (and wind and tides, hydropower and biofuels) as the confidently known energy sources for a zero-emissions, sustainable future.

The supplies of energy from the sun and from deep within the Earth will last billions of years. Stores of nuclear fuel for fission reactors are more limited: uranium could last hundreds of years; advanced fuel cycles could continue providing nuclear power for thousands of years (Pevco, Knapp and Trontl, 2012). If nuclear fusion technology becomes economic its fuel supply would be effectively unlimited, but limited supplies of other materials needed for fusion reactors could pose severe constraints on long-term viability. Long-term storage and disposal of nuclear waste materials, from both fission and fusion reactors, may also constrain the long-term use of nuclear energy.

There are claims that large quantities of hydrogen gas (H_2) might be available and economically extracted from deep in the Earth's crust (geologic hydrogen), but both the availability and economic viability have yet to be demonstrated (Patonia et al. 2018). For these reasons, geologic hydrogen will not be considered further in this report.

Energy received from the sun is 10,000 times more than is used by humanity; over a year it averages 340 W/m^2 (in Canada, about 200 W/m^2). Solar radiation reaches the Earth's surface at a temperature of about $5,250 \text{ C}$ - far above the $1,960 \text{ C}$ combustion temperature of natural gas. Mature technology exists to recover solar energy, both as electricity and as heat, in quantities and temperatures that are comparable to societal needs. (This includes energy obtained from wind, tides and flows of water from higher to lower elevations.) The production of biofuels is limited, by thermodynamic constraints on photosynthesis, to about 1 W/m^2 in Canada (Kleidon 2021), of which only a small fraction could be feasibly recovered from forestry and other waste products.

By contrast, the upward flow of energy at the Earth's surface from deep within averages a paltry 0.082 W/m^2 at a mean temperature of 15 C . The ability of technological advancements to enable economic, large-scale recovery of deep geothermal energy at higher temperatures remains unproven and speculative. Geothermal heat is not a significant consideration in this report.

In common parlance, energy is *consumed* when it is used. In truth, it is not; the amount of energy never changes. Fuels may be consumed, but that just converts the energy they hold into an equal amount of energy in different forms. If the conversion is carefully managed, then value can be derived by performing useful work. Ultimately, all energy is converted to heat. Unavoidable interactions of systems result in the temperature of the heat dropping until it comes to equilibrium with the environment. Thermal energy at the temperature of the environment has lost all its value.

The term *exergy* is used to indicate the quantity of work that energy in a given form is capable of performing in a given environment. Highly organized energy, such as is provided in the form of electric power, has almost as much exergy as energy. Whenever energy is used to perform useful work, some exergy is consumed. With care, the remaining exergy can be used for other useful purposes. Eventually, all that is left will be heat at the same temperature as the environment and *exergy* = 0.

When a CANDU reactor uses uranium to produce electric power, the first step is to heat primary heat transport fluid to about 310 C. That heat is used to produce high pressure steam that then drives turbine generators. About 30% of the released nuclear energy is converted to electricity while 70% becomes heat at about 35 C. That low-temperature heat is released to the environment which makes it useless. The exergy utilized is 30% of the released nuclear energy.

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